

Bioeconomy and bio-based innovations: Identifying key levers for delivering the EU Green Deal targets

Authors:

Maria Serena Mancini (GFN), Katsunori Iha (GFN), Tin-Yu Lai (SYKE), Sampo Pihlainen (SYKE), Marta Antonelli (GFN), David Lin (GFN), Nicolas Robert (EEA), Gorm Dige (EEA), Alessandro Galli (GFN)

Cover image AI-generated with deepAi.org
Layout: Claudia Neitzel (NIVA)

Version: 2

Publication Date: July 2025

Legal notice

Preparation of this working paper has been co-funded by the European Environment Agency as part of a grant with the European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems and expresses the views of the authors. The contents of this publication do not necessarily reflect the position or opinion of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union. Neither the European Environment Agency nor the European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems is liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of the information contained in this publication.

ETC-BE coordinator: Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)

ETC-BE partners: Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN), Association BIOPOLIS (Biopolis), Brilliant Solutions Engineering & Consulting (BRIS), Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, Aarhus University (DCE-AU), Deltares, Dark Matter Laboratories B.V. (DML), Ecologic Institute (Ecologic), Environment Agency Austria (EAA), Fresh Thoughts Consulting GmbH (Fresh Thoughts), Global Footprint Network (GFN), Hot or Cool Institute gGmbH (HoC), International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), French national institute for industrial environment and risks (INERIS), Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA), LESPROJEKT-SLUŽBY Ltd (LESP), Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg (MLU), Sapienza University Rome (SAP), Seascope Belgium (SSBE), Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE), Thematic Center for Water Research, Studies and Project Development, Ltd. (TC Vode), German Environment Agency (UBA-DE), University Duisburg-Essen (UDE), Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ)

Copyright notice

© European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems, 2025

Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged. [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (International)]

More information on the European Union is available on the Internet (<http://europa.eu>).

How to cite this working paper:

Mancini, M. S., Iha, K., Lai, TY, Pihlainen, S., Antonelli, M., Lin, D., Robert, N., Dige, G., Galli, A., (2025). Bioeconomy and bio-based innovations: identifying key levers for delivering the EU Green Deal targets (ETC BE working paper). European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and Ecosystems.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15305940

European Topic Centre on
Biodiversity on ecosystems
<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-be>

Content

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
1. INTRODUCTION	14
1.1 The global and EU contexts and policy background.....	14
1.2 Defining the European bioeconomy: the Bioeconomy Strategy and the Bioeconomy Action Plan	15
1.3 Previous bioeconomy studies: literature review and gaps identification	16
1.4 Aim and structure of the report	16
2. PART I – The most promising solutions to fuel the bioeconomy	18
2.1. Identification of key economic sectors.....	19
2.1.1. Methodology	19
2.1.1.1. Economic sectors driving the Human Footprints	19
2.1.1.2. Potential of economic sectors for innovation: supporting MRIO analysis	24
2.1.2. Key Output: primary sectors for implementing bio-based innovations.....	25
2.1.2.1. Economic sectors driving the Footprint Externalities: Ecological, Carbon, Cropland and Forest Footprints	25
2.1.2.1.1 Ecological Footprint (gha).....	26
2.1.2.1.2 Carbon Footprint (t CO2).....	33
2.1.2.1.3 Cropland Footprint (ha).....	38
2.1.2.1.4 Forest Footprint (ha)	42
2.1.2.2. Economic potential of innovations by economic sector: Supporting MRIO analysis	45
2.2. Existing Bio-based innovations: Introduction.....	53
2.2.1. Methodology of innovation research and criteria of selection.....	55
2.2.2. The final review framework and the list of Bio-based innovations.....	57
2.3. Part I - combined results: Prioritization and selection of the most promising bio-based innovations in the key economic sectors for a sustainable European future.....	70
2.3.1. Final list of innovations and sectors of application	70
2.3.2. Outcomes of experts’ workshop	72
3. PART II – Key levers for the European bioeconomy: assessing the implementation and scalability potential of selected bio-based innovations	74
3.1. Introduction.....	74
3.2. Level of implementation of the 23 selected innovations in 32 EEA countries.....	77
3.2.1. Methodology	77
3.2.2. Results of level of implementation.....	77
3.3. Scalability potential: the status of assessment on scalability potential of the 23 selected innovations	79

3.3.1.	Methodology	79
3.3.1.1.	Techno-economic assessment and Life cycle assessment (LCA)	80
3.3.1.2.	Environmental contributions: positive or negative	81
3.3.1.3.	Employment evaluation and social acceptance	81
3.3.2.	Analysis status of the 23 innovations (Results)	82
3.3.2.1.	Case by case analysis of upscaling – upsizing innovations below TRL 7	85
3.3.2.2.	Case by case analysis of Upscaling – industrialization and massification of innovations at TRL7 or above	88
4.	CONCLUSIONS	93
5.	REFERENCES.....	95
6.	GLOSSARY	107
7.	ANNEXES.....	110

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background to this study

Unsustainable trends in socio-economic practices have disrupted Earth's stability and biophysical dynamics over the past decades. Numerous studies reveal that human-induced destabilization of key Earth systems is triggering a domino effect, leading to a decline in global biodiversity. This jeopardizes the well-being of future generations. To address and reverse these trends, substantial changes are necessary in our societal connection with nature, along with transformative policy and investment decisions to rethink and reshape production and consumption patterns.

The UN's 2030 Agenda, the Paris Agreement, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, and the EU Green Deal provide essential frameworks for national and global cooperation on sustainable development. The European Green Deal outlines a strategy for a fair, inclusive, and sustainable EU economy that respects planetary boundaries by addressing climate change and the biodiversity crisis. However, despite these agreements, global greenhouse gas emissions in 2010-2019 surpassed those of any previous decade, and current contributions are projected to lead to a median warming of 2.6°C - 3.1°C by 2100. The recent UNFCCC Global Stocktake report (UNFCCC, 2023a) indicates that national climate action plans "remain insufficient to limit global temperature rise to 1.5°C and meet the goals of the Paris Agreement". Achieving these targets requires significant decarbonization efforts and widespread system transformations across all sectors (see Section 1.1).

A shift towards a circular bioeconomy can help Europe to reach its Green Deal objectives while easing the achievement of the Paris Agreement. The EU Bioeconomy Strategy emphasizes the bioeconomy's role in: (1) ensuring food security, (2) managing natural resources sustainably, (3) reducing dependence on non-renewable resources, (4) mitigating and adapting to climate change, and (5) creating jobs and maintaining EU competitiveness. However, not all bioeconomic activities may reduce GHGs emissions or mitigate human impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity: the rise of new technologies using biological and renewable resources could intensify competition for biomass – thus placing pressure on ecosystems and biodiversity – in Europe and the rest of the world. The expansion of biomass production for the bioeconomy might also lead to land use conflicts, particularly if it competes with food production or intrudes upon natural habitats. Balancing these competing demands is crucial to prevent negative ecological and social outcomes: beyond substituting fossil-based resources, a fair, inclusive and sustainable EU economy requires environmentally friendly supply chains (see Section 1.2).

Rationale and methodology used

Although numerous studies have explored the bioeconomy's potential for driving a green transition (see Section 1.3), a notable gap remains in our understanding of the role existing bioeconomy innovations can have in meeting the EU bioeconomy objectives. This report aims to fill this gap by examining whether innovations resulting from R&D investments since the first EU Bioeconomy Strategy in 2012 can support achieving the goals of the EU Green Deal.

This report thus provides a first stocktaking of the implementation of bio-based innovations, seeking to determine if the EU's emphasis on innovation over the past decade has yielded meaningful solutions. More precisely, it identifies the key bio-based innovations in priority sectors of the EU economy that stand a higher chance to support the transition called for by the EU Green Deal and trigger major improvements in the EU Bioeconomy. It focuses on those bioeconomic activities in key industrial processes that can have the highest

potential – if adequately scaled up – to help mitigating climate change and protect and restore biodiversity, while providing economic and social opportunities. We refer to them as “game changing” innovations.

Accordingly, three key research questions have guided the production of this report:

- Which bio-based innovations and in which sectors of the economy will bring about the necessary changes in the EU production and consumption activities thus helping our societies realize the needed green transition?
- Are there bio-based innovations applicable across the wider economy that can have scalable impact?
- What is their technological readiness and the level of their acceptance by the EU society?

A multi-step process was used (see Figure A) to identify the key bio-based innovations whose implementation could be scaled-up in priority sectors of the EU economies.

1. An environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) analysis allowed identifying the sectors of the EEA-32 region’s economies in which bio-based innovations are most needed given these sectors’ key role as driver of human footprints on the planet; ecological, carbon, cropland and forest footprints were considered to assess multiple environmental externalities (related to biomass use and carbon emissions) of key importance for bioeconomy considerations;
2. A review of the literature allowed identifying the potential – from a socio-economic viewpoint – for innovations to happen in the identified sectors, as technology exists and the implementation of bio-based innovation would bring high social (e.g., jobs) and economic (e.g., profit) effects;
3. A review of scientific papers and grey literature allowed mapping the existing bio-based innovations that stand a higher chance to contribute to the achievement of the European Green Deal, and the environmental and socio-economic contributions (i.e., positive or negative impacts) they would bring to society;
4. The development and application of a multi-criteria review framework (see Section 2.2.2), and experts’ feedback allowed shortlisting the most promising bio-based innovations in key economic sectors (i.e., those in which innovation is both most needed and possible);
5. A review of existing case studies and ongoing projects helped determining the current level of implementation of the shortlisted innovations throughout Europe, distinguishing between innovations with a TRL of 5-6 and innovations with a TRL ≥ 7 ;
6. Finally, the definition of key criteria to assess the “upscaling potential” of innovations (distinguishing *upsizing from laboratory to industrial scale from industrialization and massification*) and a literature review allowed identifying priority “game changing” innovations, as well as eventual gaps in our current scalability knowledge.

Figure A. Bioeconomy and bio-based innovations: steps used in this working paper for identifying key levers for delivering the EU Green Deal targets.

Key findings of this study

The use of an EE-MRIO analysis allowed us to analyse the whole supply chain of each of the 65 sectors of the EU economy (as defined by the GTAP model), thus shedding light on the multiple environmental externalities that are associated with these sectors.

Results of the ecological footprint analysis (see Section 2.1.2.1.1) – a measure of the Earth’s biocapacity needed to produce the primary resources that the sector uses, and to sequester the CO₂ emissions that the sector releases in the environment – show that the ecosystems of the EEA-32 region are able to supply only about half of the biocapacity needed to satisfy the final demands of the region’s residents, thus indicating a potential imbalance between resource availability and human consumption. More importantly, about half (48%) of the region’s total Ecological Footprint is driven by the final demand (by households, governments and businesses) for the outputs of just 10 of the 65 sectors that constitute the EEA-32 region’s economy (see Figure 3 in the main text). Among these 10 sectors, a key role is played by the *Construction* Sector and by several economic activities related to *Food* and *Transportation*¹ (see Table A). Ecological Footprint results – used here as an overarching umbrella indicator – also show that economic activities within the EEA-32 region place the highest pressures upon the carbon sequestration capacity of the earth’s ecosystems, followed by the capacity of croplands and forests to produce biomass (see Table 1 in the main text). This called for a detailed assessment of each of these 3 sub-components.

Table A. Key sectors driving the EU footprints. This table summarizes the top 5 economic sectors that contribute the most to the results of each footprint, including highly contributing countries within the EEA-32 region in each respective sectors.

Ecological Footprint		Carbon Footprint		Cropland Footprint		Forest Footprint	
Sectors	EEA countries						
Construction	1.France 2.Germany 3.Turkey	Construction	1.Germany 2.France 3.Turkey	Food products nec	1.Germany 2.France 3.Turkey	Forestry	1.Germany 2.France 3.Turkey
Accommodation, Food and service activities	1.Italy 2.Germany 3.France	Transport nec	1.Italy 2.Germany 3.Turkey	Accommodation, Food and service activities	1.Spain 2.Italy 3.Turkey	Construction	1.France 2.Sweden 3.Finland
Food products nec	1.Germany 2.France 3.Spain	Electricity	1.Germany 2.Poland 3.Turkey	Wheat	1.Italy 2.Turkey 3.Germany	Manufactures nec	1.Germany 2.France 3.Turkey
Transport nec	1.Italy 2.Germany 3.Turkey	Trade	1.Germany 2.Italy 3.France	Vegetables, fruit, nuts	1.Germany 2.Turkey 3.France	Wood products	1.Germany 2.Austria 3.Poland
Trade	1.Germany 2.Italy 3.France	Accommodation, Food and service activities	1.Germany 2.Italy 3.France	Beverages and tobacco products	1.Germany 2.Turkey 3.France	Accommodation, Food and service activities	1.Italy 2.Poland 3.Germany

Results of the carbon footprint analysis (see Section 2.1.2.1.2) – a measure of the amount of CO₂ emissions released into the environment by each economic sector – show a similar trend, with 10 out of 65 sectors contributing to more than 56% of the region’s carbon footprint, including *Construction*, *Transport* and *Electricity*. Results of the cropland footprint analysis (see Section 2.1.2.1.3) – a measure of the amount of arable land and permanent crops required to produce crop products, including livestock feed, fishmeal, oil crops, and rubber, used by each economic sector – and of the forest footprint analysis (see Section 2.1.2.1.4)

¹ The top 3 sectors – according to the GTAP classification system – are *Construction* (GTAP Sector 49), *Accommodation, food, service activities* (GTAP 51), and *Food product nec* (GTAP 25). See Annex 1 for a detailed description of each sector, their correspondence to the CPC (Central Product Classification) and ISIC (International Standard Industry Classification) classifications of the UN, and their aggregation into broader categories of the economy, which is performed here to ease the link between sectors and innovations.

– a measure of the area of forests needed by each sector to supply fuelwood and timber for forest products – complement the analysis by providing further details on the specific activities driving the demand for crop and forest biomass, respectively (Table A).

The main outcomes of the EE-MRIO analysis are that bio-based innovations would be most needed in the construction, food and agriculture, transportation, and energy/electricity sectors given the role these sectors have in driving the EEA-32 region's footprints on the planet. Results also points to the EEA-32 countries in which the implementation of such innovations should be prioritized, as activities in these countries drive the footprints of the considered sector. Although priority countries differ on the basis of the sector and externality considered, some convergence is found on countries such as France, Germany, Italy, Spain and Turkey (see Table A). Further investigations on the dependencies and interlinkages among sectors, however, shows that reducing the footprints linked to key sector of the EEA-32 region's economy (e.g., *Construction*) may necessitate prioritizing investments in bio-based innovations across key interconnected sectors (e.g., *Forestry, Transport, Electricity, or the Mineral Products* sectors), as well as changes in the production practices outside of the EEA-32 region (e.g., China), or changes in international trade relationships.

Finding from the literature review of MRIO studies and sector analyses confirm a middle to high economic potential for innovations to happen in the construction, food and agriculture, and transportation sectors, as increased production or new job opportunities associated with the implementation of bio-based innovations in these sectors would bring about additional job opportunities, wage changes, and income expansion across interconnected sectors, ultimately leading to wider economic growth (see Section 2.1.2.2). Economic potential was found to be lower in the energy/electricity sector compared to other sectors, while a low to high potential for innovations was also found for the textile sector (see Table 18 of the main text). Even though the energy/electricity sector has lower economic potential to stimulate the whole economy, innovations in the energy/electricity, construction, and transportation sectors still have the potential to open the market and create new job opportunities (see Table 19 of the main text).

But what bio-based innovations exist and which one of them will bring about the necessary changes in the EU production and consumption activities to address the climate and biodiversity crises while helping our societies realize the needed green transition? A comprehensive review of multiple sources (see Section 2.2.1) allowed us to identify a list of approximately 90 bio-based innovations (see Annex 7). Screening of such list through the lenses of the review framework (see Section 2.2.2) developed through the course of the project allowed prioritizing 23 single innovations, each derived from one (or more) of the 5 identified biomass types and implemented into one (or more) of the 6 key sectors of the EEA-32 region's economy (see Figure B).

Figure B. Final list of 23 shortlisted bio-based innovations. Connections are also shown with a) the specific biomass type from which the innovations originate (left side), and b) the economic sectors in which the innovations end-up being implemented (right side). Further details on each innovation and their complete assessment against the 26 parameters/criteria of the review framework are reported in Annex 10.

The most common biomass type used as a feedstock for the priority innovations is the agricultural biomass (8 innovations) derived from residues or waste feedstock of primary industries (i.e., bagasse, ashes, husk, fibres, stover, stubble) or processed food (i.e., waste food), followed by forest biomass as residues of the forestry industry (i.e., pulp and paper industries) and marine algae (primary biomass), which feed into 6 innovations each (see Section 2.3.1). Fish marine biomass (i.e., discards from the fishing industry) and industrial and municipal waste (i.e., urban sludges, organic waste) are used as feedstock in 4 and 3 innovations, respectively. Meanwhile, most innovations are implemented in the food sector, including derived and processed animal- and vegetable-based food (11 innovations). Most of the other innovations fall under Other sectors, and mainly consists of bio-chemicals and bio-polymers. The Energy/Electricity sector is also characterized by multiple bio-based innovations such as those related to the production of biogas and biofuels as alternative energy sources. Bio-based innovations in the Agriculture sector (i.e., primary products and processes) consist primarily of bio-fertilizers and agroforestry practices. Finally, 5 innovations relate to the Textile sector, 3 to the Construction sector, and 2 to the Transportation sector as bioenergy for aviation and shipping.

Most (14) of the shortlisted bio-innovations contribute to the EU Bioeconomy Strategy's ambition of *"reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad"* as they use food waste, agriculture residues or forestry by-product as feedstocks to reduce the use of primary natural resources; conversely, only a few innovations (e.g., those dealing with alternative fuels for aviation and shipping sectors, and those using advanced technologies for converting urban waste feedstock into biopolymers and biogas) help address the objectives of *"Mitigating and adapting to climate change"* and of *"strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs"*. Algae constitute another recurring primary feedstock, at least for those bio-based innovations supporting the ambition of *"managing natural resources sustainably"* as they have a high potential to be used in bio-refineries for the production of bio-energy, as alternative food and feeds (thus also contributing to the ambition of *"Ensuring food and nutrition security"*), and biochemicals. Overall, most of these bio-based innovations follow a very precise transformative pathway, that is to increase the efficiency in the use of biomass (e.g., by leveraging by-products, residues and waste) and to create new ways of using biomass (by means of new technologies), with the ultimate goal to substitute fossil-based with bio-based resources (see Section 3.1).

Our assessment of the current level of implementation of the 23 bio-based innovations in the EEA region shows a heterogeneous situation (see Section 3.2.2). Although innovations have different technology readiness levels across the countries of the EEA-32 region, our findings indicate that most of them have passed TRL 7 and are mainly implemented in Northern Europe (e.g., Germany, Poland, the Netherlands) and Scandinavian countries; with the exception of a few innovations in France (e.g., poultry feathers to produce bioplastics, waste from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food for human use), Slovenia (e.g., wood material in the construction industry), and Spain (e.g., lignin-based asphalt, urban biowaste for the production of insect/microbial proteins for food/feeds), a lack of implementation in an operational environment was found for these 23 bio-based innovations in Southern Europe. Moreover, a few innovations (e.g., macro-algae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent) have been solely tested in laboratory and information on their actual implementation at country level is currently lacking. A further review of the literature of existing case studies could potentially close some of these geographical gaps.

Finally, our combined review of existing assessments of the 1) techno-economic feasibility, 2) environmental contributions (i.e., impacts and/or benefits), 3) feedstocks' availability, 4) employment potential, and 5) societal acceptance, of innovations – which altogether we deem critical aspects to inform about the potential scalability of a bio-based innovation – show that most innovations have reached the necessary technological

and economic readiness for further upscaling (see Section 3.3.2, Table 30). “Climate change” is most commonly included in environmental assessments, followed by “land use/land use change”, although gaps exist in our understanding of the biodiversity- and ecosystem-services-related implications of implementing bio-based innovations. Feedstock availability assessments have been conducted – at least qualitatively – for most of the feedstock types, although more precise information on the feedstock type would be needed for nearly one-third of the 23 bio-based innovations to be able to conduct quantitative feedstock availability assessments. Major gaps exist in our knowledge of the effects on employment of bringing innovations to their full upscaling potential as assessments of the employment implications are missing for all but one (i.e., Wood as sustainable material in construction) of the 23 bio-based innovations. Meanwhile, assessments of societal acceptance are more commonly available or can be indirectly derived from other information in the literature. Further details on each of these five aspects for the 23 shortlisted bio-based innovations can be found in section 3.3.2 of the main text.

Conclusions and way forward

Against the goal of this report – *to identify key bio-based innovations in priority sectors of the EU economy that would stand a higher chance to support the transition called for by the EU Green Deal* – we identified 23 innovations that use by-products, residuals or waste from agricultural, forest, marine, or industrial/municipal waste biomass as feedstock to bring about innovations in 6 key sectors: *Construction, Food, Agriculture, Transportation, Energy/electricity, and Textile*. We also identified a list of priority countries (e.g., France, Germany, Italy, Spain and Turkey) in which the implementation of such innovations should be prioritized, as activities in the above-mentioned 6 sectors of these countries drive the EEA-32 region’s footprints. Comparing these countries against those in which these 23 innovations are currently primarily implemented (i.e., mainly Northern European and Scandinavian countries), however, shows a mismatch, and calls for 1) further investments in the implementation of these innovations in Southern European countries, and 2) north-south sharing of knowledge and practical experiences within the EEA region (see Section 4).

An initial analysis of the interdependencies that the 6 priority sectors of the EEA-32 region’s economy have with other sectors and economies (including outside of the region) also indicates that reducing EEA-32 footprints and moving towards the EU Green Deal ambitions could require investments in bio-based innovations across key interconnected sectors, as well as abroad. Further research, however, would be needed to better understand these interconnections and identify all the stages of key supply chains (including intermediate steps); further research would be also needed to distinguish (and quantify) the impacts associated with the bio-based sectors of the economy from the impacts of the non-bio-based activities of the classical economy, also considering the economic value added generate by the bio-economy vs. the rest of the economy.

Finally, the evaluation of the 23 shortlisted innovations indicates that we have knowledge about the economic feasibility and climate effects of scaling them up. However, there are significant gaps in our understanding of the potential impacts on biodiversity and employment. A full-scale implementation of these innovations may thus help decarbonize the European economy at the expenses of potential impacts on land-use and biodiversity. Still, our analysis highlights innovations using algal biomass as the most promising, as algae can be grown in labs or sourced from the marine environment, contributing to nutrient removal. They have diverse applications across various sectors, including food-related uses, without competing for land designated for food production. However, uncertainties persist regarding the trade-offs between the impacts of biorefineries and their potential benefits, requiring further research. Innovations using agricultural

biomass also show promise across six key sectors, but their impact on soil quality and biodiversity, especially when removing agro-biomass residuals from croplands, needs further understanding. Bio-based innovations utilizing discarded marine fish biomass for human consumption, such as fish pulp and surimi, have high technological readiness and economic potential, although their environmental contributions are not fully clear. To comprehend the biodiversity and ecosystem-service implications, as well as potential job creation impacts, further research is needed for all the mentioned innovations. A “what if” scenario assessment to foresee the environmental implications of upscaling the 23 key innovations could not be performed in this task, suggesting it as a crucial next step (at least for climate implications, for which data is more readily available), in the potential continuation of *Task 1.2.7.2 – Bioeconomy as Solution Provider* in the coming years.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The global and EU contexts and policy background

Over the last decade, a growing number of studies have highlighted how human activities have altered the planet's biophysical dynamics and the urgent need for unsustainable economic and social trends to be reversed (Barnosky et al., 2012; Davis et al., 2016; Bjørn et al 2018; Steffen et al., 2018). These studies indicate that humans have perpetuated an exponential growth, contributing to a decline in the global biodiversity (Butchart et al., 2010; Tittensor et al., 2014), which destabilizes the planet (Steffen et al., 2015), and puts the foundations of the health and wellbeing – in all three dimensions of social, environmental and economic – of future generations at risk (Diaz et al., 2019; O'Neill et al., 2018). To stop these losses and revert the trends, societal actors - from civil society to policy makers - must revise policy choices (including incentives) and investment decisions, stimulate long-term changes in beliefs and social norms (Kinzig et al., 2013), and transform production and consumption activities, including via technology and innovation (TWI2050, 2020). To provide a comprehensive roadmap towards a sustainable and climate-resilient future, the 2030 Agenda of the UN with its 17 SDGs, the Paris Agreement, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, and the EU Green Deal are interconnected frameworks for promoting sustainable development, as well as climate and biodiversity actions to be achieved through regional and global cooperation and efforts.

The EU is faced with sustainability challenges that include pollution, biodiversity loss, resource use and climate change. The Ecological Footprint of the EU-27 already exceeds the region's biocapacity (Galli et al. 2023), most of the planetary boundaries are now transgressed and overall biophysical dynamics and stability of the Earth are altered (Richardson et al., 2023). Achieving sustainability requires a substantial and comprehensive transformation of key systems — the way we produce, transform and distribute our food as well as the amount we waste of it; the way we produce and consume goods; the way we build and organize our cities, and manage the protection of key biodiversity areas. This is needed to boost resilience while mitigating and adapting to the impacts of climate change and resource constraints (EEA, 2020). The European Green Deal (EC, 2019) sets out a new growth strategy for a more sustainable EU economy that better respects planetary boundaries by tackling both climate change and biodiversity crises. It contributes to the achievement of the SDGs, aligns with the objectives of the Paris Agreement, and positions the EU as a global leader in climate action by ambitiously setting as a target the decarbonization of the EU by 2050.

Despite such global agreements and regional processes, average annual global GHG emissions during 2010-2019 were higher than in any previous decade, and nationally determined contributions (NDCs) will likely lead to a median warming of 2.6°C - 3.1°C by 2100 (Rogelj et al., 2016). Meeting the 2°C by 2100 target of the Paris Agreement requires a major decarbonization of our economies and societies, with a doubling of the efforts compared to what countries committed to with their NDCs (Liu et al., 2021). In 2022 at the fifteenth meeting of the Conference of the Parties (COP 15), the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework was adopted to support the achievements of the SDGs and reach the global vision of a world in harmony with Nature by 2050. Specifically, 4 goals for 2050 and 23 targets for 2030 have been set out as an ambitious plan to implement broad-based actions to bring about a transformation in our societies' relationship with biodiversity. A need thus exists to tackle climate change and the biodiversity crisis at the same time, while allowing for a just and sustainable transition of our economies and societies.

1.2 Defining the European bioeconomy: the Bioeconomy Strategy and the Bioeconomy Action Plan

“The bioeconomy is a central element to the functioning and success of the EU economy” (EC, 2018: 5). It has been estimated that it accounts for almost 9% of the EU-27 labour force, 4.7% of the EU-27 GDP and include more than 2,300 bio-based plants (Ronzon et al. 2020; Parisi et al. 2020). A shift towards a circular bioeconomy, as described in the European Bioeconomy Strategy (EC, 2018), can contribute to achieving decarbonization, helping Europe to reach its Green Deal objectives while easing the achievement of the Paris Agreement. The strategy has also been linked afterwards to the post-Covid recovery by improving resilience, competitiveness and ensuring a just transition through systemic solutions (Galanakis et al., 2022).

The bioeconomy is defined as “an economy that covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources, their functions and principles; it is an economy that stays within planetary limits through reducing, reusing, and recycling materials for rebalancing production and consumption” (EC, 2018). Innovation in the bioeconomy might have the capacity to support a reduction in GHGs emissions, or to reduce the impacts of human activities on ecosystems. But, the emergence of many new technologies using biomass, may also trigger an increased competition for resources thus intensifying the pressure on ecosystems – and on biodiversity – in Europe and the rest of the world. As such, a need exists for careful resource management and conservation efforts to mitigate any negative consequences on biodiversity and ecosystems.

The first bioeconomy strategy was adopted in 2012 by the European Commission, with a second updated version released and adopted in 2018. Both versions focus on the use of biological and renewable resources, while only the 2018 version encompasses ecosystem services and processes in addition. In fact, the purpose of the updated European Bioeconomy Strategy is “to further develop a bioeconomy that valorises and preserves ecosystems and biological resources, drives the renewal of our industries and the modernization of our primary production systems through bio-based innovation, involves local stakeholders, protects the environment and enhances biodiversity” (EC, 2018: 4).

The 2012 Bioeconomy Strategy’s aim to pave “the way to a more innovative, resource efficient and competitive society that reconciles food security with the sustainable use of renewable resources for industrial purposes, while ensuring environmental protection” (EC, 2012) still holds in the 2018 updated version, as well as its five objectives: (1) ensuring food security, (2) managing natural resources sustainably, (3) reducing dependence on non-renewable resources, (4) mitigating and adapting to climate change, and (5) creating jobs and maintaining EU competitiveness. In addition, the 2018 Bioeconomy Strategy develops a set of 14 concrete actions to adapt the scope of the five objectives in order to better use the potential of the bioeconomy to meet current and future EU priorities, such as the renewed Industrial Policy, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package. For this purpose, the updated strategy proposes action across a three-tiered action plan: to strengthen and scale-up the bio-based sectors, unlock investments and markets; to deploy local bioeconomies rapidly across Europe; to understand the ecological boundaries of the bioeconomy. To spur the transitions, the European Bioeconomy Strategy calls for the development of national and regional bioeconomy strategies in the EU. An assessment of the gaps in the current Action Plan includes the need for an increased focus on how to better manage land and biomass demands in a climate neutral Europe, as well as on sustainable consumption patterns for environmental integrity, and on how to close the ‘biomass gap’ between supply and demand from the food, materials and energy sectors (EC, 2022a).

The bioeconomy plays a vital role in achieving the objectives of the European Green Deal by driving the transition towards a sustainable, low-carbon, and resource-efficient economy as well as ensuring social fairness and a just transition. It combines environmental stewardship, economic development decoupled from resource consumption and carbon emissions, and social well-being, offering a pathway to a greener and more resilient future. “A sustainable bioeconomy is the renewable segment of the circular economy” (EC, 2018: 6). However, the fact that the bioeconomy is based on renewable resources does not make it intrinsically sustainable: beyond the substitution of fossil-based resources, sustainability requires sustainable supply chains, including sustainable biomass feedstock production and logistics, sustainable biomass conversion processes and sustainable products (Tan and Lamers, 2021). Moreover, the expansion of biomass production for the bioeconomy might lead to land use conflicts, particularly if it competes with food production or intrudes upon natural habitats. Balancing these competing demands is essential to prevent negative ecological and social outcomes.

Bio-based innovations have been at the core of the bioeconomy since the beginning, with huge investments in research and development. However, innovations are not spread uniformly across the EU as they are mainly concentrated in the central and western areas. Knowledge sharing and international collaboration is thus needed to allow for an even implementation across the region and an upscaling at the market level. We now need to understand where we are and if this has been fruitful in finding new solutions. To tackle such issues, this report identifies and carries out an assessment of the key bio-based innovations in priority economy sectors that could trigger major improvements in the EU Bioeconomy. As such, critical assessments are needed so that decision makers can support the development of the most promising solutions.

1.3 Previous bioeconomy studies: literature review and gaps identification

A number of studies have looked at the role bioeconomy can play in triggering a green transition, although most publications have focused on one product category or sector, such as Karvonen et al. (2017) on the forestry sector; on a restricted group of sectors and representative products (Sinkko et al., 2023), on regional aspects of the bioeconomy (Lakner et al., 2021; Philippidis et al., 2014) as well as on the circularity of bio-based products and their sustainable use of renewable natural resources (EEA, 2018). It has been shown that, between 2010 and 2020, the Footprint of the EU bioeconomy increased by 23%, with food consumption holding the highest share of total impacts (83–85%), followed by bioenergy (9–10%) (Sinkko et al., 2023). An EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System has been implemented to monitor progress of the EU bioeconomy with indicators covering value chain steps, sustainability pillars, primary production sectors (EC, 2021). Scenarios towards a sustainable, clean, and resource-efficient bioeconomy in the EU have also been developed (Fritsche et al., 2021); yet, a comprehensive picture of the bioeconomy innovations that currently exist and their applicability throughout the various sectors of the EU economies is still lacking. This report thus seeks to address this specific gap by setting out to understand whether some of the latest innovations that result from investments in R&D since the first bioeconomy strategy can make a change.

1.4 Aim and structure of the report

The aim of this report is to identify the key bio-based innovations in priority economy sectors that could stand a higher chance to support the transition called for by the EU Green Deal (EC, 2019) and trigger major improvements in the EU Bioeconomy. This report is an integral part of Task 1.2.7.2, whose objective is to identify which bioeconomic activities in key industrial processes can have the highest potential – if adequately scaled up – to help mitigating climate change and retain and restore biodiversity, while providing economic and social opportunities (i.e. game changers).

The research questions addressed in this report are as follows: which bio-based innovations and in which sectors of the economy will bring about the necessary changes in the EU production and consumption activities so that the current climate and biodiversity crisis can be addressed, helping our societies realize the needed green transition? Are there bio-based innovations applicable across the wider economy that can have scalable impact? What is their technological readiness and the level of their acceptance by the EU society? Answering these very questions is at the centre of this report.

The remainder of the report is divided into 2 parts. Part I presents the most promising innovations (i.e., solutions) to fuel the bioeconomy for a sustainable European future. Part II assesses the implementation and scalability potential of selected bio-based innovations to act as key levers for the European bioeconomy.

2. PART I – The most promising solutions to fuel the bioeconomy

To identify the key bio-based innovations in priority economy sectors that could stand a higher chance to support the transition called for by the EU Green Deal (EC, 2019) and trigger major improvements in the EU Bioeconomy, here we take a wider look at the economic structure of the EEA-32 region² via a multiple step process, structured as follows:

1. Through a combination of literature review and environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) analyses, we identify the industrial sectors in which bio-based innovations are both most needed and have the highest potential to happen (section 2.1).
2. In parallel, we conduct a review of existing bio-based innovations, scanning both scientific papers and grey literature, to identify the environmental and socio-economic contributions (i.e., positive or negative impacts) they bring to society (section 2.2).
3. Outcomes of the previous steps are jointly used to prioritize – based on a range of criteria – the most promising bio-based innovations in the key economic sectors for a sustainable European future (section 2.3).

The overall process of work of Part I, with its inner interconnections and the related sections where methodologies and outcomes are explained, is summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the work process of Part I of the Report, showing connections among the various steps and the related sections of the report where methodologies and outcomes can be found

² The 32 member countries of the European Environment Agency (see <https://www.eea.europa.eu/help/glossary/eea-glossary/eea-32>).

2.1. Identification of key economic sectors

Within this section, an environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) analysis is used to first identify the industrial sectors in which bio-based innovations are most needed given these sectors' key role as driver of human footprints on the planet (section 2.1.1.1). Such EE-MRIO analysis combines monetary and physical units to extend the GTAP 10 MRIO model (Andrew and Peters, 2013) with multiple environmental externalities (namely, ecological, carbon, cropland and forest footprints). Next, we complement the EE-MRIO analysis with a literature review on the highest potential – from a socio-economic viewpoint – for innovations to happen in the identified sectors, as technology exists and its implementation would bring the highest social (e.g., jobs) and economic (e.g., profit) return on investment (section 2.1.1.2). For each analysis, we first describe the methodology used (section 2.1.1) and then provide and discuss its results (section 2.1.2).

2.1.1. Methodology

2.1.1.1. Economic sectors driving the Human Footprints

In the realm of environmental studies, two main approaches are generally deployed: the consumer principle and the producer principle. The consumer principle assigns responsibility for environmental impacts to the end consumer, based on specific consumption habits. In contrast, the producer principle attributes the impacts originating from the production processes to the producers³.

For this task, we apply the consumer principle at a sectoral level within the global supply chain. This methodology allows us to analyse environmental externalities that are embedded throughout the lifecycle of goods and services, ranging from their production to their consumption and including cross-border trade. Consequently, we are able to identify the industrial sectors that are most in need of bio-based innovations, given their highest environmental externalities.

Conventionally, datasets related to environmental externalities, such as the carbon emission data from the International Energy Agency (IEA), are presented from the perspective of the producer principle. To implement our consumer-focused approach, we require a first step to recontextualize this data. We use a Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) model to systematically translate the data from the perspective of the producer principle to that of the consumer principle. The entire workflow for calculating the EEA-32 Footprints follows a three-steps methodology as outlined in Figure 2 and described here below:

- Step 1 involves the preparation of raw data for the environmental extension matrix.
- Step 2 comprises the development of an environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) model. This model integrates environmental extension matrix data (Ecological Footprint, Carbon emission, Cropland, and Forest land data) into the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) MRIO model, effectively transitioning data from the producer principle to the consumer principle and mapping various economic sectors' environmental externalities within final demand, considering global supply chain dynamics.
- Step 3 involves a sector analysis in the EEA-32 regions to identify the industrial sectors where bio-based innovations are most needed. Due to limited data availability from the GTAP model for Iceland and Liechtenstein, these two countries are excluded from the analysis. As such, the EEA-32 region's

³ For instance, if country A emits a certain amount of carbon while producing goods Z, the responsibility for this emission falls on country A as per the producer principle. On the other hand, under the consumer principle, if the goods Z are consumed in country B, the associated carbon emissions become the responsibility of the consumer in country B, irrespective of the production location.

analysis refers to 30 countries. Furthermore, as an in-depth investigation, a dependency analysis of the economic sectors across the value chain within and outside the EEA region is carried out.

The Flowchart of the Calculation Methodology

Step 1. Data Preparation for the Environmental Extension Matrix

Step 2. Environmentally Extended MRIO Analysis

Step 3: Economic Sector and Dependency Analysis in the EEA-32 Region

Figure 2. The flowchart of the calculation methodology for analysing the four Footprints in the EEA-32. Due to data quality issues in the NFBA and limited data availability from the GTAP model for Iceland and Liechtenstein, these two countries are excluded from the analysis. As such, the EEA-32 region's analysis refers to just 30 countries.

Step 1. Data Preparation for the Environmental Extension Matrix:

For the purposes of this Task, our focus lies on four environmental externalities: Ecological Footprint, Carbon Footprint, Cropland Footprint, and Forest Footprint (see Glossary). We first obtain production-based externality data from the National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts (NFBA; Footprint Data Foundation, 2023), IEA, and FAO sources and allocate it to the corresponding sectors based on GTAP 10⁴. Subsequently, we generate the environmental extension matrix by calculating the ratios of each Footprint's measurements (Ecological Footprint in global hectares, carbon emissions in metric tons of CO₂, cropland in hectares, and forest land in hectares) in relation to the total output (measured in US dollars) of each sector according to GTAP 10. The following paragraph provides a description of the data sources for each Footprint within the environmental extension matrix.

Ecological Footprint and Biocapacity data are obtained from the 2023 Edition of the NFBA. They track both the supply (biocapacity) and demand (Ecological Footprint) of renewable resources, along with ecosystem services. The 'demand' aspect of this model, the Ecological Footprint, measures the pressure humanity places on the Earth's ability to regenerate a particular subset of ecosystem services, in particular provisioning services (i.e. provisioning of natural resources) and one regulating service, that is the sequestration of CO₂ emissions by terrestrial ecosystems (Mancini et al., 2018). The Ecological Footprint framework identifies six categories of land providing such services: cropland, grazing land, fishing grounds, forests used for timber and non-timber products, built-up land, and land needed to sequester carbon dioxide emissions. The typical formula to compute the Ecological Footprint relevant to each category of land is as follows (Galli, 2015):

$$EF_f = \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{T_i}{Y_{w,i}} \times EQF_j$$

where

- i represents the input required for the production chain to generate the flow T .
- j corresponds to the six distinct types of ecological assets tracked by the Ecological Footprint analysis.
- $Y_{w,i}$ is the world-average (W) annual yield (in $t\ wha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) for the production of each product i , given by the tonnes of product, i , produced annually across the world divided by all areas in the world on which this product is grown.
- EQF_i is the equivalence factor for the land type producing each product i .

In contrast, Biocapacity tracks the capability of Earth's biologically productive areas to provide such provisioning and regulating ecosystem services. Biocapacity (BC) for each nation is quantified using the following formula:

$$BC = \sum_i A_{N,i} \cdot YF_{N,i} \cdot EQF_i$$

where

- $A_{N,i}$ represents the bioproductive area available for the production of a specific product i within the nation.
- $YF_{N,i}$ denotes the nation-specific yield factor for the land generating product i .

⁴ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v10/index.aspx>

- EQF_i indicates the equivalence factor⁵ for the land use category associated with product i .

Both Ecological Footprint and Biocapacity are measured in global hectares (gha), a standardized unit representing a hectare of land with an average global biological yield (Kitzes et al., 2007).

Carbon dioxide emission data is sourced from the International Energy Agency (IEA), which tracks emissions resulting from fossil fuel combustion across various economic sectors within a country's economy. In cases where IEA data is unavailable for a specific country, an estimation from the Carbon Dioxide Information Analysis Center is utilized⁶. To distribute the carbon emission data to each of the 65 sectors in the GTAP dataset, we determine the proportional share of total emissions for each sector using the existing energy-environmental extension within the GTAP dataset.

Cropland data is obtained from the UN's FAO ProdSTAT database. This data encompasses crops used for direct human consumption, as well as crops utilized for animal feed (such as alfalfa), fibres (like cotton), and other purposes (including tobacco and rubber). The system used for tracking agricultural production covers 177 different categories of agricultural products. To determine the area of cropland, measured in hectares, we multiply the amount of cropland by the corresponding cropland yields.

Forest products data is obtained from the UN's FAOSTAT ForeSTAT database, which includes two main categories of products: wood used for fuel, and timber/pulp used as raw materials for derived wood products. Information regarding global and country-specific forest yields, representing the net annual increments, is collected from various sources such as the FAO Temperate and Boreal Forest Resource Assessment (UNECE and FAO, 2000), Mancini et al. (2016), and Global Footprint Network's calculations based on the IPCC accounting methodology (IPCC 2006).

Step 2: Environmentally Extended Multi-Region Input-Output (EE-MRIO) Analysis

To calculate the Footprints of economic sectors based on final consumption activities, we employ an environmental extension within a multi-region input-output model, as per Leontief (1970). The Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP)⁷ database version 10 (Aguiar et al., 2019) forms the backbone of our Environmentally Extended Multi-Region Input-Output (EE-MRIO) model, utilizing data from 2014⁸. This EE-MRIO model aligns with established standards verified in previous studies, such as those by Weinzettel et al. (2014), Kitzes (2013), Munoz and Steininger (2010), Wiedmann et al. (2006), and Miller and Blair (2009). The goal of this step is to determine the Footprints linked to the final demand across 141 countries, further divided into 65 economic sectors. The Footprints' computation within the EE-MRIO model follows a standard formula, detailed as follows:

$$Footprint = F(I - A)^{-1}Y_N$$

⁵ More extensively, EQFs are productivity-based scaling factors that convert a specific land type (such as cropland or forest) into a universal unit of biologically productive area, a global hectare. See Glossary for more information or visit <https://www.footprintnetwork.org/> for more information.

⁶ See <https://cdiac.ess-dive.lbl.gov/>

⁷ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/default.asp>

⁸ Despite its 2014 timestamp, the GTAP 10 dataset remains reliable for sectoral prioritization. Gradual economic structural changes, combined with the dataset's comprehensive global supply chain overview and the slow mutation of production structures, lend it ongoing relevancy. This is further reinforced by the typically delayed updates of IO tables by national governments due to data intensity.

where

- F is the environmental extension matrix, or the direct footprint intensity. This intensity is measured in gha m $\$^{-1}$ for Ecological Footprint, tones CO $_2$ m $\$^{-1}$ for Carbon Footprint, hectare m $\$^{-1}$ for Cropland Footprint, and hectare m $\$^{-1}$ for Forest Footprint. This is derived from the ratio of Footprint (Ecological Footprint, Carbon emission, Cropland, and Forest land) data drawn in step 1 - all relative to the total output of each sector according to GTAP 10 (Galli et al., 2017).
- I denotes the identity matrix, which consists of zeros across 65 columns and rows except for a diagonal line of ones.
- A symbolizes the technical coefficients matrix, which captures the monetary exchange between each sector required to produce one currency unit's worth of output from a specific economic sector.
- Y_N represents the total country-wide final demand for goods and services, expressed in dollars \$.

The total Footprint intensity, defined as $F(I-A)^{-1}$, is key to the EE-MRIO model. It enables the investigation of interconnected effects and sectoral dependencies. $(I-A)^{-1}$, known as the Leontief inverse, captures the sum of direct and indirect demand triggered across all sectors by a unit increase in final demand within a specific sector. Obtaining the total Footprint intensity involves multiplying the environmental extension matrix with the Leontief inverse. The total Footprint intensity accounts for both direct and indirect environmental externalities throughout the entire global supply chain linked to final demand.

Finally, to estimate the Footprint based on the consumer principle, the total Footprint intensity is multiplied by domestic final demands⁹ across 65 economic sectors. This calculation provides a comprehensive understanding of the environmental externalities generated by consumer activities within each sector.

Step 3: Economic Sectors and related Dependency Analysis in the EEA-32 Region

The Sector and Dependency Analysis in the EEA-32 Region investigates the environmental impacts of various sectors and their interconnection along the supply chain. As a primary analysis, sectors with the largest externalities (i.e. the four Footprint: Ecological, carbon, cropland and forestland) as well as countries within the EEA region contributing to those sectors are identified. Subsequently, a dependency analysis is conducted to identify the subsidiary sectors and countries that have an impact on the footprints of the top sectors (i.e. target sectors) and countries within the EEA region throughout the entire supply chain. This analysis encompasses both the EEA region and non-EEA region influences. For detailed sector descriptions, please see Annex 1.

To perform sectoral analysis within the EEA-32 region, the results of the EE-MRIO model for 141 regions obtained in step 2 are reformatted by aggregating the data of the EEA 32 countries across 65 sectors. The primary objective of this analysis is to identify the top ten sectors that contribute the most to the Footprint externalities, along with the corresponding countries associated with these sectors. Further investigation can be conducted to understand the factors driving these results, such as examining the impact of final demand and/or total Footprint intensities (as described in Step 2).

⁹ Final demands encompass a variety of factors. These include household consumption, which consists of items like food, housing maintenance, and various commodities; government consumption, which involves public services, education, security, and defence; and gross fixed capital formation, contributed by households through residential properties and durable goods, by businesses through machinery, and by governments through elements like transportation infrastructure.

The rationale for conducting the dependency analysis lies in the understanding that addressing environmental externalities cannot be achieved solely by focusing on individual countries or sectors. Environmental impacts occur globally across the supply chain during the entire lifecycle of goods and services. Therefore, the dependency analysis considers the interconnected nature of sectors from production to consumption, providing a comprehensive assessment of the environmental implications.

To establish effective connections between the key economic sectors identified in this analysis and the most promising bio-based innovations highlighted in Section 2.2, a detailed concordance table is developed (see Annex 1). This table maps GTAP sectors to more commonly used sector classifications such as the Central Product Classification (CPC) and the International Standard Industry Classification (ISIC). The concordance table also allows to consolidate GTAP sectors into broader categories of the economy, which are identified by more general and colloquial names. Specifically, within this report, such broader categories are: *Agriculture* (primary raw products from agriculture and including fishing activities), *Food* (derived or processed products, animal- or vegetable- based), *Food** (related to tourism activities), *Construction*, *Energy/Electricity*, *Transportation*, *Textile*, *Others* (including all sectors pertaining to different sectors from those explicated). For further details, please refer to Annex 1.

2.1.1.2. Potential of economic sectors for innovation: supporting MRIO analysis

Based on the method in Section 2.1.1.1 that was used to identify the sectors that most need bio-based innovations because of largest Footprints, results from the MRIO analysis (Section 2.1.2.1) show that carbon is the main component under the Ecological Footprint “umbrella” (Table 1). In relation to the EU policy target of achieving climate neutrality and phasing down fossil fuels (EC, 2019; Council of the European Union, 2023), here we further identify the industrial sectors/processes in which bio-based innovations have the potential to complement/substitute traditional fossil-based processes based on the results of Carbon Footprints analysis. Section 2.1.2.1.2 identifies the economic sectors that have high total carbon footprints or carbon footprints intensities (i.e. per dollar of final demand). Ideally, for consistency, an MRIO model with economic components based on the same database could derive the output multiplier and employment multiplier to identify the bio-economic sectors that have the highest potential, such as the approach presented by Loizou et al. (2019) for Poland. However, developing such economic components in the MRIO model implemented in this report requires a separate project to collect the relevant economic and employment data for all 32 EEA countries. As such, here we only reviewed literature about the economic potential for the high carbon footprints sectors identified by EE-MRIO analysis, to support the EE-MRIO results and help to scope the review of existing bio-based innovation (section 2.2) and prioritize the innovations for upscaling (Part 2).

Two types of literature reviews are conducted to support the EE-MRIO results. In the first review, we focus on other MRIO and IO studies or sector analysis that have analysed the potential of bio-economy sectors or assessed economic impacts from the bio-economic transformation, i.e., some of the sectors replace their fossil-based material or processes with bio-based material or new biotechnology. These MRIO studies may only cover parts of the sectors, and usually only cover one country rather than the entire EU. Also, the analysis context and data used from those MRIO studies do not necessarily match the study purpose of this report. Thus, they are not directly usable to conclude which economic sector has the highest economic potential if the traditional fossil-based processes within the sector are replaced by bio-innovation. However, those (MR)IO studies can compare the economic potential or effects among different sectors within the same scenario, thus the review can provide a hint whether some of the sectors have higher economic potential than others under certain bio-economic transformation scenarios (e.g., replacing 10 billion USD of original

input material with bio-based material or residual material), and compare whether the high economic potential sectors match the sectors with the highest carbon footprints, as identified in section 2.1.2.1.

The second review follows the identified sectors from EE-MRIO analysis, focusing on Carbon Footprint due to the EU policy target mentioned above. Once the top 5 sectors that have either the highest total carbon footprints or carbon footprints intensity are identified (see section 2.1.2.1), we further analyse which production components or processes result in such high carbon emissions, based on both literature reviews and the sectoral dependency analysis from MRIO results. Further, we identify which innovations could replace such high carbon emission production components or processes, based on the literature review and the innovation review (section 2.2). Next, based on the literature review we identify the potential of the market, possible employment effects, and possible negative or side effects of such replacement to the bio-based innovations. We also mark the TRL of these innovations within the sectors based on the information collected in the innovation review (section 2.2). The collected information is summarised in Table 19 (section 2.1.2.2) and indicates whether the economic potential of the high carbon footprints sectors is high or low.

2.1.2. Key Output: primary sectors for implementing bio-based innovations

Within this section, we present the results of the EE-MRIO sector analysis. This analysis is intended to identify the economic sectors within the EEA-32 region in which bio-based innovations are both most needed and have the highest potential to complement/substitute traditional fossil-based processes, and/or improve the material efficiency of the bio-based sectors (e.g., via circularity, waste reduction). Such analysis is realized via distinct steps as explained in the methodology section: first, an environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) model is applied to identify the industrial sectors in which bio-based innovations are most needed given these sectors' key role as drivers of multiple human Footprints on the planet (section 2.1.2.1); then, the analysis of the innovation potential of economic sectors (section 2.1.2.2.) is used to confirm or integrate the results of the EE-MRIO analysis, thus leading to the identification of the key sectors in which bio-based innovations will stand the higher chance to bring about the necessary changes in the EEA-32 production and consumption activities so that carbon emissions and resource use can be reduced, thus supporting the transition called for by the EU Green Deal.

2.1.2.1. Economic sectors driving the Footprint Externalities: Ecological, Carbon, Cropland and Forest Footprints

In this section, we present the findings derived from the environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE-MRIO) model, aiming to identify the economic sectors that have the greatest impact on the EEA-32 region's various Footprints on a global scale, regardless of whether they occur within or beyond the region's geographical boundaries. Four distinct Footprints are examined, which encompass a range of externalities associated with economic activities:

- 1) The Ecological Footprint (measured in global hectares - gha) combines the carbon, cropland, and forest Footprints, along with the grazing land, built-up area, and fishing ground Footprints, to measure the collective demand for biological resources and ecosystem services by each economic sector. In other words, each sector's Ecological Footprint provides a measure of the "appropriated biocapacity", that is the biocapacity needed to produce the primary resources that the sector uses, and to sequester the CO₂ emissions that the sector releases in the environment.
- 2) The Carbon Footprint (measured in metric tons of CO₂) accounts for the amount of CO₂ emissions released into the environment by each economic sector.

- 3) The Cropland Footprint (measured in hectares) quantifies the amount of arable land and permanent crops required to produce crop products, including livestock feed, fishmeal, oil crops, and rubber, used by each economic sector.
- 4) The Forest Footprint (measured in hectares) tracks the area of forests needed by each sector to supply fuelwood and timber for forest products.

The Ecological Footprint serves as a representative measure of the overall environmental impact exerted by different economic sectors on the planet; it is therefore used in this report as an umbrella indicator bringing together the various externalities associated with such sectors. It recognizes that these sectors can have multiple and diverse Footprints, which are often evaluated independently. However, a systemic assessment can reveal synergies and trade-offs among them. This combined look at anthropogenic pressures is then complemented via a detailed analysis (see the following sections) of the individual Carbon, Cropland and Forest footprints.

For each Footprint, the analysis has been conducted using the following three steps:

1. A *sectoral analysis in the EEA-32 region* identifies the top 10 sectors that contribute the most to the overall footprint of the EEA-32 region. For the top 3 sectors, a brief description of their contribution to the overall regional footprint – analysing the role of the total footprint intensity vs. that of the final demand as determinants of the footprint – is also provided.
2. For the sole Ecological Footprint section, *an assessment of the contribution of the six land types to the Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region* by the top 10 economic sectors is also provided.
3. A *dependency analysis in the EEA-32 countries* then reveals the complex geographical dependencies within target sectors described in the *Sectoral analysis in the EEA-32 region*. It traces the flow of each footprint across sectors and nations, within and outside the EEA-32 region. More precisely, for each sector investigated, the dependency analysis looks at the sum of the total inputs needed for that sector in a given country to operate, grouped by source country and sector, and includes both direct and indirect inputs from the source sectors to the sector under analysis.

The identification of the top 3 sectors driving the EEA-32 region's footprints and the outcomes of the dependency analysis provide valuable insights to identify the specific sectors within which bio-based innovations would be most needed.

2.1.2.1.1 Ecological Footprint (gha)

Ecological balance in the EEA-32 region:

Figure 3 compares the total EEA-32 Ecological Footprint broken-down by the top 10 industries with the overall biocapacity of the region. The total Ecological Footprint in the EEA-32 region is 2,327 billion global hectares (gha), which is equal to 12% of the world's Ecological Footprint. On the other hand, the biocapacity of the EEA-32 region is approximately 1,192 billion gha, accounting for about 10% of the global biocapacity (11,897 billion gha). Forest land contributes to 41% of the region's biocapacity, while cropland makes up 37%. Interestingly, the Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region is twice the size of its inherent biocapacity. This means that the ecosystems of the EEA-32 region are potentially capable to supply only about half of the biocapacity needed to satisfy the final demand of the region's residents, thus indicating a potential imbalance between resource availability and human consumption. This highlights the potential challenges and pressures on the region's ecosystems to sustainably meet the needs of its population.

Figure 3. Comparison of Ecological Footprint and Biocapacity Among the Top 10 Sectors of the EEA-32 Region

Assessment of the six land components of Ecological Footprint in the EEA-32 region:

Ecological Footprint results of the EEA-32 region are provided in Table 1 as percentage contribution of the six land components (cropland, grazing land, forest land, fishing grounds, built-up land, and carbon footprint) in the top 10 economic sectors as well as total contribution. Of the total Ecological Footprint, the carbon footprint emerges as the primary contributor (accounting for 55% of the total), followed by cropland (22%) and forest land (13%).

Among the top 10 sectors, the Ecological Footprint of the Construction sector (GTAP 49) is primarily driven by the carbon (63%) and the forest (29%) components. These two components together make up 92% of the sector's total Ecological Footprint. In contrast, Accommodation, Food and service activities (GTAP 51) and Food products nec (GTAP 25) show relatively high contributions from cropland, accounting for 37% and 60% of their total Ecological Footprint, respectively. The Forestry sector (GTAP 13) is predominantly influenced by the forest land component, which constitutes 98% of its Ecological Footprint. The Transport nec sector (GTAP 52), Electricity sector (GTAP 46), and Computer, electronic and optical products sector (GTAP 40) are mainly dominated by carbon footprint, representing 94%, 94%, and 83% of their respective Ecological Footprints.

EEA 32 Ecological Footprint by 6 land types

GTAP Economic Sector		Cropland	Grazing Land	Forest Land	Fishing Grounds	Built-up Land	Carbon
Number	Description	%	%	%	%	%	%
49	Construction	3%	1%	29%	1%	4%	63%
51	Accommodation, Food and service activities	37%	4%	9%	9%	3%	39%
25	Food products nec	60%	3%	4%	9%	1%	22%
52	Transport nec	1%	0%	2%	0%	2%	94%
50	Trade	6%	1%	11%	1%	5%	77%
64	Human health and social work activities	17%	3%	13%	4%	5%	59%
46	Electricity	1%	0%	4%	0%	1%	94%
13	Forestry	0%	0%	98%	0%	0%	1%
62	Public Administration and defense	12%	2%	13%	1%	5%	67%
40	Computer, electronic and optical products	4%	1%	6%	0%	5%	83%
Total		22%	3%	13%	4%	3%	55%

Table 1. Contribution of 6 Land Types to the Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 Region for the Top 10 Economic Sectors. When observing the table horizontally, the percentages provided represent the contribution of each land type to the corresponding sector.

Sectoral analysis for Ecological Footprint in the EEA 32 region:

Of the 65 economic sectors analysed, ten sectors alone make up approximately half (47.9%) of the region's total Ecological Footprint (see Table 2). Such pressure on ecosystems is driven by the final purchases of EEA-32 consumers from these 10 sectors, which also represents about half (50.8%) of the demand from all sectors.

The *Construction* sector (GTAP 49) holds the top position for its contribution to the total Ecological Footprint results in the EEA-32 region, making up approximately 9% of the region's total Ecological Footprint. In other words, about 9% of the Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region is due to the purchases (by households, governments and businesses) from the construction sector. The total Footprint intensity of the construction sector (132 gha m\$⁻¹) is 10% lower than the average of all sectors (147 gha m\$⁻¹); this implies that this sector requires a relatively small amount of direct and indirect Ecological Footprint per unit of economic value compared to the average of all sectors in the region. The top contribution of this sector to the region's Footprint is thus primarily influenced by the final demand of EEA-32 residents from this sector, which accounts for roughly 10% of the total final demand in the EEA 32 region.

Table 2. Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region by top 10 economic sectors. GTAP 10 sectors' list is used, which is defined by reference to the Central Product Classification (CPC) – for agricultural and food processing sectors – and the International Standard Industry Classification, Rev. 4 (ISIC4) – for all other sectors. Annex 2 provides tables of the top 10 countries and their Ecological Footprint contribution to the top three sectors (i.e. sectors 49, 51 and 25).

EEA32 Ecological Footprint (gha)

GTAP Economic Sector		Total Ecological Footprint		Total EF Intensity	Final Demand	
Number	Description	[gha]	[%]	[gha/m\$]	[m\$]	[%]
49	Construction	204,158,018	8.8%	132	1,548,128	9.8%
51	Accommodation, Food and service activities	152,460,086	6.6%	168	908,493	5.7%
25	Food products nec	149,732,729	6.4%	491	305,054	1.9%
52	Transport nec	110,063,490	4.7%	299	367,633	2.3%
50	Trade	100,755,118	4.3%	67	1,498,034	9.4%
64	Human health and social work activities	95,687,169	4.1%	59	1,634,373	10.3%
46	Electricity	92,374,179	4.0%	650	142,034	0.9%
13	Forestry	70,901,202	3.0%	6,487	10,929	0.1%
62	Public Administration and defense	69,519,578	3.0%	50	1,377,434	8.7%
40	Computer, electronic and optical products	69,404,878	3.0%	253	273,825	1.7%
Total		2,327,015,933	47.9%	146.6	15,875,590	50.8%

The *Accommodation, Food and Service Activities*, sector (GTAP 51) ranks second, contributing to approximately 7% of the total Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region. This is due to a considerably high final demand (accounting for 5.7% of the overall final demand) and a total EF intensity (168 gha m\$⁻¹) higher than the average of all sectors (147 gha m\$⁻¹).

The *Food Products nec* sector (GTAP 25) occupies the third position in the ranking and contributes to approximately 6% of the overall Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region. The observed footprint results stem from a significantly high total Footprint intensity (491 gha m\$⁻¹), which is about 2.4 times higher than the weighted average intensity of all sectors (147 gha m\$⁻¹). Remarkably, this is the case despite the sector's share of the overall final demand being a mere 1.9%.

Dependency analysis for Ecological Footprint in the EEA-32 countries:

We focused our analysis on (a) Construction (GTAP 49), (b) Accommodation, food, service activities (GTAP 51), and (c) Food product nec (GTAP 25) as these three sectors have a notable influence on the overall Ecological Footprint of the EEA-32 region.

- a. Construction (GTAP 49)** (see Table 3): Among the EEA countries, France emerges as the primary contributor (14.8%) to the EEA Construction sector's Ecological Footprint. Germany follows closely behind with a contribution of 14.4%, while Turkey contributes to 9.2%. Together, final demand in these countries accounts for 38.4% of the Ecological Footprint of the Construction sector in the EEA-32.

Table 3. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to Ecological Footprint in the construction sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Ecological Footprint in the Construction sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors		Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors							
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
France	14.8%	Forestry	32.3%	81.0%	19.0%	France	62.1%	China	3.1%	Germany	3.0%
		Electricity	20.1%	28.0%	72.0%	China	44.6%	France	14.7%	Russian Federation	4.5%
		Transport nec	9.9%	63.7%	36.3%	France	43.8%	China	8.7%	United States of America	7.0%
Germany	14.4%	Forestry	23.1%	77.6%	22.4%	Germany	42.1%	Poland	7.4%	Czech Republic	5.9%
		Electricity	21.7%	35.9%	64.1%	China	40.0%	Germany	24.5%	Russian Federation	4.9%
		Construction	9.8%	99.8%	0.2%	Germany	99.6%	China	0.1%	United Kingdom	0.0%
Turkey	9.2%	Electricity	35.9%	57.5%	42.5%	Turkey	54.4%	China	15.6%	Russian Federation	7.4%
		Mineral products nec	17.4%	88.9%	11.1%	Turkey	87.6%	China	7.6%	India	1.2%
		Forestry	11.5%	68.8%	31.2%	Turkey	56.1%	Ukraine	7.9%	Russian Federation	6.3%

In France, the construction sector depends on its relationships (i.e., dependencies) with various sectors, the most important ones being Forestry (32.3%), Electricity (20.1%), and Transport nec (9.9%), whose outputs are fundamental to the functioning of the Construction sector. These percentages represent the respective contributions of each sector to the total Ecological Footprint of the Construction sector. Regarding Forestry, for instance, 62.1% of its Ecological Footprint originates from France itself, while 18.9% comes from other EEA 32 countries. Additionally, 19% of the biocapacity relied upon by the Forestry sector comes from outside the EEA 32 region, with significant contributions from countries like China and Germany (about 3%). Similarly, the second largest dependency sector in France is Electricity, of which 14.7% of the Ecological Footprint comes from the country itself, while 13.3% originates from other EEA 32 countries. Remarkably, 72% of the biocapacity used by the Electricity sector in supporting the construction sector in France is sourced from outside the EEA 32 region, primarily from China (44.6%) and the Russian Federation (4.5%). This could mean that the production (of CO₂) or harvest (of biomass) that is input to the construction sector was emitted by the electricity sector in China or the Russian Federation.

Germany also showcases distinct characteristics in its dependency relationships for the Construction sector: the Forestry sector accounts for 23.1% of the Ecological Footprint of the German's Construction sector, followed by the Electricity sector (21.7%), and the Construction sector itself (9.8%). As for Forestry, Germany contributes 42.1% of the Ecological Footprint, while 35.5% originates from other EEA 32 countries such as Poland (7.4%) and the Czech Republic (5.9%). Nonetheless, 22.4% of the forest biocapacity comes from outside the EEA 32 region, including contributions from China (4.5%). Similarly, in the Electricity sector contributing to construction, 24.5% of the biocapacity comes from within Germany, while 11.3% originates from other EEA 32 countries. Notably, 64.1% of the biocapacity used by the Electricity sector for the construction sector is sourced from outside the EEA 32 region, with significant contributions from China (40%) and the Russian Federation (4.9%).

In Turkey, the top three sectors contributing to the construction sector are Electricity (35.9%), Mineral products nec (17.4%), and Forestry (11.5%). The Electricity sector relies on the biocapacity originating from within the country itself for 54.4% of its Ecological Footprint, with an additional 3.1% originating from other EEA 32 countries. The rest (42.5%) of the biocapacity for the Electricity sector comes from outside the EEA 32 region, with notable contributions from China (15.6%) and the Russian Federation (7.4%). For the Mineral products nec sector contributing to the Construction sector, Turkey relies on its own biocapacity for 87.6% of the Ecological Footprint, with an additional 1.3% originating from other EEA 32 countries. Meanwhile, 11.1% of the biocapacity used by the Mineral products nec sector in supporting the construction sector in Turkey is sourced from outside the EEA 32 region.

In summary, the results of the sectoral dependencies analysis conducted in the top three EEA-32 countries (France, Germany, and Turkey) suggest that reducing the Ecological Footprint linked to the Construction sector in the EEA-32 region may necessitate prioritizing investments in bio-based innovations across key interconnected sectors like Forestry, Transport, Electricity, and Mineral sectors. These results also show that reducing the Ecological Footprint associated with the Construction sector in the EEA-32 region might also require changes in the production practices outside of the region, or in alternative changes in trade relationships.

Specifically, for each country:

- In France, it is important to focus on the Forestry sector within the country and the Electricity sector in China.
- In Germany, attention should be given to the Forestry sector within Germany and other EEA countries. Additionally, emphasis should be placed on the Electric sector outside of the EEA region, particularly in China.
- In Turkey, priority should be given to the Electricity sector within Turkey and China, as well as the Mineral products nec sector within Turkey.

b. Accommodation, food, service activities (GTAP sector 51) (see Table 4): Italy, Germany, and France are the top three countries contributing the most to this sector’s Ecological Footprint in the EEA-32 region. Italy accounts for 13.4% of the sector’s overall Ecological Footprint, followed closely by Germany (13.2%), and France (12.5%). Collectively, these three countries contribute 39.1% of the total Ecological Footprint of the sector.

Table 4. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to Ecological Footprint in the Accommodation, Food and service activities sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Ecological Footprint in the Accommodation, Food and service activities sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors			Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors						
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Italy	13.4%	Electricity	14.3%	50%	50%	Italy	35.3%	China	23.4%	Russian Federation	4.8%
		Cereal grains nec	12.6%	79%	21%	Italy	41.4%	Ukraine	10.6%	France	9.2%
		Wheat	11.0%	69%	31%	Italy	21.6%	France	13.5%	Canada	11.9%
Germany	13.2%	Electricity	18.0%	63%	37%	Germany	54.7%	China	18.5%	Russian Federation	4.0%
		Transport nec	15.0%	85%	15%	Germany	76.9%	United States of America	3.4%	China	3.0%
		Cereal grains nec	11.5%	88%	12%	Germany	54.5%	Poland	10.5%	France	8.3%
France	12.5%	Fishing	16.8%	69%	31%	France	45.5%	Norway	10.4%	United Kingdom	9.8%
		Electricity	11.8%	42%	58%	France	31.8%	China	30.4%	United States of America	3.9%
		Oil seeds	9.9%	48%	52%	France	33.1%	Brazil	11.7%	Ukraine	10.5%

In Italy, sectoral dependencies analysis found the main sectors supporting the Accommodation, Food, and Service Activities (hereafter AFS) sector to be Electricity (14.3%), Cereal grains nec (12.6%), and Wheat (11.0%). The Electricity sector contributing to the AFS sector sources 35.3% of its biocapacity needs from Italy itself. Meanwhile, an additional 14.5% is supplied by the other EEA-32 countries. Half of this sector’s biocapacity needs is dependent on non-EEA 32 countries, with China contributing a substantial 23.4% and Russia at 4.8%. In the Cereal grains nec sector supporting the AFS sector, 41.4% of its biocapacity needs is domestically sourced, while 37.7% is derived from other EEA-32 countries, including contributions from France (9.2%) and Hungary (7.5%). Furthermore, 21% of the biocapacity used by this sector comes from countries outside of the EEA-32 region, such as Ukraine, which contributes 10.6%.

For Germany, results of the dependency analysis indicate that the sectors upon which the AFS sector depends the most are Electricity (18.0%), Transport nec (15.0%), and Cereal grains nec (11.5%). 54.7% of the biocapacity needed by the Electricity sector contributing to the AFS sector in Germany comes from within Germany, 8.6% from the rest of the EEA-32, while the remaining 37% is sourced outside of the EEA-32 region, primarily from China (18.5%). The Transport nec sector shows a higher domestic reliance, with 76.9% of its biocapacity being sourced from Germany, and only 15% being dependent on non-EEA 32 countries (primarily from USA and China).

In France, the top three sectors contributing to the AFS sector are Fishing (16.8%), Electricity (11.8%), and Oil seeds (9.9%). 45.5% of the biocapacity needed by the Fishing sector in support of the AFS sector in France is sourced from within France, while 23.7% comes from other EEA-32 countries, including Norway at 10.4%. Additionally, 31% of its biocapacity is dependent on non-EEA 32 countries, with the United Kingdom being a top contributor at 9.8%. The Electricity sector contributing to the AFS sector, as the second largest in France, relies on 31.8% domestic sourcing, 10.6% from the EEA-32, and a considerable 58% from outside of the EEA-32, with China alone accounting for 30.4%.

To summarize, the sectoral dependencies analysis conducted in the top three EEA-32 countries (Italy, Germany, and France) suggests that addressing the Ecological Footprint associated with the AFS sector in the EEA-32 region may require focusing on bio-based innovations across key interconnected

sectors – such as Electricity, Cereal grains nec, Wheat, Transport nec, Fishing, and Oil seeds sectors – and countries.

Specifically, for each country:

- In Italy, it is important to focus on the Electric sector within Italy and China, as well as the Cereal grains nec sector in Italy within the EEA-32 region and Ukraine.
- In Germany, priority should be given to the Electricity sector in Germany and China, as well as the Transport sector in Germany.
- In France, emphasis should be placed on the fishing sector in France and other EEA countries such as Norway. Additionally, attention should be given to the Electric sector in France and China.

c. Food product nec (GTAP sector 25) (see Table 5): At the country level, Germany stands out as the top contributor with 24.7%, followed by France with 12.4%, and Spain with 11.0%. Together, final demand in these three countries drives nearly 48% of the EEA-32's total Ecological Footprint of the Food product nec sector.

Table 5. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to Ecological Footprint in the Food product nec sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Ecological Footprint in the Food products nec sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors			Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors						
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Germany	24.7%	Oil seeds	24.3%	59%	41%	Germany	24.5%	Brazil	11.4%	United States of America	10.6%
		Cereal grains nec	22.3%	93%	7%	Germany	57.8%	Poland	11.8%	France	9.3%
		Wheat	9.6%	94%	6%	Germany	40.3%	Czech Republic	22.5%	Poland	10.4%
France	12.4%	Cereal grains nec	19.7%	92%	8%	France	79.0%	Germany	4.9%	Chile	1.6%
		Oil seeds	19.4%	56%	44%	France	42.5%	Ukraine	10.7%	Brazil	10.1%
		Wheat	15.8%	96%	4%	France	83.9%	Germany	4.9%	Belgium	1.7%
Spain	11.0%	Cereal grains nec	25.2%	69%	31%	Spain	47.9%	Ukraine	17.3%	France	12.5%
		Oil seeds	18.7%	24%	76%	Brazil	26.6%	United States of America	16.8%	Spain	12.1%
		Wheat	17.5%	85%	15%	Spain	57.4%	France	11.9%	Ukraine	6.4%

In Germany, the top three sectors contributing to the Food products nec sector as identified by the dependency analysis are Oil seeds (24.3%), Cereal grains nec (22.3%), and Wheat (9.6%). The biocapacity needs of the Oil seeds sector contributing to the Food products nec sector are sourced as follows: 24.5% is domestically sourced from within Germany; 34.2% is garnered from other EEA-32 countries, including noteworthy contributions from France (10.5%) and Poland (7.4%); and a significant 41% hinges upon non-EEA 32 regions, with Brazil at 11.4% and USA at 10.6%. The secondary dependency sector for the Food products sector, Cereal grains nec, presents a different composition, with 57.8% of the biocapacity needs sourced domestically, 35% from other EEA-32 countries (including Poland at 11.8% and France at 9.3%), and a mere 7% from external sources.

In France, the top three sectors contributing to the Food products nec sector are Cereal grains nec (19.7%), Oil seeds (19.4%), and Wheat (15.8%). The Cereal grains sector is particularly noteworthy as it relies heavily (79%) on domestically sourced biocapacity. Additionally, 13.5% is sourced from other EEA-32 nations (including Germany at 4.9%). In the Oil seeds sector contributing to the Food products sector in France, 42.5% of its biocapacity comes from domestic sources, 13.2% from the EEA-32, and a significant 44% is dependent on regions beyond the EEA-32, including contributions from Ukraine (10.7%) and Brazil (10.1%).

Similarly, in Spain, the top three sectors contributing to the Food products nec sector are Cereal grains nec (25.2%), Oil seeds (18.7%), and Wheat (17.5%). The Cereal grains nec sector stands as the principal dependency sector, with 47.9% of its biocapacity needs sourced domestically, 20.8% from the EEA-32 (including France at 12.5%), and 31% dependent on external sources, with Ukraine and Brazil each contributing over 10%. The Oil seeds sector supporting the Food products sector is heavily reliant on biocapacity sources outside of the EEA-32, accounting for 76% of its biocapacity. Notably, Brazil alone contributes 26.6%, while USA provides 16.8%. Only 12.1% is procured domestically.

In summary, the results of the sectoral dependencies analysis conducted in the top three EEA-32 countries (Italy, Germany, and France) suggest that reducing the Ecological Footprint associated with the Food products sector in the EEA-32 region may require prioritizing innovation in key interconnected sectors, such as Oil seeds, Cereal grains nec, and the Wheat sector, as well as in foreign countries such as Brazil, USA and Ukraine.

Specifically, for each country:

- In Germany, emphasis should be placed on the Oil seeds sector within Germany and other EEA-32 countries, as well as Brazil. Additionally, attention should be given to the Cereal grains nec sector and Wheat sector within Germany.
- In France, priority should be given to the Cereal grains nec sector within France. Additionally, innovation should be focused on the Oil seeds sector in France and other EEA countries, including Ukraine. Furthermore, the Wheat sector in France should be taken into consideration.
- In Spain, the focus should be on the Cereal grains nec sector within Spain and other EEA countries, as well as Ukraine. Innovation in the Oil seeds sector in Brazil and the USA are also important. Finally, the Wheat sector in Spain and other EEA countries should be considered.

2.1.2.1.2 Carbon Footprint (t CO₂)

Sectoral analysis for Carbon Footprint in the EEA 32 region:

An evaluation of the carbon footprint in the EEA-32 region highlights a significant finding: out of the 65 economic sectors, just 10 sectors contribute to more than 56% of the region's carbon footprint (see Table 6). Moreover, the final demand for these 10 sectors constitutes slightly over 45% of the region's total final demand.

Table 6. Carbon Footprint of the EEA-32 region by top 10 economic sectors (see Annex 3 for the full sectors' list). GTAP 10 sectors' list is used, which is defined by reference to the Central Product Classification (CPC) – for agricultural and food processing sectors – and the International Standard Industry Classification, Rev. 4 (ISIC4) – for all other sectors. Also, Annex 4 provides tables of the top 10 countries and their carbon Footprint contribution to the top three sectors (i.e. sectors 49, 52 and 46).

EEA32_Carbon Footprint (tCO₂)

GTAP Economic Sector		Total Carbon Footprint		Total Carbon Intensity	Final Demand	
Number	Description	[tCO ₂]	[%]	[tCO ₂ /m\$]	[m\$]	[%]
49	Construction	378,332,454	10.0%	244	1,548,128	9.8%
52	Transport nec	306,156,548	8.1%	833	367,633	2.3%
46	Electricity	256,939,091	6.8%	1,809	142,034	0.9%
50	Trade	227,008,208	6.0%	152	1,498,034	9.4%
51	Accommodation, Food and service activities	174,995,594	4.6%	193	908,493	5.7%
40	Computer, electronic and optical products	169,178,353	4.5%	618	273,825	1.7%
64	Human health and social work activities	167,235,708	4.4%	102	1,634,373	10.3%
54	Air transport	157,994,277	4.2%	1,459	108,298	0.7%
42	Machinery and equipment nec	148,411,928	3.9%	398	372,543	2.3%
43	Motor vehicles and parts	145,788,330	3.9%	387	376,951	2.4%
Total		3,770,404,136	56.5%	237.5	15,875,590	45.5%

The *construction* sector (GTAP 49) is at the top of the ranking, accounting for 10% of the carbon footprint in the EEA-32 region. This indicates its significant role in shaping the region's carbon footprint, mainly due to its high final demand, which makes up nearly 10% of the overall final demand in the EEA-32 region.

The *transport nec* sector (GTAP 52) follows in the ranking, contributing approximately 8% to the EEA-32 region's carbon footprint. This sector's notable impact can be mainly attributed to its higher total footprint intensities, which are about 2.5 times higher than the weighted average intensity across all sectors.

The *electricity* sector (GTAP 46) ranks third with a contribution to the EEA-32 region's overall carbon footprint of approximately 7%. Despite representing only 0.9% of the total final demand in the EEA region, this sector demonstrates a remarkable outcome driven by significantly higher total footprint intensities, which are approximately 6.6 times higher than the weighted average intensity of all sectors.

Dependency analysis for Carbon Footprint in the EEA-32 countries:

- a. **Construction (GTAP 49)** (see Table 7): An examination of the Construction sector within the EEA 32 region is provided, focusing on the contribution of the top 3 countries. In the country level, Germany, France, and Turkey emerge as the leading contributors to the carbon Footprint of the Construction sector in the EEA-32 region. Germany takes the lead with a contribution of 16.0%, followed by France with 13.5%, and Turkey with 12.2%. The findings demonstrate that these countries collectively drive more than 41.7% of the sector's carbon Footprint.

Table 7. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to Carbon Footprint in the Construction sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Carbon Footprint in the Construction sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors		Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors							
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Germany	16.0%	Electricity	31.2%	35.8%	64.2%	China	40.1%	Germany	24.5%	Russian Federation	4.9%
		Transport nec	13.7%	68.2%	31.8%	Germany	51.7%	China	8.4%	United States of America	6.9%
		Mineral products nec	13.1%	71.7%	28.3%	Germany	57.8%	China	20.3%	Poland	2.5%
France	13.5%	Electricity	35.1%	28.0%	72.0%	China	44.7%	France	14.6%	Russian Federation	4.5%
		Transport nec	17.1%	63.7%	36.3%	France	43.8%	China	8.7%	United States of America	7.1%
		Mineral products nec	11.8%	69.2%	30.8%	France	47.1%	China	22.2%	Italy	5.6%
Turkey	12.2%	Electricity	42.9%	57.5%	42.5%	Turkey	54.4%	China	15.6%	Russian Federation	7.4%
		Mineral products nec	20.8%	89.0%	11.0%	Turkey	87.7%	China	7.6%	India	1.2%
		Ferrous metals	12.2%	32.9%	67.1%	Turkey	26.4%	Ukraine	20.1%	China	15.2%

In Germany, the dependency sectors contributing to the construction sector are Electricity (31.2%), Transport nec (13.7%), and Mineral products nec (13.1%). In the electricity sector, 24.5% of the Carbon Footprint is attributed to domestic sources, and an additional 11.3% is contributed by other countries within the EEA-32. However, a substantial 64.2% of the Carbon Footprint is derived from regions outside the EEA-32, with China alone contributing to 40.1%, followed by the Russian Federation at 4.9%. Transport nec emerges as the second-most significant dependency sector for the construction sector in Germany, with 51.7% sourced domestically, 16.5% from the EEA-32, and 31.8% from regions beyond, including China at 8.4%.

In the context of France, the dependency sectors for the construction sector of focus are Electricity (35.1%), Transport nec (17.1%), and Mineral products nec (11.8%). The Carbon Footprint within the electricity sector is dispersed as follows: 14.6% is domestically generated, 13.3% is attributed to other EEA-32 nations, and a staggering 72% originates from outside the EEA-32, with China contributing 44.7% and the Russian Federation adding 4.5%. The transport nec sector contributing to the construction sector in France, exhibits a different pattern with 43.8% sourced domestically, 19.9%

from within the EEA-32, and 36.3% from external regions, including China at 8.7% and the United States at 7.1%.

Turkey's top three contributing sectors for the construction sector are Electricity (42.9%), Mineral products nec (20.8%), and Ferrous metals (12.2%). As for the electricity sector, a significant 54.4% of the Carbon Footprint in supporting Turkey's construction sector originates domestically. Notably, 42.5% of the Carbon Footprint arises from outside the EEA-32, with contributions from China (15.6%) and the Russian Federation (7.4%). The mineral products nec, is predominantly influenced by domestic sources, contributing 87.7% to the Carbon Footprint, while only 1.3% is sourced from the EEA-32, and 11% comes from external regions.

The dependency analysis looks at the total requirements from specific sectors, both directly and indirectly, to produce the outputs of the construction sectors in Germany, France, and Turkey. In the case of dependency on China's electricity sector, this refers to CO2 emissions generated by the electricity sector in China that are embedded in the inputs to the construction sector. For example, electricity produced in China can be sold to a factory in China, which produced construction tools or construction materials that are then purchased by the construction sector of Germany, France or Turkey. While it is possible that the results include direct purchases of electricity by these construction sectors from China, it is unlikely in Germany, France, or Turkey because electricity trade is limited by geographical distance and China does not report electricity exports to these countries.

In summary, the results of the dependency analysis conducted in the top three countries of the EEA-32 region, namely Germany, France, and Turkey, indicate that reducing the Carbon Footprint associated with the Construction sector may require prioritizing innovations in the key interconnected sectors such as Electricity, Transport nec, Mineral products nec, and Ferrous metals sector.

Specifically, for each country:

- In Germany, the Electricity sector in Germany and China, as well as the Transport and Mineral products nec sector in Germany, should be prioritized.
- In France, the Electricity sector in China, along with the Transport and Mineral products nec sector in France, should be given priority.
- In Turkey, the Electricity sector in Turkey and China, the Mineral products nec sector in Turkey, and Ferrous metals in Turkey, Ukraine, and China should be the primary areas of focus.

b. **Transport nec (GTAP 52)** (see Table 8): in this sector, Italy, Germany, and Turkey are the three leading contributors to the Carbon Footprint within the EEA-32 region. Italy stands out as the largest contributor with a significant share of 17.7%, followed by Germany with 13.4%, and Turkey with 10.6%. Combined, these three countries account for over 41.7% of the sector's total carbon footprint.

Table 8. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to Carbon Footprint in the Transport nec sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Carbon Footprint in the Transport nec sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors				Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors					
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Italy	17.7%	Transport nec	78.1%	99%	1%	Italy	98.7%	Russian Federation	0.3%	China	0.1%
		Petroleum, coal products	8.8%	89%	11%	Italy	86.3%	Rest of North Africa	3.0%	Russian Federation	2.2%
		Electricity	6.3%	48%	52%	Italy	39.7%	China	15.8%	Russian Federation	14.0%
Germany	13.4%	Transport nec	85.2%	99%	1%	Germany	98.5%	Russian Federation	0.3%	United States of America	0.2%
		Electricity	7.6%	66%	34%	Germany	60.2%	China	12.3%	Russian Federation	10.7%
		Petroleum, coal products	3.0%	87%	13%	Germany	73.4%	Russian Federation	4.9%	Netherlands	4.7%
Turkey	10.6%	Transport nec	74.6%	99%	1%	Turkey	98.7%	Russian Federation	0.4%	United States of America	0.1%
		Electricity	10.0%	59%	41%	Turkey	56.1%	Russian Federation	13.1%	China	9.9%
		Petroleum, coal products	5.8%	72%	28%	Turkey	63.0%	Russian Federation	6.5%	India	5.7%

For Italy, the dependency sectors for the transport nec sector are Transport nec (78.1%), Petroleum, coal products (8.8%), and Electricity (6.3%). The Carbon Footprint in the transport sector heavily relies on domestic sources, which account for 98.7% of the Carbon Footprint. A negligible 0.2% is attributed to other EEA-32 countries, while a minuscule 1.1% is derived from outside the EEA-32. Of the total Carbon Footprint in the petroleum and coal products sector to support the transport sector, a significant 86.3% is sourced domestically, while 2.7% originates from within the EEA-32, and 11% comes from regions outside the EEA-32.

Moving to Germany, the dependency sectors are Transport nec (85.2%), Electricity (7.6%), and Petroleum, coal products (3.0%). In the transport nec sector, the pattern closely resembles Italy's, with 98.5% of the Carbon Footprint being domestically sourced, 0.4% contributed by other EEA-32 countries, and 1.1% from beyond the EEA-32. The electricity contributing to the transport sector exhibits a different footprint profile with 60.2% sourced domestically, 6.3% from within the EEA-32, and 33.5% from regions beyond, including China at 12.3% and Russia Federation at 10.7%.

Similarly, Turkey's top three contributing sectors are Transport nec (74.6%), Electricity (10.0%), Petroleum, coal products (5.8%). 98.7% of the Carbon Footprint in the transport sector is sourced domestically, 0.2% from the EEA-32, and 1.2% from external regions. The electricity sector in supporting Turkey's transport sector displays a different dispersion of sources; 56.1% is domestically generated, 2.5% emanates from other EEA-32 nations, and 41.4% originates from outside the EEA-32, including Russian Federation at 13.1% and China at 9.9%.

In summary, the results of the dependency analysis conducted in Italy, Germany, and Turkey suggest that reducing the Carbon Footprint in the Transport nec sector may require prioritizing investments in key interconnected sectors, including the Transport nec sector itself, the Petroleum, coal products sector, and the Electricity sector.

For each country specifically:

- In Italy, priority should be given to reducing the Carbon Footprint in the Transport sector within Italy itself, as well as in the Petroleum and coal products sector within Italy. Additionally, investments in bio-based innovations in the Electricity sector in both Italy and China should be considered.
- In Germany, efforts should be directed towards reducing the Carbon Footprint in the Transport sector within Germany, as well as investments in bio-based innovations in the Electricity sector in both Germany and China. Furthermore, the Petroleum and coal products sector in Germany and China should be targeted.

- In Turkey, it is important to focus on reducing the Carbon Footprint in the Transport sector within Turkey. Additionally, investments in bio-based innovations in the Electricity sector in both Turkey and the Russian Federation should be prioritized. Lastly, attention should be given to the Petroleum and coal products sector in Turkey.

c. **Electricity (GTAP 46)** (see Table 9): The footprint of the Electricity sector in the EEA-32 region is most strongly driven by Germany, comprising 20.3% of the region’s footprint, followed by Poland at 11.9%, and Turkey at 11.5%. These 3 countries together account for 43.7% of the sector's carbon footprint.

Table 9. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to Carbon Footprint in the Electricity sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Carbon Footprint in the Electricity sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors		Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors							
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Germany	20.3%	Electricity	95.1%	98%	2%	Germany	97.8%	China	0.8%	Russian Federation	0.4%
		Transport nec	1.8%	69%	31%	Germany	59.0%	United States of America	7.4%	Russian Federation	6.1%
		Petroleum, coal products	0.6%	76%	24%	Germany	64.4%	China	7.6%	Russian Federation	4.9%
Poland	11.9%	Electricity	92.4%	98%	2%	Poland	96.7%	Germany	0.9%	China	0.6%
		Gas	1.7%	0%	100%	Kazakhstan	94.8%	Egypt	1.8%	Canada	1.1%
		Transport nec	1.6%	74%	26%	Poland	64.5%	Russian Federation	8.9%	United States of America	3.8%
Turkey	11.5%	Electricity	97.3%	99%	1%	Turkey	98.6%	Iran, Islamic Republic of	0.3%	China	0.3%
		Transport nec	0.6%	22%	78%	Rest of North Africa	36.4%	Turkey	18.2%	United States of America	18.1%
		Petroleum, coal products	0.6%	68%	32%	Turkey	61.3%	Rest of North Africa	8.0%	Russian Federation	4.6%

In Germany, most of the carbon emissions directly originate from the interactions among the various subcomponents (e.g., the extraction of natural gas for the production and distribution of electricity – see Annex 1 for further details on each sectors and its subcomponents) of the Electricity sector, which thus accounts for the largest share (95.1%) of the overall Carbon Footprint, followed by Transport nec at 1.8%, and Petroleum, coal products at 0.6%. Remarkably, a large majority, 98.8% of the Carbon Footprint in Germany's Electricity sector originates from domestic sources.

Similarly, in Poland, the dependency sectors for the Electricity sector are Electricity (92.4%), Gas (1.7%), and Transport nec (1.6%). Within the Electricity sector, 96.7% of the Carbon Footprint is domestically generated.

Moving on to Turkey, the dependency sectors include Electricity (97.3%), Transport nec (0.6%), and Petroleum, coal products (0.6%). The Electricity sector in Turkey closely resembles that of Germany and Poland, with 98.6% of its Carbon Footprint sourced domestically.

In summary, the dependency analysis conducted in the top three EEA-32 countries, namely Germany, Poland, and Turkey, highlights the importance of prioritizing innovation in key interconnected sectors to reduce the Carbon Footprint associated with the Electricity sector. These sectors include Electricity, Transport nec, Petroleum and coal products, and the Gas sector.

Interestingly, the analysis reveals that the Electricity sector itself has a significantly higher Carbon Footprint ratio compared to other sectors in these three countries. Therefore, it becomes crucial to prioritize efforts and investments specifically in the Electricity sector to effectively reduce the overall Carbon Footprint in these countries.

2.1.2.1.3 Cropland Footprint (ha)

Sectoral analysis for Cropland Footprint in the EEA 32 region:

The cropland footprint is distributed among various sectors related to food within the 65 economic sectors. The top 10 sectors make a substantial contribution, accounting for over 75.2% of the total cropland footprint in the EEA-32 region. Interestingly, despite their significant impact, the final demand for these top 10 sectors represents only approximately 21.2% of the overall final demand in the EEA-32 regions. On the other hand, these sectors exhibit higher total cropland intensity compared to the weighted average of all 65 sectors.

Table 10. Cropland Footprint of the EEA-32 region by top 10 economic sectors. The GTAP 10 sectors' list is utilized, which is based on the Central Product Classification (CPC) for agricultural and food processing sectors, and the International Standard Industry Classification, Rev. 4 (ISIC4) for all other sectors. Also Annex 5 provides tables of the top 10 countries and their cropland Footprint contribution to the top three sectors (i.e. sectors 25, 51 and 2).

EEA32_Cropland Footprint (hectare)

GTAP Economic Sector		Total Cropland Footprint		Total Cropland Intensity	Final Demand	
Number	Description	[hectare]	[%]	[hectare/m\$]	[m\$]	[%]
25	Food products nec	35,855,132	17.9%	118	305,054	1.9%
51	Accommodation, Food and service activities	22,448,757	11.2%	25	908,493	5.7%
2	Wheat	21,226,316	10.6%	1,755	12,095	0.1%
4	Vegetables, fruit, nuts	19,455,500	9.7%	259	75,156	0.5%
26	Beverages and tobacco products	11,581,029	5.8%	72	159,864	1.0%
20	Meat products nec	10,726,771	5.4%	91	117,697	0.7%
21	Vegetable oils and fats	9,436,291	4.7%	416	22,676	0.1%
3	Cereal grains nec	6,698,548	3.3%	1,548	4,328	0.0%
22	Dairy products	6,698,213	3.3%	53	126,128	0.8%
64	Human health and social work activities	6,367,941	3.2%	4	1,634,373	10.3%
Total		200,246,423	75.2%	12.6	15,875,590	21.2%

The *Food products nec*, (GTAP 25) stands out as the primary contributor, accounting for approximately 18% of the total cropland footprint in the EEA-32 regions, amounting to 35 million hectares. The main factor driving this significant cropland footprint is the notably higher total cropland intensity, which measures 118 hectares per million US dollars. This intensity is approximately nine times greater than the weighted average across all 65 sectors.

Accommodation, Food, and Service Activities (AFS; GTAP 51) holds the second position by contributing approximately 11% to the total cropland footprint in the EEA-32 regions. This accounts for an estimated area of 22 million hectares. While the total cropland intensity of this sector is not remarkably high, it is the final demand directed towards this sector that serves as a key driver behind its significant impact. The final demand value for this sector represents 5.7% of the total final demand, contributing to the noteworthy results observed in this sector.

Wheat (GTAP 2) takes the third position and makes a significant contribution to the overall cropland footprint in the EEA-32 region, exceeding 10% and covering an area of 21 million hectares. With the highest intensity among all 65 sectors, reaching 1,755 hectares per million US dollars, it is an astounding 139 times greater than the weighted average across all sectors. It is worth noting that despite this high intensity, the final demand for the wheat sector represents only 0.1% of the total final demand within the EEA-32 regions.

Dependency analysis for Cropland Footprint in the EEA-32 countries:

- a. Food products nec (GTAP 25)** (see Table 11): Germany, France, and Turkey emerge as the three primary contributors to this footprint, with respective contributions of 24.4%, 12.3%, and 12.0%. Together, these three countries account for a notable 48.7% of the total cropland Footprint in the Food products nec sector.

Table 11. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to cropland Footprint in the Food products nec sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Cropland Footprint in the Food products nec sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors			Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors						
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Germany	24.4%	Oil seeds	37.8%	56.5%	43.5%	Germany	20.7%	Brazil	12.0%	France	11.2%
		Cereal grains nec	33.3%	92.2%	7.8%	Germany	53.8%	Poland	12.9%	France	10.3%
		Wheat	15.7%	94.4%	5.6%	Germany	39.8%	Czech Republic	22.6%	Poland	10.4%
France	12.3%	Cereal grains nec	32.0%	92.6%	7.4%	France	79.9%	Germany	4.2%	Chile	1.6%
		Oil seeds	31.5%	55.8%	44.2%	France	43.1%	Ukraine	10.7%	Brazil	10.1%
		Wheat	25.9%	95.8%	4.2%	France	84.1%	Germany	4.8%	Belgium	1.6%
Turkey	12.0%	Wheat	55.2%	52.6%	47.4%	Turkey	49.9%	Russian Federation	37.1%	Kazakhstan	2.0%
		Oil seeds	17.2%	35.6%	64.4%	Turkey	26.6%	Ukraine	14.0%	Russian Federation	9.9%
		Vegetables, fruit, nuts	12.5%	85.3%	14.7%	Turkey	84.2%	Canada	5.3%	United States of America	1.1%

In Germany, the leading contributors to its cropland Footprint within the Food products sector are Oil seeds (37.8%), Cereal grains nec (33.3%), and Wheat (15.7%). Among these, the Oil seeds sector stands out as the predominant source, showing an interesting mix of origins. Approximately 20.7% of the Oil seeds contributing to the Food products sector are domestically sourced, while a significant 35.8% comes from other EEA-32 countries, with France being a major contributor at 11.2%. Additionally, a noteworthy 43.5% of the cropland for Oil seeds relies on regions outside the EEA-32, including Brazil (12%) and the United States (11.1%). As for Cereal grains nec sector in supporting the food products sector in Germany, the country heavily depends on domestic production, accounting for 53.8% of the cropland. Another 38.4% is imported from other EEA-32 countries, with Poland and France being important sources. A small proportion of 7.8% of the cropland for Cereal grains nec comes from regions outside the EEA-32.

In the case of France, the major sectors influencing the cropland Footprint within the Food products sector are Cereal grains nec (32.0%), Oil seeds (31.5%), and Wheat (25.9%). The data indicates that 79.9% of cropland Footprint within the cereal grains sector, which supports the food products sector in France originates domestically. Additionally, there is a contribution of 12.7% from EEA-32 countries and 7.4% from regions beyond. The Oil seeds sector demonstrates a relatively balanced distribution with 43.1% domestic, 12.7% from EEA-32 countries, and 44.2% from external sources. Ukraine makes a notable contribution of 10.7% to the cropland Footprint used by the Oil seeds sector in supporting the food production sector in France.

In the case of Turkey, the leading sectors contributing to the Food products sector are Wheat (55.2%), Oil seeds (17.2%), and Vegetables, fruit, nuts (12.5%). As for the wheat sector, 49.9% of cropland Footprint originates domestically and 47.4% from external sourcing. such as the Russian Federation (37.1%). Contributions from EEA-32 countries are minimal at 2.7%. On the other hand, the Oil seeds sector in supporting the food products sector presents a different scenario. Domestic production accounts for 26.6%. A substantial 64.4% of cropland within the Oil seeds sector relies on sources outside of the EEA-32, including Ukraine contributing 14%.

In summary, the dependency analysis conducted in Germany, France, and Turkey suggests that reducing the cropland Footprint in the Food products nec sector may require prioritizing investments in key interconnected sectors, namely Oil seeds, Cereal grains nec, and Wheat, and Vegetables, fruit, nuts sector.

For each country specifically:

- In Germany, attention should be given to the Oil seeds sector involving Germany, Brazil, and France. Additionally, focus on the Cereal grains nec sector with Germany, Poland, and France.
- In France, efforts should be directed towards the Cereal grains nec sector within France, as well as the Oil seeds sector involving France, Ukraine, and Brazil.
- In Turkey, a key focus area should be the Wheat sector in Turkey and the Russian Federation.

b. Accommodation, Food and service activities (AFS; GTAP 51) (see Table 12): Spain, Italy, and Turkey are the major players, contributing 15.3%, 13.7%, and 11.8% respectively. Together, these countries account for a significant 40.8% of the cropland Footprint within the AFS sector in the EEA 32 region.

Table 12. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to cropland Footprint in the Accommodation, Food and service activities sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Cropland Footprint in the Accommodation, Food and service activities sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors		Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors							
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Spain	15.3%	Cereal grains nec	48.5%	69%	31%	Spain	48.7%	Ukraine	16.8%	France	12.5%
		Wheat	23.5%	82%	18%	Spain	48.9%	France	14.1%	Ukraine	7.2%
		Oil seeds	16.7%	25%	75%	Brazil	26.4%	United States of America	16.8%	Spain	12.9%
Italy	13.7%	Cereal grains nec	32.0%	79%	21%	Italy	40.2%	Ukraine	10.8%	France	9.6%
		Wheat	28.3%	69%	31%	Italy	20.4%	France	13.9%	Canada	11.8%
		Oil seeds	19.2%	31%	69%	Italy	13.6%	Brazil	13.0%	Argentina	12.9%
Turkey	11.8%	Wheat	34.5%	51%	49%	Turkey	47.7%	Russian Federation	36.4%	Ukraine	2.1%
		Oil seeds	25.8%	27%	73%	Turkey	16.7%	Ukraine	15.7%	Russian Federation	11.2%
		Cereal grains nec	18.0%	70%	30%	Turkey	63.0%	Russian Federation	15.6%	Ukraine	5.3%

In Spain, the AFS sector is significantly influenced by key sectors, namely Cereal grains nec (48.5%), Wheat (23.5%), and Oil seeds (16.7%). 48.7% of the cereal grains originates from domestic production, 20.8% from other EEA-32 countries (with France at 12.5%), and 31% from regions outside the EEA-32, with Ukraine (16.8%). As for the Wheat sector, 48.9% of wheat which is used in the AFS sector in Spain comes from domestic production, 33.1% from the EEA-32, including France (14.1%), and 18% from external sources.

In Italy, its major dependency sectors for the AFS sector in Italy are Cereal grains nec (32.0%), Wheat (28.3%), and Oil seeds (19.2%). As for the cereal grains, domestic production accounts for 40.2%, contributions from within the EEA-32 account for 38.4% (with France being a notable contributor), and external sources account for 21.5%, with Ukraine (10.8%). For Wheat, the pattern changes slightly, with domestic production at 20.4%, contributions from the EEA-32 rising to 48.6%, and external sources (31%), including Canada (11.8%).

Lastly, in Turkey, the major contributing sectors for the AFS are Wheat (34.5%), Oil seeds (25.8%), and Cereal grains nec (18.0%). As for the wheat, there is an almost equal distribution between domestic sourcing at 47.7% and sourcing from outside the EEA-32 at 48.7%. Importantly, imports from the Russian Federation significantly contribute to the external sourcing, accounting for 36.4%,

while EEA-32 countries play a minor role, contributing only 3.6% to the wheat sector in supporting the AFS in Turkey. In the Oil seeds sector, domestic sourcing is relatively low at 16.7%, while an overwhelming majority of 73.1% relies on non-EEA-32 region. Notable contributors to the external sourcing include Ukraine at 15.7%, the Russian Federation at 11.2%, and the United States at 11%.

In brief, the dependency analysis conducted in Spain, Italy, and Turkey indicates that to reduce the cropland Footprint in the AFS sector, it might be necessary to focus on investing in interconnected sectors such as Cereal grains nec, Wheat, and Oil seeds.

For each country specifically:

- In Spain, the focus should be on the Cereal grains nec sector involving Spain, Ukraine, and France, as well as the Wheat sector in Spain and France.
- In Italy, efforts should be directed towards the Cereal grains nec sector within Italy and Ukraine, and the Wheat sector in Italy, France, and Canada.
- In Turkey, a key focus area should be the Wheat sector in Turkey and the Russian Federation, as well as the Oil seeds sector involving Turkey, Ukraine, and the Russian Federation.

c. *Wheat (GTAP 2)* (see Table 13): Italy, Turkey, and Germany stand out as the top three countries making substantial contributions to the Wheat sector within the EEA 32 region, with respective shares of 18.2%, 18.0%, and 15.7%. Together, these countries collectively account for an impressive 51.9% of the total cropland Footprint in the Wheat sector. The result clearly shows that the Wheat sector itself is solely responsible for contributing to the crop footprint in this sector.

Table 13. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to cropland Footprint in the Wheat sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Cropland Footprint in the Wheat sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its 3 cascading sectors		Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors							
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sectors	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Italy	18.2%	Wheat	99.9%	99%	1%	Italy	97.1%	France	0.5%	Canada	0.5%
		Cereal grains nec	0.1%	65%	35%	Italy	26.8%	Ukraine	10.3%	China	9.0%
		Oil seeds	0.0%	24%	76%	Brazil	12.9%	Argentina	10.3%	United States of America	9.6%
Turkey	18.0%	Wheat	99.9%	100%	0%	Turkey	99.8%	Russian Federation	0.2%	Kazakhstan	0.0%
		Cereal grains nec	0.0%	67%	33%	Turkey	58.8%	China	13.3%	Russian Federation	6.6%
		Oil seeds	0.0%	21%	79%	China	12.2%	Turkey	11.9%	United States of America	11.5%
Germany	15.7%	Wheat	99.9%	100%	0%	Germany	99.6%	Czech Republic	0.2%	Poland	0.1%
		Cereal grains nec	0.0%	77%	23%	Germany	42.6%	China	10.4%	Poland	8.9%
		Oil seeds	0.0%	38%	62%	Germany	13.2%	United States of America	11.9%	China	11.1%

In the case of Italy, the country heavily relies on its domestic wheat production, which accounts for an impressive 97.1% of its consumption. The contribution from other countries within the EEA is minimal, standing at 1.8%, while only a negligible 1% is imported from countries outside the EEA.

Moving on to Turkey, the country's wheat sector is predominantly sustained by domestic production, with an overwhelming 99.8% coming from within the country. Importation from outside the EEA plays a negligible role, accounting for only 0.2%.

Lastly, a closer look at Germany reveals that domestic production overwhelmingly dominates its wheat sector, accounting for 99.6%. The contribution from EEA countries is minimal, standing at 0.4%, and there is no reliance on non-EEA countries for wheat.

In summary, the dependency analysis conducted in Italy, Turkey, and Germany indicates that reducing the cropland Footprint in the Wheat sector may require focusing on investments within the Wheat sector itself.

For each country specifically:

- Italy should concentrate its efforts on the Wheat sector within its own borders.
- Turkey should direct its efforts towards the Wheat sector within the country.
- Germany's main focus should be on prioritizing the Wheat sector within its own territory.

2.1.2.1.4 Forest Footprint (ha)

Sectoral analysis for Forest Footprint in the EEA-32 region:

The collective forest footprint of the top 10 sectors constitutes around 73% of the total forest footprint in the EEA-32 region. Additionally, the total final demand linked to these sectors accounts for 51% of the overall final demand within the region. It is worth highlighting that the two primary sectors, Forestry (GTAP 13) and 49 (Construction (GTAP 49)), play a substantial role in the forest footprint, together representing over 40% of the total forest footprints.

Table 14. Forest Footprint of the EEA-32 region by top 10 economic sectors. The GTAP 10 sectors' list is utilized, which is based on the Central Product Classification (CPC) for agricultural and food processing sectors, and the International Standard Industry Classification, Rev. 4 (ISIC4) for all other sectors. Annex 6 provides tables of the top 10 countries and their forest Footprint contribution to the top three sectors (i.e., sectors 13, 49 and 45).

EEA32_Forest Footprint (hectare)

GTAP Economic Sector		Total Forest Footprint		Total Forest Intensity	Final Demand	
Number	Description	[hectare]	[%]	[hectare/m\$]	[m\$]	[%]
13	Forestry	54,826,993	22.3%	5,017	10,929	0.1%
49	Construction	46,791,933	19.0%	30	1,548,128	9.8%
45	Manufactures nec	14,406,489	5.8%	57	254,626	1.6%
30	Wood products	12,916,380	5.2%	738	17,495	0.1%
51	Accommodation, Food and service activities	10,756,152	4.4%	12	908,493	5.7%
64	Human health and social work activities	9,515,594	3.9%	6	1,634,373	10.3%
50	Trade	8,861,074	3.6%	6	1,498,034	9.4%
56	Communication	7,609,305	3.1%	10	789,381	5.0%
62	Public Administration and defense	6,878,005	2.8%	5	1,377,434	8.7%
31	Paper products, publishing	6,152,886	2.5%	117	52,618	0.3%
Total		246,376,003	72.5%	15.5	15,875,590	51.0%

Forestry (GTAP 13) emerges as the largest contributor to the overall forest footprint, accounting for over 22% of the total forest footprint in the EEA 32 regions, estimated to be 55 million hectares. The main driver behind this substantial forest footprint is the high total forest intensity, measuring at 5,017 hectares per million US dollars, which surpasses the weighted average intensity among the 65 sectors by a factor of 323.

Construction (GTAP 49) secures the second-largest position, requiring 19% of forest-related materials and encompassing 47 million hectares of forest areas. Although the total forest intensity in the sector is relatively low (30 hectares per million US dollars) compared to the Forestry sector, the significant final demand for construction accounts for 141 times more than that of the Forestry sector and approximately 10% of the entire final demand in the EEA 32 region. This high demand serves as the driving force behind the sector's substantial resource requirements related to forests.

Manufactures nec (GTAP 45) holds the third-largest position in terms of contribution, but it represents less than 6% of the overall forest footprint in the EEA 32 region. Compared to the Forestry and Construction sectors, which exhibit significant total forest intensity (in the forestry sector) and substantial final demand

(in the construction sector), the manufacturing sector demonstrates moderate figures with a total forest intensity of 57 hectares per million US dollars, roughly twice the average, and a 1.6% share of the total final demand.

Dependency analysis for Forest Footprint in the EEA-32 countries:

Forestry is one of the primary sectors, meaning that the demand of forest resources starts from the forestry itself before propagating in the entire economy along the supply chain. This is the reason why no further dependency sectors come out from the analysis and forestry only is the only sector contributing to forest Footprint. Yet, countries in which the demand of forest is placed may vary, as explained below:

- a. **Forestry (GTAP 13)** (see Table 15): Germany, France, and Turkey emerge as the primary contributors to the sector, representing 18.1%, 12.0%, and 11.1% of the total forest footprint, respectively. These countries hold a significant role, collectively accounting for over 41.2% of the forest footprint in the sector.

Table 15. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to forest Footprint in the Forestry sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Forest Footprint in the Forestry sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its cascading sector				Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors					
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sector	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Germany	18.1%	Forestry	100.0%	99.7%	0.3%	Germany	99.0%	Poland	0.2%	Czech Republic	0.2%
France	12.0%	Forestry	100.0%	97.7%	2.3%	France	96.8%	Rest of Eastern Africa	1.1%	Rest of Central Africa	0.3%
Turkey	11.1%	Forestry	100.0%	100.0%	0.0%	Turkey	100.0%	Russian Federation	0.0%	China	0.0%

Germany stands tall, where the forestry sector is largely sustained by domestic sources accounting for 99% of the total. A modest 0.7% comes from neighbouring EEA countries, and a negligible 0.3% is sourced from outside the EEA-32 regions.

Similarly, France demonstrates a substantial reliance on its own resources in the forestry sector, with a whopping 96.8% coming from within its borders. The contribution from other EEA countries is a slim 0.8%, and a slightly higher 2.3% represents the biocapacity dependent on sources beyond the EEA.

Turkey, another noteworthy player in the forestry sector, boasts an almost complete reliance on domestic sources. In this case, nearly 100% of the resources in the forestry sector are sourced within the country, indicating a self-sufficient approach to sustaining this sector.

In summary, the dependency analysis conducted in Germany, France, and Turkey indicates that reducing the forest footprint in the Forestry sector requires a focus on investing within the sector itself. For each country, the priority is to direct efforts and investments towards their own Forestry sector.

- b. **Construction (GTAP 49)** (see Table 16): France takes the lead with 16.2%, closely followed by Sweden with 13.0%, and Finland with 12.6%. These countries play a significant role, collectively accounting for over 41.8% of the forest footprint in the Construction sector.

Table 16. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to forest Footprint in the Construction sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Forest Footprint in the Construction sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its cascading sector				Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors					
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sector	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
France	16.2%	Forestry	100.0%	81%	19%	France	62.4%	China	3.0%	Germany	3.0%
Sweden	13.0%	Forestry	100.0%	97%	3%	Sweden	87.4%	Finland	1.9%	Latvia	1.7%
Finland	12.6%	Forestry	100.0%	91%	9%	Finland	83.8%	Russian Federation	8.2%	Estonia	2.8%

In France, the forest-related resources supporting the construction sector primarily come from the only forestry sector, and a majority of 62.4% of the resources used in this sector originate from domestic sources. Additionally, there is a reliance of 18.6% on other EEA countries.

Sweden, on the other hand, has a high level of self-sufficiency, as 87.4% of its forestry sector resources supporting the construction sector originate domestically. Compared to France, Sweden relies less on other EEA countries, with just 9.5%.

As for Finland, it also relies on domestic forest sources for the construction sector, with 83.8% of the resources originating within the country. While resources from other EEA countries make up smaller share at 7.2%, an 8.2% comes from external sources like the Russian Federation.

In summary, the dependency analysis conducted in France, Sweden, and Finland indicates that to reduce the forest footprint in the Construction sector, it may be necessary to prioritize investments in their own forestry sector.

- c. **Manufactures nec (GTAP 13)** (see Table 17): Germany leads the pack with a significant contribution of 24.4%, followed by France with 9.2%, and Turkey with 8.2%. When combined, these three countries account for 41.8% of the forest footprint within the sector.

Table 17. Top three EEA countries and their dependency sectors contributing to forest Footprint in the Manufactures nec sector, including source regions and top three country contributions in each sector.

Forest Footprint in the Manufactures nec sector

Top 3 EEA countries and its cascading sector				Source region of Footprint		The top 3 countries contributing into the cascading sectors					
EEA countries	[%]	Cascading sector	[%]	Within EEA	Outside EEA	Country	[%]	Country	[%]	Country	[%]
Germany	24.4%	Forestry	100.0%	74%	26%	Germany	35.0%	Poland	8.7%	Czech Republic	6.8%
France	9.2%	Forestry	100.0%	80%	20%	France	61.3%	China	3.8%	Germany	2.9%
Turkey	8.2%	Forestry	100.0%	69%	31%	Turkey	55.2%	Ukraine	9.6%	Russian Federation	5.3%

In the case of Germany, there is a balanced dependence on various sources for the forestry sector in supporting the manufacture sector. Approximately 35% of the forest materials are derived domestically, while a slightly higher proportion of 39.1% is procured from other EEA countries, including contributions from Poland at 8.7%. Additionally, 25.9% of the forest material relies on non-EEA countries.

Shifting our attention to France, a different pattern emerges. The forestry sector contributing to the manufacture sector in France heavily relies on domestic sources, accounting for 61.3% of the materials. There is a reliance on other EEA countries at 18.7%, and 20% of the forest-related material is dependent on sources from outside the EEA.

Lastly, in Turkey, more than half (55.2%) of the forest resources from the forestry sector into the manufactures sector are sourced domestically. However, there is a lesser dependence on other EEA countries at 13.4%, and a substantial 31.4% of the forest Footprint is sourced from outside the EEA, with Ukraine being a key player at 9.6%.

In summary, the dependency analysis conducted in Germany, France, and Turkey suggests that to reduce the forest Footprint in supporting the Manufactures nec sector, it may be necessary to prioritize investments in the forestry sector.

For each country specifically:

- Germany should consider investments in its own forestry sector and other EEA countries, such as Poland.
- France should prioritize investments in its own forestry sector and other EEA countries.
- Turkey should focus on investments in its own forestry sector, other EEA countries, and Ukraine.

2.1.2.2. Economic potential of innovations by economic sector: Supporting MRIO analysis

For the review of MRIO or IO studies on bio-economy, the summary of the review is presented in Table 18. Some studies focused on establishing the IO model to have separated bio-based sectors and then derive the coefficient from the model to evaluate the economic potential of the bio-based sectors. Other studies applied MRIO or IO models to simulate bio-economy transformation with specific scenarios.

The indicators of each study are slightly different. For example, Loizou et al. (2019) used output multiplier, employment multiplier, output elasticities, and employment elasticities as metrics, while Ferreira et al. (2021) used diffusion effect and absorption effect (Table 18). If the output multiplier of a specific sector is 2, it means that if the final demand of that specific sector increases by one euro, the total output of the entire economy will increase by 2 euros due to the direct and indirect linkage relations of that sector. Employment multiplier refers to how many additional jobs will be created in the entire economy, for each additional employee in a sector, to cover the direct and indirect employment needs. Elasticities refers to the percentage change, rather than euro or job unit change, for the above-mentioned indicators (Loizou et al., 2019). Diffusion effect indicates income expansion effect generated from a sector to other sectors that provide input in the production of this sector (backward income expansion). Absorption effect refers to how much this sector must produce due to an increase in one monetary unit in final demand (Ferreira et al., 2021). In addition, Asada et al. (2020) measured the effects of substituting a certain amount of input material with bio-based material on employment (number of persons engaged in production and worked hours) and labour compensation (gross wages plus employers' social security contributions); and Lasarte-López et al. (2022) directly estimate the employment and gross value added from sector's production activities. Notwithstanding the differences between these metrics, we can interpret these indicators as proxies of economic potential.

Despite the differences in methods and indicators, some trends can be found in Table 18. When the sectors are included in the analysis, the value of indicators for food production, agriculture, and construction, and travel/transportation related sectors usually give a hint of middle to high economic potential. The results of textile and bio-based pharmaceuticals vary a lot across different studies. Some studies showed that these have higher potential than other sectors, while some showed the other way around. The indicators for

bio-energy, bio-electricity, and bio-chemical usually have values lower than other sectors. Such a general trend of economic potential corresponds to the top sectors ranked in Carbon Footprints (section 2.1.2.1.2, Table 6) for the innovation selection. However, the characteristics of MRIO and IO studies must be acknowledged to understand the results summarised here. The economic structure of the countries studied influences these indicators. For instance, a sector that spends less on direct labour cost than intermediate input, or a sector that has a longer supply chain will lead to a higher output multiplier (McNerneya et al., 2021), implying higher economic potential in this context.

Table 18. summary of literature review on MRIO or IO studies related to bio-economy

Paper	Study scope	scenario	Indicators	Results: the economic potential of different sectors*
Loizou et al. (2019)	Poland, cover all bio-based sectors + non-biobased sector if their output multiplier/elasticities are high	No scenario, but established the IO model that includes the bio-based sectors and estimated the coefficients	Output Multiplier	High: food products (including beverages), constructions (including bio-based and non-biobased furniture and construction material), travel agency Middle: agriculture, bio-based electricity, forestry, bio-based plastics and rubber Low: bio-based energy, bio-based chemical, bio-based textile, bio-based pharmaceuticals, fisheries
			Output Elasticities	High: constructions, food products, motor vehicles Middle: agriculture, bio-based furniture, bio-based pharmaceuticals Low: bio-based plastics and rubber, bio-based textile, bio-based chemical, forestry, bio-based electricity, bio-based energy, fisheries
			Employment Multiplier	High: food products (including beverages) Middle: bio-based electricity, bio-based pharmaceuticals, bio-based plastics and rubber, bio-based furniture Low: bio-based textile, agriculture, bio-based chemical, forestry, fisheries, bio-based energy
			Employment Elasticities	High: food products (including beverages), Middle: bio-based pharmaceuticals, agriculture, bio-based electricity, bio-based furniture Low: bio-based plastics and rubber, bio-based textile, bio-based chemical, bio-based energy, forestry, fisheries
Ferreira et al. (2021)	Spain, cover all bio-based sectors	No scenario, but established the IO model of bio-based sectors and estimated the coefficient	Diffusion effect	Agriculture (part of the subsectors), food (part of the subsectors) > agriculture (rest of subsector), food (rest of subsector), bio-electricity, bio-energy (fuel) > biochemicals, textile
			Absorption effect	Non-bioeconomy > agriculture (part of the subsectors), food (part of the subsectors), textile > agriculture (rest of subsector), food (rest of subsector) > biochemicals, bio-electricity, bio-energy (fuel)
			Employment Multipliers	Agriculture (part of the subsectors) > agriculture (rest of subsector), food, bio-energy (fuel), textile, biochemicals > bio-electricity
Asada et al. (2020)	Global, including a separate EU result, covers four sectors	Replace 10 ⁹ USD of original input material with bio-based material or residual material	Labor compensation	textile (+) > vehicle equipment (+) = construction (+) > chemical (-)
			Person engaged and hours worked	vehicle equipment (+) = construction (+) ≥ textile (+) > chemical (-)

Paper	Study scope	scenario	Indicators	Results: the economic potential of different sectors*
Lasarte-López et al. (2022)	EU, 2015, cover all bio-based sectors	No scenario, Sector analysis, based on economic data	Employment	High: food products (including beverages), agriculture (including forestry and fishing) Middle: paper and wood production (including bio-based furniture), bio-based textile, bio-based pharmaceuticals, bio-based chemical (include bio-based plastics and rubber) Low: bio-energy
			Gross value added	High: food products (including beverages), agriculture, forestry and fishing, bio-based pharmaceuticals Middle: paper and wood production (including bio-based furniture), bio-based chemical (including bio-based plastics and rubber), bio-based textile, bio-based energy

*The table only presents the sectors related to the high carbon footprints sectors identified in section 2.1.2.1 and the sectors that are identified to use the reviewed bio-based innovations in section 2.2. The sectors that supply the feedstock for bio-based innovation (e.g., forestry and fishery) are not included in this table. In the Table, “high”, “middle” or “low” refer to the values of the indicators and its hint to economic potential in high, middle or low. “>” means the values of the indicators is higher than the other sectors and thus also hints a higher economic potential than other sectors. “+” and “-” imply the effects are positive or negative from the original studies. “=” means the values of the indicators are close to each other, based on the results shown as figure form in the literature, as precise numbers were not provided in the literature.

The review of potential to transform traditional fossil-based processes with bio-based innovations in the high carbon footprints sectors is summarised in Table 19. The focused sectors are Construction, Electricity, Transportation, Accommodation, Food and Service activities. The Transportation here covers the transport nec (i.e., Land transport and transport via pipelines), trade, air transport, and water transport. With these four integrated sectors, the top 5 highest total Carbon Footprint identified from EE-MRIO analysis (Table 6) are covered, as well as other sectors with high total carbon footprints or high total carbon intensity.

The dependency analysis for the Construction sector (Table 7) is more or less aligned with the literature: the main sources of carbon footprints or said the main fossil-based processes within the sectors, are material (mineral products and ferrous metal), electricity/energy, and transportation. The materials that cause high carbon emission in construction sectors include cement that accounts for around 50% carbon emission in construction sectors (Labaran et al. 2022), plastic (Oberti et al., 2022), steel and aluminium (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022). The transportation emission mainly results from transporting materials, equipment, and workers to and from worksite (Labaran et al. 2022). The energy demand from building sectors, which covers construction, usage, renovation and demolition, accounts for 40% of Europe's energy demand, of which 80% is fossil-based origin (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022, European Commission, 2020). In addition to the above three sources, the carbon emission from construction sector also comes from waste management and operation of the construction site without preserving and recovering the trees around the construction sites (Labaran et al. 2022). The solutions for these carbon emissions includes non-bio-based solutions, such as use recycle materials, low carbon cements, local materials, non-bio-based renewable energy (e.g., solar, winds, or hydro), carbon capture and storage technology, and change waste management and cite operational practice etc. (Labaran et al. 2022). The opportunity of replacing traditional fossil-based processes with bio-based innovations is mainly focused on material, transportation, and energy parts. Thus, the further potential analysis only focuses on these aspects (Table 19), and the analysis of transportation and energy parts are combined with the Transportation and Electricity sectors in the same tables.

Bio-based construction materials from wood, waste and residuals from forest and agriculture related are the main innovations for construction recently (see innovation review from section 2.3). Both using wood, forest-based waste, and agricultural waste as new construction materials has economic benefit and market potential due to its current low market occupation rate, the abundance of feedstock resources, or the potential economic competitive and employment effects (Maraveas, 2020, Hildebrandt et al., 2017, Asada et al. 2020). Replacing traditional construction materials with wood, or construction materials from forest-based waste or agricultural waste also have positive employment effects (Maraveas, 2020, Asada et al. 2020). However, both have some negative effects or disadvantages from such replacement. For instance, cost and fire safety issues and the related regulation are the main obstacles to expanding wood related innovations or solutions within the construction sectors (Pitkänen et al., 2016). Agricultural waste-based material has some limitation in its application due to its lightweight nature (Maraveas, 2020). From the innovations collected in the Review Framework (see Annex 9, Section 2.2. and Part II of the report) we can conclude that most wood-based material or the new construction materials from forest or agricultural wastes have quite good technology readiness level (TRL) from 6-9 (see Annex 10). The TRL for some innovations of bio-grout, microbial bio-cementation, or bio-based insulation is relatively low (4-6 TRL) (see Annex 9). The economic potential of some of them have been identified at the lab innovation level (e.g., Iqbal et al., 2021), but there was not much economic or market research at the sector level.

Bio-plastic, one of the solutions for plastic used in the construction sectors, also have market potential to expand in the construction sectors as the construction sector currently uses 23% of the world's plastic production, and only 8% of which is bioplastic (Oberti et al., 2022). The TRL for bio-plastic varies from TRL3-

9 (see the collected innovations in the review framework in Annex 9 and 10), depending on the technology, sources, and type of feedstock used to produce bio-plastic, but many of them have TRL 9 and are already on the market. The main current issue is that construction products from bio-based and recycled plastic are facing a shortage and require more supplier for such products (Swedish Environmental Research Institute, 2021). No specific study on the employment effects of replacing certain or all plastic used in the construction sector to bioplastic was found.

The dependency analysis for the Transportation sector (Table 8) shows that the sub-components of the Transportation sector itself (see Annex 1 for further details on each sector and its component), as well as the Petroleum and coal products, and Electricity sectors contribute to the carbon footprint of this sector. Compared to the transformation of the Electricity sector with the important role of gas mentioned above, biofuel can play an important role in the transformation of the transportation sector (Cavelius et al., 2023). Especially, biofuel relevant innovations focusing on shipping and air transportation can be found (see Table 26 of the collected innovations), with a limited role in road transportation, possibly because this latter is becoming increasingly dependent on electricity: electricity consumption in road transport within the EU (which includes electricity used for electric trolley buses and to charge electric vehicles) experienced a notable (+80%) increase in 2021 compared with 2020. (Eurostat, 2023). Therefore, from Petroleum and coal products, we focus on fuel for the Transportation (Table 19) as one of the fossil-based processes to be transformed. Also, the Transportation in Table 19 includes trades, which covers the wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, thus not only fossil fuel but also production of vehicle equipment also included in the analysis for the Transportation sectors.

First to fourth generation biofuels are among the possible replacements of fossil fuel on transport (Cavelius et al., 2023). However, 1st generation (feedstock from food-grade rapeseed, soy, or palm oil) causes land competition and deforestation and increases CO₂ emissions, thus, despite a rather large market currently, this is not seen as an option anymore. 2nd generation (residue from agriculture and wood industry and food waste) has potential to open the market, but its feedstock may only be able to supply up to 30% of energy for transportation use (Cavelius et al., 2023). 3rd generation (microalgae and cyanobacteria biomass) has potential to open the market, but it still needs further development in technology to upscaling and reducing cost for commercialization. The TRL of 4th generation (genetic engineering) are even lower (Cavelius et al., 2023). For replacing the material in vehicle equipment with bio-based materials, a study shows its positive effects on employment, but no specific assessment on its market potential and TRL level.

The dependency analysis for the Electricity sector (Table 9) shows that the main sources of carbon footprints are due to the inputs that the Electricity sector gets from sub-components of the Electricity sector itself, as well as from Transportation, Petroleum, coal products, and Gas¹⁰. Solutions for reducing the carbon footprint of the Electricity sector include transforming traditional fossil-based processes to non-bio-based renewable energy or improving the distribution of electricity; yet different innovations transforming from traditional fossil-based processes to biogas are the focuses of this potential analysis here. The relevant literature not only focuses on the transformation of electricity but broader energy systems. A regional study in Germany shows that replacing all the natural gas energy to local wood-based biogas in the local energy networks (including electricity) would bring both economic and employment benefit to the locals, measured by indexes of health and safety, adequate remuneration, adequate working time, employment, knowledge capital and equal opportunity. The environmental benefits from this case are also higher than other scenarios that only replace part of the natural gas energy to biogas (Bezama et al., 2022). An EU level assessment took an even

¹⁰ It should be noted that the transportation of electricity or said distribution of electricity and their relevant CO₂ emissions are classified under the Electricity sectors, rather than Transportation sector, based on the sector classification in Annex 1.

broader aspect, an “optimized gas” scenario, meaning replacing the fossil-based energy production not only biogas but also hydrogen from non-biobased renewable energy (Guidehouse Inc, 2019). The results show that such scenario could create 50,000-300,000 direct jobs respectively in renewable electricity (hydrogen production), in the energy sector, in agriculture and forestry (providing feedstock to biomethane production), and in developing and operating digesters, thermal gasification plants, and electrolyzers. In addition, it brings new jobs in the construction sectors, technical and non-technical services, and operations and maintenance sectors by deployment of renewable gases.

Accommodation, Food and service activities refers to those providing short-term accommodation and restaurants in the GTAP description (see Annex 1), and thus the carbon emission of this sector is closely related to tourism activities (Lehikoinen et al., 2023, Camelia et al. 2020), which include the energy and electricity consumptions, vehicles and transportation provided by hotels, food waste and other kinds of waste generated by hotels and restaurants (UN Environment Programme, 2021). Therefore, the fossil-based process within this sector may be related to Energy, Electricity, and Transportation sectors mentioned above. However, the reduction in GHG emission from accommodation, Food and service activities can be highly influenced by behaviour change and non-biobased innovation, such as increases in the efficiency of energy and electricity use, reductions in the production of different kinds of waste (incl. food, water, and electricity), as well as by using smart equipment to control the use of light, water and air conditioning or through a re-balancing of actual guests’ demand and facilities’ supply (e.g., Ben Youssef and Zeqiri, 2022).

As summarised in Table 19, although there are some negative side effects, disadvantages or challenges existing in applying bio-based innovations in these sectors, the economic potential of these selected sectors to transform their traditional fossil-based processes with bio-based innovations is positive in general.

Table 19: economic potential of the high CF sectors in replacing traditional fossil-based processes with bio-based solutions

Identified high carbon footprints sectors	Fossil-based processes in the sector*	Possible bio-based solutions** ^	Potential to open the market**	Possible labour effect**	Negative/side effect**	TRL**
Construction	Material: cement	Wood and other bio-based material (e.g., timber, straw, wood, cork, bamboo, sawdust) for construction, for main construction material and for bio-grout, bio-based insulation, and microbial bio-cementation	Wood or forest-based waste: +	+	Safety issue and higher cost	4-9 TRL, depending on innovation and biomass types
			Agro waste or residue bio-based material: +	+	Light-weight nature of the materials that only suitable for certain application	
	Material: plastic	Bioplastic	+	?	lack of supply (currently, probably just a temporary issues)	3-9 TRL depending on types of bio-plastic and products
	Energy/transportation	See the rows for Electricity and Transportation		+		
Electricity	Production from fossil fuel based	Biogas	+/- (The optimal would be combine with other non-bio-based renewable energy solutions)	+ (domestic/local) +/- (The optimal would be combine with other non-bio-based renewable energy solutions)	Jobs related to coal mining or to operating fossil fuel power plants may disappear.	5-9 TRL
Transportation (land transport, transport via pipelines air transport, water transport, and trade)	Fossil fuel	1 st to 4 th Generation Biofuels	+/- (2 nd Generation) + (3 rd Generation)	?	-Same as above - 1 st Generation competed with arable land and caused deforestation -2 nd Generation has limitation in feedstock availability	1 st and 2 nd generation biofuels have generally a TRL of 8-9. 3 rd Generation have a TRL4-6 4 th Generation biofuels have an even lower TRL.
	vehicle equipment	Bio-based material	?	+	?	?
Accommodation, Food and service activities	Electricity, Energy, Transportation	See the rows for Electricity and Transportation				

*From literature & EE-MRIO dependency results (section 2.1.2.1.2)

**From literature and Review Framework (see section 2.3)

^Non-bio-based solutions are not included in this table

2.2. Existing Bio-based innovations: Introduction

This section presents the approach followed to identify the existing bio-based innovations that may have the higher chance to contribute to the achievement of the European Green Deal objectives, given the benefits they bring from an environmental and socio-economic point of view. This work has been conducted in parallel to the identification of the key economic sectors (section 2.1) to provide a comprehensive picture of the possible innovations currently available throughout all economic sectors.

Innovations refer here to the process of creating new or improved products, processes, or services that add value and improve or transform existing systems, technologies, or practices. The process involves the identification of a problem or an opportunity and the development of a new solution or improvement to an existing solution (OECD/EUROSTAT, 2018). Innovations can be classified in 4 typologies:

- **Product innovation:** the creation of new or improved products or services.
- **Process innovation:** the development of new or improved methods of producing or delivering products or services.
- **Organizational innovation:** the implementation of new or improved organizational structures or management practices.
- **Marketing innovation:** the development of new or improved marketing strategies or techniques.

Although the bioeconomy innovations fall in all the four categories, in this specific study the focus is on **bio-based innovations** that fall under the first two typologies as **they are defined by the European Commission¹¹ as new products or processes that use biological resources and biological processing methods in more efficient, sustainable, and cost-effective ways.**

Innovations based on biological principles may be the key enabling factors for transforming usual economic sectors into sectors relying on biological principles, thus helping to reducing the EU's dependencies from fossil-based resources for energy and materials and so advancing the achievement of 2050 policy targets. According to Stark et al. (2022), four bioeconomic transformative pathways (TP) can be identified, which are complementary to each other, but serve different purposes and affect different sustainability outcomes:

- **TP 1: Substitution of fossil- by bio-based resources.** This pathway is driven by the growing environmental threat of fossil resource scarcity, energy security, and climate change. Examples are the alternative sources of energy production from crops or forest biomass as well as the production of bioplastics to tackle the problem of waste generation and pollution.
- **TP 2: Increases in primary sector productivity:** in this pathway, technological innovations come into play for increasing primary productivity or efficiency. One example is the increased production of soybean in South America thanks to the dissemination of new agricultural technologies that increase yield but also allow for an expansion of agricultural land.
- **TP 3: Increases in biomass use efficiency and new biomass uses.** Such pathway leads to a more efficient use of biomass by processing industries, and it is driven by technological innovation as well as public policies that create new forms of biomass-based applications. Examples are the production of bioplastics from 2nd or 3rd generation feedstocks via the use of an integrated biorefinery making use of recycled biomass waste stream and wastewater.
- **TP 4: bio-based value added in low-volume / high-value industries.** This pathway is about the introduction of biological principles in technical applications (i.e., enzymatic synthesis) that can produce bioeconomic change with minimum impact on biomass flow. Examples are in the biopharmaceutical industry having low intensity use of bio-based input per monetary unit of output.

¹¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bio-based-products-and-processes_en

These four pathways can be used to explain the techno-economic mechanism through which a given change unfold (e.g., substitution, enhanced productivity or efficiency, product or process innovation) and may inform on the potential causal relationships between drivers and outcome of transformation process, thus providing entry points for sustainability governance.

Bioeconomy cannot be said to be intrinsically sustainable just because it is based on renewable resources (Tan and Lamers, 2021); rather, it needs to have “*sustainability and circularity at its heart*”, pointing to the fact that 1) primary biomass extraction should not lead to ecosystem degradation (sustainable use aspects), and 2) natural resources should be reused and recycled and the use of organic waste and by-products should be prioritized as feedstock, thus minimizing the consumption of primary biomass and eliminating unnecessary production of raw materials (circularity aspects). Sustainability and circularity can be also enhanced by following the cascading use of biomass principle, for which biomass should be used where it has higher economic added value, thus first prioritizing (when possible) the production of materials and then as a source of bioenergy (EEA, 2018; EC, 2022b). Also, priority should be given to long-lived products over short-lived products (including single-use products), and this applies to waste, to by-products and to primary biomass coming from agriculture, forestry or aquaculture (EC, 2022b).

Since the publication of the first EU Bioeconomy strategy in 2012 (EC, 2012) and increasingly so after its 2018 update, important efforts and investments have been put towards driving the knowledge around the bioeconomy, as well as developing the monitoring and assessment of its status and progress (e.g., Robert et al., 2020; EC, 2022a). Given the inherent complexity of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and its high-level ambitions cutting across multiple policy fields, a monitoring framework is essential to collect reliable data and robust analysis to ideally provide a holistic view of all the dimensions of sustainability and ensure that the European economic sectors are on track towards a real circular and sustainable bioeconomy (EC et al., 2020). The JRC, in collaboration with several Commission services and other stakeholders, is leading the action and developing a knowledge centre for bioeconomy centred on identifying, collecting and communicating relevant information on the sustainability (i.e., environmental, social and economic) of the bioeconomy, so to connect researchers, policymakers and other experts in the field¹² (Robert et al., 2020). Such monitoring system is able to represent the current status of the bioeconomy, but it does not aim to foresee future consequences. A forecast analysis would require additional key parameters (e.g. the intensity of innovations) that help keep track of the role of bio-based innovations as effective game changers to support the transition towards a circular bioeconomy, while also addressing other climate change and biodiversity policies. Accessing information on bio-based innovation from patents and registries is rather difficult because of the lack of specific codes for many of the bio-economy products, services or activities.

Furthermore, although various institutions, governmental bodies and international organizations are actively involved in promoting, supporting, and framing bio-based innovations within the bioeconomy (e.g., European commission, UNEP, OECD, IEA, FAO and may others), there is no single official classification that is universally adopted and endorsed, nor there are bioeconomy classes in any EU coding system or statistical classification (e.g., NACE, CPA).

Given all the above, the following sections intend to describe the approach adopted in our search for existing bio-based innovations as well as the criteria we defined to critically review innovations and prioritize them for a subsequent comprehensive analysis (section 2.2.1). Then, the final list of the most relevant bio-based innovations and the review framework through which to evaluate them are presented as outcome of the

¹² https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy_en

research (section 2.2.2). Finally, Section 2.3 combines the results of the economic sector and the bio-based innovations review highlighting the next steps of investigation.

2.2.1. Methodology of innovation research and criteria of selection

The research of bio-based innovations was conducted as a literature review on the web scanning both scientific papers, including review and research papers, and the grey literature, including project websites with their reports and communication materials as well as webpages of specific branded or patented innovations. The research and selection of innovations was done in four steps with the aim of selecting and prioritizing the most promising innovations based on some priority criteria progressively identified and applied to the list. The methodological approach is represented in Figure 4.

To collect an initial, comprehensive list of existing bio-based innovations, a review framework was developed in a MS Excel worksheet aiming at listing the bio-based innovations and analyse them against a set of evaluation parameters encompassing a description of the economy they pertain to, how they contribute to the bioeconomy, their environmental and socio-economic contributions, and an assessment of their implementation potential. An iterative approach was used to conceive the review framework while conducting the research and selection of bio-based innovation, as the framework was progressively tailored to allow for a complete understanding of the innovations and their interpretation as effective game changer for the transition called for by the EU Green Deal.

Figure 4. Schema of the methodological approach used for the research of bio-based innovations and identification of those most promising to be the game-changer for the achievement of the Green Deal.

In the **first step**, a comprehensive list of bio-based innovations was compiled based on the outputs of the literature research. For each innovation, an overall description is reported in the Review Framework (see Annex 10) based on the content of the related sources. The outcome of the first step is a list of 90 innovations, which was considered as the starting point to then define the selection criteria to review and prioritize the innovation to analyse.

In the **second step**, all innovations are analysed by looking at the economic or industry sector in which each of them is being implemented as final application or demand. To assign each innovation to the final economic sector, the GTAP Classification of 65 sectors is used, in line with the Footprint analysis conducted to identify the major driver in the EU in section 2.1.1.1, and specifically using the broader categories for the purposes of this Task (see concordance table in Annex 1). The assignment of economic sectors to the top 6 sectors identified in section 2.1.2 represents the first selection criteria for shortlisting the bio-based innovations.

In the **third step**, a further selection is conducted based on the analysis of the specific feedstock used to create and implement each innovation, the quality and circularity of the feedstock (i.e., its role in the value chain) and the technology readiness level (TRL). More precisely, the criteria used in steps 2 and 3 are as follows:

- Focus on the top 3 economic sectors with highest Footprint (Food, Agriculture and Construction) and give priority to the innovations using “waste” or “by-product” as feedstock.
- Focus on the remaining high-footprints sectors (Energy, Transportation, and Textile), and prioritize innovations derived from waste or by-product feedstocks.
- Select innovations derived from algae as primary resource (i.e., macro and microalgae, seaweed and seagrass).
- Prefer innovations with TRL equal or higher than 5, despite few exceptions with lower TRL levels are still factored in because of their overall relevance (e.g. macro-algae for nutrient removal. See section 3.3. and Annex 10 for further details).

Finally in the **fourth step**, all single bio-based innovations have first been classified into 8 typologies of innovations and 5 classes of feedstock’s origin. The typologies of innovations reflect the need to have broader clusters of innovations for our analysis, which refer to the general field of application rather than to single case studies. The scope of this study is in fact to analyse the feasibility/potential of contributing to the bioeconomy of the overall functioning of an innovation, while specific case studies are likely related to a specific company with a patented innovation technology or a branded product; promoting a specific company or patent was outside the scope of our work. Of the 8 typologies, six of them can be classified as product innovations, while 2 of them as process innovations (see Table 20).

Table 20. Classification of bio-based innovations based on the typology

Product Innovation	Process innovation
- Bio-based materials for construction	- Bio-based processes for pollution mitigation
- Bio-chemicals and bio-degradable polymers	- Bio-based processes for food&feed
- Bio-based food&feed alternatives	
- Bio-based textile products	
- Bio-based energy sources	
- Energy for aviation	

The identified innovations have also been classified according to the origin of their feedstock, referring to five classes as reported in Table 21.

Table 21. Classification of bio-based innovation based on the feedstock's origin

Land based feedstock	Aquatic/blue economy	Waste
Agro-biomass: it includes primary products, by-products and residues from agriculture and food processing. E.g., crops, straw, husks, bagasse, ash	Marine algae-biomass: it includes micro and macro algae	Industrial and urban waste biomass: it includes organic fraction of municipal waste, sludge and wastewater, liquid or solid organic waste.
Forest-biomass: it includes primary- and by-products. E.g., virgin timber, wood pulp and sawdust	Marine fish-biomass: it includes fish biomass and discards	

The fourth step of the analysis was conducted after consultation between EEA experts and ETC BE partners (GFN and SYKE). This consultation was triggered by the need to further reduce the list of 38 innovations identified in step three to approximately 15-20 innovations for the subsequent “*implementation and scalability potential*” analysis (see PART II of this report); such consultation embraced the following considerations:

- Within the Construction sector, innovations dealing with structural construction materials should be preferred over innovations focusing on filling materials (e.g., those used for insulation);
- Priority should be given to innovations with a clear end-point application in the key sectors identified by the Footprint analyses, over innovations pointing to bio-based molecules with various (not specified) applications.
- Innovations regarding mostly processing/extraction systems or chemical production of biomolecules are to be left out.
- Ensure the selection of at least one innovation per combination of typology and feedstock’s origin¹³, leaving out those innovations with limited information, and combining – when possible – similar innovations into a single innovation, merging all the related sources.

Once finalized, the shortlisted innovations can be fully analysed against the complete Review Framework.

2.2.2. The final review framework and the list of Bio-based innovations

The final Review Framework (see Figure 5 and Annex 10) for use in the analysis of the bio-based innovations consists of 26 parameters grouped into 4 pillars: i) description and economic context, ii) environmental contributions, iii) socio-economic contributions, iv) implementation potential.

¹³ Not all combinations of typologies and feedstock biomass use are possible as well as it is the case that multiple typologies and multiple feedstock use contribute to the same innovation.

Figure 5. Key parameters of description and analysis of each innovation in the review framework

Each pillar contains a series of key parameters to describe a specific aspect of each innovation. The key parameters are described in Tables 22, 23, 24 and 25.

Table 22: Pillar 1 of the review framework.

Description of bio-based innovations and the context in the industry/economy							
This pillar aims at collecting general information on how each innovation works, how it relates to the bioeconomy and where it fits within the sectors of economy.							
Description	Country	Economy sector (production side)	Economy sector (end-use)	Objectives of the bioeconomy Strategy addressed	Bioeconomic Transformative pathways (by Stark et al., 2022)	Feedstock use	Quality/Circularity of feedstock
To describe the functioning of each innovation, how it operates and where it is implemented in the final products	Countries in which case studies of innovations are occurring. To specify EEA countries, BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) and USA. All others indicate Other or Not specified if information is not available.	Sectors of the economy where the initial feedstock is harvested and processed to create and implement the specific bio-based innovation. The Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) and its 65 economic sectors are taken as reference	Sectors of the economy in which the bio-based innovations find their ultimate application as final products ready to be used or consumed.	The 5 objectives of the 2018 EU Bioeconomy strategy each innovation is going to address. 1 - ensuring food and nutrition security 2 - Managing natural resources sustainably 3 - Reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad 4 - Mitigating and adapting to climate change 5 - Strengthening EU competitiveness and creating jobs	According to Stark et al., 2022, transformative pathways are techno-economic mechanisms through which a given change unfold. In the context of the bioeconomy, 4 complementary (rather than mutually exclusive) pathways are identified through which the economic sectors or activities may become “biologized”, that is based on biological renewable resources. The 4 identified pathways are: TP 1 - Substitution of fossil- by bio-based resources TP 2 - Increases in primary sector productivity TP 3 - Increases in biomass use efficiency and new biomass uses TP 4 - Bio-based value added in low-volume/high-value industries	The type of primary natural/biological resource used to create and implement the biobased innovations.	Quality and circularity refer to the characteristics of the feedstock used and how it is sourced in the value chain of the innovation. The quality of the feedstock indicates if it's a primary/raw resource (i.e. crops), a by-product or residue (i.e. residues from agriculture like straw or bagasse) or waste (i.e. food waste or sewage sludge), while the circularity gives an indication of whether the feedstock is used as it stands, if it's reduced, reused or recycled in the value chain of the innovation.

Table 23. Pillar 2 of the review framework

Environmental contributions (positive or negative) This pillar aims at qualitatively assessing the positive or negative consequences from an environmental point of view of implementing bio-based innovations. A core set of impact categories has been identified, which are the following:				
Land use / land use change	Ecosystem services – provisioning	Ecosystem services – regulating	Climate Change	Biodiversity
an evaluation of the extent to which innovations are going to impact or change the land use. It may concern the area/size of land (increase or decrease), it can be the intensification of use of land or impacts on the soil organic matter.	How the use of biomass from the ecosystems is impacted when implementing the innovations. It can regard the biomass or water use for food, materials, or energy.	how the regulating services of ecosystems are impacted when implementing the innovations. It can regard the pollination activity, the water purification, flood control, nutrient availability.	major factors contributing to climate change are CO ₂ and other GHG emissions. Innovations may influence the amount of emissions or of carbon sequestered, and may affect the capacity of ecosystems to capture CO ₂ from the atmosphere as well.	factors influencing the biodiversity may be impacted by the implementation of innovations. These factors may include habitat protection or restoration, invasive alien species, richness of flora/fauna.

Table 24. Pillar 3 of the review framework

Socio-Economic contributions (positive or negative)						
this pillar aims at qualitatively assessing the positive or negative consequences from a socio-economic point of view of implementing bio-based innovations. A core set of social or economic impact categories has been identified, which are the following						
Innovation types	Economic potential	Economic barrier	Economic impact	Job/employment	Influences on culture, or traditional uses or local community	Other societal impacts
<p>According to Bröring et al., 2020, innovations can be categorised into four types that point to different challenges they are going to face. The category provides an indication on which economic potential or barrier as well as social acceptance should be checked. Innovation types are:</p> <p>IT I: Substitute Products IT II: New Processes IT III: New Products IT IV: New Behaviour</p>	<p>According to Bandarian (2007), cost-benefit analysis is the common economic evaluation for new technologies/ innovations and their commercialization. In addition, resources abundances and market potential also often mentioned in the economic assessment of an innovation. Therefore, 5 aspects of potential are used, which are not mutual exclusive to each other:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. No assessment from current research 1. Cost-benefit positive or cost-effective high or has potential 2. Cost-benefit negative or cost-effective low 3. Abundance of resources 4. Potential to open the market or existing gap between demand and supply of specific products 5. Decrease cost of carbon from the company/sector if the sector under the ETS or national tax 	<p>Barriers to the economic development of innovations can be grouped in 6 categories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. No assessment from current research 1. Market Barrier to enter the market 2. Small and centralized domestic market 3. Resource competition or limitation (e.g., seasonal issue)¹⁴ 4. Limitations (space or cost) on infrastructure and storage capabilities¹⁵ 5. Cost, management, and technology limitation in transportation/logistics on bioresources for the products¹⁶ 	<p>Refers the impact on other markets</p>	<p>How the type of jobs and the level of employment are affected by the implementation of bio-based innovations. There are 6 categories of assessment:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. No assessment from current research 1. Assess job creation from pilot level 2. Assess job destruction from pilot level¹⁷ 3. Assess other effects (e.g., to supplier, or wage) from pilot level¹⁸ 4. Assess job creation for full potential of the innovation 5. Assess job destruction for full potential of the innovation 6. Assess other effects (e.g., to supplier, or wage) for full potential of the innovation 	<p>Impacts of implementing bio-based innovations on the local traditions and culture</p>	

¹⁴ Salvador, R., Barros, M. V., Donner, M., Brito, P., Halog, A., & Antonio, C. (2022). How to advance regional circular bioeconomy systems? Identifying barriers, challenges, drivers, and opportunities. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 32, 248-269.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ Vivarelli, M. (2015). Innovation and employment. *IZA World of Labor*.

¹⁸ Korinek, A. (2022). *How innovation affects labor markets: An impact assessment*. Working Paper, Brookings Institution June.

Table 25. Pillar 4 of the review framework

Implementation potential					
This pillar aims at evaluating the factors that enable a full implementation and adoption of innovations into the economy. Key parameters for its assessment are:					
Feedstock availability	Technology Readiness level	Speed/timeline of implementation to arrive at TRL 9	Society acceptance	Policy and regulation environment	SDGs addressed/impacted by the long-term outcomes of innovations
An evaluation of the availability of feedstock per each innovation, primarily at the EU level then at the global level. The evaluation can be quantitative, semi-quantitative or qualitative. Such information may require additional research once the final group of bio-based innovations is being identified and brought to the next phase of the task (sub-task 4)	TRL is a scale indicating the maturity level of a technology or an innovation ¹⁹ , from the initial research to prototype and system development. Typically, there are 9 levels of TRL: 1 – Basic principles observed 2 – Technology concept formulated 3 – Experimental proof of concept 4 – Technology validated in a lab 5 – Technology validated in a relevant environment 6 – Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment 7 – System prototype demonstration in an operational environment 8 – System complete and qualified 9 – Actual system proven in an operational environment	it refers to the rate at which bio-based innovations are successfully developed, tested, and deployed in real-world applications. For the purposes of the Task, this parameter is intended to measure how quickly innovations may reach TRL 9 in a timeframe consistent with the 2030 UN Agenda, as it represents the time horizon and turning point of many target objectives of EU priorities and policies. Identified timelines are: ▪ Short term: <3 years (timeframe: 2024-2027) ▪ Medium term: 3<years>7 (timeframe: 2027-2030) ▪ Long term: >7 year (timeframe: beyond 2030)	Such parameter is intended to evaluate the positive (acceptance), neutral, negative (opposition), or conflict with respect to innovations based on the <i>Innovation Types</i> (IT) or on literature. 7 levels of society acceptance: 1. Negative based on IT and author judgement 2. Negative based on literature 3. Neutral based on IT and author judgement 4. Neutral based on literature 5. Positive based on IT and author judgement 6. Positive based on literature 7. Conflict based on literature	This parameter is going to evaluate how current policy, and regulation may influence the development and implementation potential of the innovation	This parameter aims at indicating which of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the UN Agenda are addressed by each innovation thus connecting the EU bioeconomy strategy with the targets of the SDGs.

¹⁹ <https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-12/trl-assessment-tool-guide-final.pdf>

To arrive at the final list of innovations, the approach presented in section 2.2.1 (see also Figure 4) is followed. At start, the first step of the approach results in a full list of 88 single innovations (see Annex 7) and their related description reported through scanning about 115 different sources, of which:

- 57 webpages
- 29 research papers
- 12 review papers
- 12 reports
- 5 other materials including project presentations, websites and grey literature

These sources constitute the reference point for all the subsequent analyses of each single innovation.

The first selection of innovations (i.e. Step 2 of the approach) resulted in a reduced list of 67 single innovations (see annex 8) by selecting those innovations with an end-use application falling in one of the top 5 economic sectors contributing to the European Footprint as identified in section 2.1 (i.e. construction, food, agriculture, transportation, electricity), plus the textile sector identified by the socio-economic analysis in section 2.1.2.2. A visual map of the 67 bio-based innovations and their connections with economic sector is given in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Classification of typologies of innovations (blue boxed on the left and right of the figure) based on the economic sector (grey boxes at the centre) of their final application. Not all the 67 innovations are visualized as some of them are grouped into macro-groups.

Then, the second set of selection criteria is applied (see Figure 4) and a list of 38 innovations is prioritized to be considered as game changer in the transition to a greener EU (see Annex 9), as they

- promote the use of by-products or residues from agriculture and forests rather than the primary biomass,
- develop solutions for using biological materials from industrial or urban wastes thus also alleviating the problem of their management,
- or finally use the blooming algae biomass in bio-refineries for multiple products and purposes.

Also, innovations with a high level of technology readiness are prioritized.

A map of the connection of feedstock's biomass derivation with the bio-based innovations is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Connections of bio-based innovations with the origin of their feedstock. Bio-based innovations are grouped into macro-groups.

The final list of 23 innovations, as selected after step 4, is presented in Table 26 and Figure 8 alongside a clustering of the final shortlisted innovations into 8 typologies and 5 feedstock's origins.

Figure 8: Classification of the 23 final bio-based innovations into typologies. Blue boxes are the typologies of innovations, white boxes show the single innovations. Single innovations can fit into one single typology (then nested in the blue boxes) or fall under multiple typologies depending on the applied technology and the final product demanded (central column of white boxes linked with arrows to the various typologies).

Table 26. Final list of bio-based innovations for which a complete analysis is conducted

Typology of Bio-based innovation	Biomass origin	Specific Bio-based innovations
Bio-based materials for construction	Forest-biomass	Lignin-based asphalt
Bio-based materials for construction	Agro-biomass Forest-biomass	Agro-waste as building material in construction sector
Bio-based materials for construction	Forest-biomass	Wood as sustainable material in construction
Bio-chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Agro-biomass	Natural biopolymers extracted from plant leftovers for a novel generation of bio-circular and plastic-free materials.
Bio-chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Marine algae-biomass Industrial and urban waste biomass	Bio-based and biodegradable polymers (PLA and PHA) used for producing bio-plastics
Bio-based processes for pollution mitigation	Marine algae-biomass	Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal
Bio-based energy sources Bio-based food&feed alternatives Bio-chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Marine algae-biomass	Macroalgae biorefinery for bio-energy, food& feed and bio-chemicals
Bio-based processes for pollution mitigation	Marine algae-biomass	Macroalgae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent
Bio-based Energy sources Bio-based Chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Marine algae-biomass	Algae-based biorefinery
Bio-based processes for food&feed	Marine algae-biomass	Chlorella algae ingredients for food, feed and dietary supplement applications
Bio-based energy sources Bio-Chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Industrial and urban waste biomass	Food waste used to produce PHAs and biogas
Bio-based food&feed alternatives Bio-Chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Industrial and urban waste biomass	Urban biowaste to have insect protein/microbial protein for food/feed
Bio-based food&feed alternatives	Agro-biomass	Food waste for feed production
Energy (for aviation)	Forest-biomass	Side-stream of the chemical pulp industry for fuel (aviation and shipping)
Energy (for aviation)	Agro-biomass	Jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin
Bio-based processes for food&feed Bio-based energy sources	Agro-biomass Forest-biomass	Agroforestry circular economy for producing animal feed, energy, biorefinery, fertilizer, wood pellets, board for packing, etc., and maintain biodiversity
Bio-based textile products	Agro-biomass Forest-biomass	Use wood fibre from Agricultural and Forestry waste to produce textile fibre
Bio-based textile products Bio-chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Agro-biomass	Feathers from poultry sector to bioplastic and other bio-products

Typology of Bio-based innovation	Biomass origin	Specific Bio-based innovations
Bio-based food&feed alternatives	Marine fish-biomass	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food (e.g., fish pulp, fish mince, surimi) for human consumption
Bio-based food&feed alternatives Bio-based energy sources	Marine fish-biomass	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce animal feed (e.g., Fish Protein Concentrates, Fish protein hydrolysate, Insect Meal, Fish meal and Fish Oil, Silage)
Bio-based textile products	Marine fish-biomass	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce leather
Bio-based energy sources Bio-Chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Marine fish-biomass	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce fertilizer or biogas
Bio-Chemicals and biodegradable polymers	Agro-biomass	Lignin as Bio-based packaging materials

Challenges and limitation of the innovations' review work:

- The application of selection criteria to the full list of innovations was necessary (including also the adoption of subjective judgements) as a complete review of the whole initial list of 88 innovations was soon realized to require time and resources beyond those available for this study.
- Comprehensive information needed to review all the innovations against all the criteria could not be extracted from the sources collected, thus highlighting the existence of knowledge gaps. Further research would be needed to complete the analysis;
- Matching each bio-based innovation (thus pertaining to the bioeconomy field) to proper GTAP sectors proved to be challenging as GTAP classification refers to the standard global economy and does not provide explicit indication of innovative biological processes, products or applications.

2.3. Part I - combined results: Prioritization and selection of the most promising bio-based innovations in the key economic sectors for a sustainable European future

2.3.1. Final list of innovations and sectors of application

Combined outcomes from the economic sectors' analysis (section 2.1.1) and the identification of existing bio-based innovations (section 2.2.1) allowed us to prioritize a list of innovations pertaining to key economic sectors. The final list of innovations consists of 23 single innovations, each of them is derived from one (or more) of the 5 identified biomass types and is implemented into one (or more) of the 6 key economic sectors driving the Footprints of the EEA-32 region (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. The final list of bio-based innovations is shown in the centre of the figure. Connections are also shown with a) the specific biomass type from which the innovations originate (left side of the figure), and b) the economic sectors in which the innovations end-up being implemented (right side of the figure). These 23 innovations are prioritized for the complete analysis of their implementation and scalability potential to lead the transition towards a greener Europe (see Part II of the report and Annex 10).

The most common type of biomass from which innovations are made is the agricultural biomass (8 innovations), derived from residues or waste feedstock of primary industries (i.e., bagasse, ashes, husk, fibres, stover, stubble) or processed food (i.e., waste food). Then, forest biomass as residues of the forestry industry (i.e., pulp and paper industries) and marine algae (primary biomass), which feed into 6 innovations each. Finally, fish marine biomass (i.e., discards from the fishing industry) and industrial and municipal waste (i.e., urban sludges, organic waste) are used to make 4 and 3 innovations, respectively.

On the right side, Figure 9 shows the top economic sectors in which the innovations end-up being implemented. Such sectors correspond to the results of the EE-MRIO analysis showing sectors with the highest overall Ecological Footprint value (see Table 1 in section 2.1.2.1.1). Of the total Ecological Footprint, encompassing multiple pressures on natural resources and ecosystem services, it is also important to highlight that the carbon component (i.e., emissions of CO₂) is the main driver, representing on average for all sectors 55% of the Footprint. In fact, carbon Footprint is the highest component in the top 10 economic sectors, except the food sector (GTAP 25, in which 60% is represented by cropland and 22% by carbon), and the forestry sector (GTAP 13, in which forest land represents 98% of the total Footprint).

In relation to bio-based innovations, the sector with the greatest number of innovations implemented is the food sector, which includes derived and processed animal- and vegetable-based food (11 innovations). Then, most of the innovations fall under 'other sectors' which mainly include bio-chemicals (i.e. bio-molecules and bio-fertilizers) and bio-polymers (i.e., bio-plastics). Also, the Energy/Electricity sector draws multiple innovations such as implementation of biogas and biofuels for alternative energies. Bio-based innovations in the sector of Agriculture (i.e. primary products and processes) regard mostly the production and applications of bio-fertilizers and the benefits from agro-forestry practices. Finally, 5 innovations fall under the Textile sector, 3 in the Construction and 2 in Transportation as bioenergy for aviation and shipping.

Given its complexity and the density of information, the complete analysis of the prioritized bio-based innovations against the whole set of criteria identified in the Review Framework (see Figure 5) is provided as Annex 10 to this Report. The analysis of each innovation is conducted primarily based on the sources found in the literature or on the web, as cited in the file itself.

2.3.2. Outcomes of experts' workshop

In September 2023, an expert consultation event was held online to present the work conducted within Part I of this report – the analysis of the industrial sectors in which bio-based innovations are most needed and the identification of existing bio-based innovations – and gather experts' feedback and guidance on the way forward. Attendees of the event were experts in the field of bioeconomy, biochemistry, ecosystem accounting and sustainability, circular economy and economic indicators, ecological economics, as well as practitioners working on the implementation of bio-based solutions and innovations.

Overall, experts found the work conducted to be a valuable contribution to the knowledge base on bioeconomy and were very interested on its continuation. Several experts highlighted the need to connect for the task team and the EEA to further connect with the various institutes working on bioeconomy issues, to compare results and outcomes, and further collaborate.

Concerning the analysis of economic sectors and the Footprint assessment based on GTAP MRIO model, suggestions were made to double check the Footprint results to avoid double-counting as well as properly explain the dependency analysis across multiple sectors (i.e. the use of electricity in China for the construction sector in France). The lack of commonly considered sectors - i.e. packaging, plastics, or textiles - was pointed out and clarifications were asked. Most importantly, a comment was made on the potential usefulness of calculating - in each economic sector - the impacts due to bio-based activities versus the

impacts due to non-bio-based activities of the classical economy, also considering the economic value added generate by bioeconomy vs. rest of economy.

Concerning bio-based innovations, the circularity of innovations was stressed, while also pointing out that aspects such as recyclability, durability, biodegradability, and reuse should be taken into consideration in the identification of innovations alongside the use of secondary natural resources (i.e. by-products, residues, waste). An initial draft version of this report was amended accordingly, and the revised version used to produce the present final report.

3. PART II – Key levers for the European bioeconomy: assessing the implementation and scalability potential of selected bio-based innovations

3.1. Introduction

Building on the knowledge and outputs obtained in the previous sections, Part II of this report assesses the implementation and scalability potential of the prioritized innovations to identify the “game changers”, that is those bio-based innovations that are likely to have the highest potential – if adequately scaled up – to help mitigating climate change and protect (avoid losses) and restore biodiversity, while providing economic and social opportunities. We first summarize how the previously selected 23 innovations fit into the context of bioeconomy based on the innovation review framework (Table 22) in this section. The analysis then is conducted by identifying the current level of implementation of the prioritized bio-based innovations in the EEA-32 countries (section 3.2) as well as by understanding the consequences (positive or negative) from an environmental and socio-economic point of view when considering their scalability potential (Section 3.3).

Based on the conducted research upon the prioritized 23 bio-based innovations and referring to their general description (Table 22), Table 27 represents a qualitative matrix showing how these innovations fit into the context of bioeconomy and specifically which of its 5 objectives are addressed (blue-coloured cells). In addition, the four transformative pathways through which innovations may unfold (as delineated by Stark et al., 2022) are also included in the matrix and orange-coloured cells indicate which pathway is addressed by the innovations. The assessment of objectives and transformative pathways is an interpretation of the authors based on the description of bio-based innovations and the related sources.

Table 27. Matrix showing concordance of each innovation with the 5 Bioeconomy objectives and the 4 transformative pathways (Stark et al., 2022)

		1 - ensuring food and nutrition security	2 - Managing natural resources sustainably	3 - Reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources	4 - Mitigating and adapting to climate change	5 - Strengthening EU competitiveness and creating jobs	TP 1 - Substitution of fossil- by bio-based resources	TP 2 - Increases in primary sector productivity	TP 3 - Increases in biomass use efficiency and new biomass uses	TP 4 - Bio-based value added in low-volume/ high-value industries
1	Lignin-based asphalt									
2	Agro-waste as building material									
3	Wood as sustainable material in construction									
4	Natural biopolymers extracted from plant leftovers for a novel generation of bio-circular and plastic-free materials.									
5	Bio-based and biodegradable polymers (PLA and PHA) used for bio-plastics									
6	Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal									
7	Macroalgae biorefinery for bio-energy, food& feed and bio-chemicals									
8	Macro algae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent									
9	Algae-based biorefinery									
10	Chlorella algae ingredients for food, feed and dietary supplement applications									
11	Food waste used to produce PHAs and biogas									
12	Urban biowaste to have insect protein/microbial protein for food/feed									
13	Food waste for feed production									
14	Side-stream of the chemical pulp industry for fuel (aviation and shipping)									
15	Jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin									
16	Agroforestry for the circular economy...									
17	Use wood fibre from Agricultural and Forestry waste to produce textile									
18	Feathers from poultry sector to bioplastic and other bio-products									
19	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food for human use									
20	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce animal feed									
21	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce leather									
22	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce fertilizer or biogas									
23	Lignin as Bio-based packaging materials									

The bioeconomy Objective n°3, which is *“reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad”*, is the objective with the highest number of innovations addressing it (14 innovations). Then, follows Objective n°2 *“managing natural resources sustainably”* with 8 innovations and Objective n°1, *“Ensuring food and nutrition security”* with 3 innovations. Objective n°4 (*“Mitigating and adapting to climate change”*) and Objective n°5 (*“strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs”*) are explicitly represented by 2 types of innovations each, although all innovations may contribute indirectly to tackle these aspects (e.g. innovations that replace imported fossil material may support EU competitiveness and the re-location of production activities).

As a matter of fact, the majority of prioritized innovations use waste or by-products as feedstock types to better manage and reduce the use of primary natural resources. Such feedstock comes from the food (in the form of food waste), agriculture (as residues) or forestry (as by-product) sectors. When a primary resource is used in innovations addressing Objective n°3, this is almost entirely referring to the use of algae. Algae are also a recurring primary feedstock in innovations addressing Objective n°2: given their biological composition, algae have a high potential to be used in bio-refineries for the production of bio-energy, alternative food and feed (thus also contributing to Objective n°1), and biochemicals (Seghetta et al., 2017). Agroforestry practices, discards from the fishery industry or animal farming (i.e. poultry) are then the other resources' type that may be managed in a more sustainable way. Objective n°4 is addressed by the two bio-based innovations dealing with alternative fuels for aviation and shipping sectors, which prevent the use of fossil fuels and thus reduce the emission of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. Finally, Objective n°5 is represented by the innovations making use of advanced technologies for converting urban waste feedstock into biopolymers and biogas.

Transformative pathways (TPs) as delineated in Stark et al., 2022 (see Section 2.2) have also been analysed for the 23 bio-based innovations. The TP n°3 *“increases in biomass uses efficiencies and new biomass uses”* is the mechanism most frequently used by the innovations (used by 12 innovations) as this is also connected to the quality of feedstock when it is by-product, residues or waste. On the other hand, the use of primary resources as algae can also fall in this TP as new biomass use. TP n°1 *“substitution of fossil- by bio-based resources”* is covered by 9 selected bio-based innovations, those that make use of biological resources to substitute the fossil ones. TP n°4 *“bio-based value added in low volume/high value industries”* is the mechanism through which 8 selected bio-based innovations unfold as they involve the development of new technologies through the application of biological principles of resource waste. Finally, TP n°2 *“Increases in primary sector productivity”* is covered by 2 bio-based innovations, one related to agroforestry practices that enhance productivity and the cultivation of a specific type of algae (*Chlorella*) to create food and feed complements.

The Review Framework provided in Annex 10 showcases the analysis conducted for the 23 prioritised bio-based innovations against the whole set of criteria selected for a full evaluation of their role in the economy and their potential to boost the transition to a more sustainable society. While constantly referring to Annex 10, in the remaining sections of the report we are going to analyse and comment on the most prominent outcomes of the framework to understand the level of implementation of all selected 23 innovations and their scalability potential by specifically looking at selected parameters of the review framework.

3.2 Level of implementation of the 23 selected innovations in 32 EEA countries

This section shows the implementation condition of the 23 selected innovations in 32 EEA countries. We first describe the methodology (section 3.2.1) and then summarize the results in a table (section 3.2.2).

3.2.1. Methodology

Some studies, such as Caldeira et al., (2020), consider TRL 5-6 as the “pilot scale” for an innovation, while the reference document (APRE and CDTI, 2022) that was used in this report for identifying the TRL of innovations indicates that the technology is demonstrated in the operational environment (and thus considered reliable from the technological viewpoint) when reaching TRL 7. Therefore, the information on the implementation status of an innovation at TRL 7 reveals a scalability potential compared to the case implemented at or below TRL 6. In order to reveal this information in presenting implementation condition of the countries, we classified implementation countries into two groups: one presents the countries that implement the innovation at the scale that reach TRL 7 or above, and the other one collects countries which only test in the pilot (up to TRL 6) or have plan to implement in higher levels but have not realized the implementation yet. As shown in Table 22, the country of implementation is one type of information that was collected in the Review Framework, which was either directly drawn from the literature that we used to collect the innovation, or from the literature that was further collected when filling other criteria in the Review Framework. Still, the implementation countries listed in the result section (Section 3.2.2) are likely not exhaustive.

3.2.2. Results of level of implementation

Table 28 presents the implementation level of each innovation in 32 EEA countries based on the collected literature. As mentioned in section 3.2.1, the list of countries is not exhaustive. For some innovations, there is no country listed. This might result from two reasons. First, the information of the innovation was mainly collected from the review papers from an overview aspect, so the information on implementation country was not specified. Innovation #2 (Agro-waste as building material in construction sector) is one example for such case. Another reason is that the TRL of the innovation is too low to discuss its implementation in countries, such as innovation #8 (Macro algae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent) which only has been tested in the laboratory.

Table 28: Implementation of the 23 selected innovations in EEA-32 countries

No.	Innovation	Countries implemented (reached TRL 7)	Countries that have test or have plan to implement but have not reached TRL 7
1	Lignin-based asphalt	Belgium, Finland, Netherlands, Sweden, Spain	Poland
2	Agro-waste as building material	-	-
3	Wood as sustainable material in construction	The example from the collected literature in this review includes Finland, Germany, Norway, Slovenia etc., but it can be expected that this innovation has been implemented in most of the 32 EEA countries	-
4	Natural biopolymers extracted from plant leftovers for a novel generation of bio-circular and plastic-free materials.	Germany (the innovation was taken from a start-up company in Germany. It might be other similar innovation implemented in other countries)	
5	Bio-based and biodegradable polymers (PLA and PHA) used for bio-plastics	Netherlands	-
6	Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal	(Denmark, Sweden: have commercial scale in macroalgae cultivation and show its capacity for nutrient removal, although it is not their primary purpose)	Estonia, France, Ireland, Latvia, Netherlands
7	Macroalgae biorefinery for bio-energy, food & feed, and bio-chemicals	-	Denmark, Ireland, UK
8	Macro algae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent	-	-
9	Algae-based biorefinery	-	-
10	Chlorella algae ingredients for food, feed and dietary supplement applications	Denmark, the Netherlands	
11	Food waste used to produce PHAs and biogas	-	Italy, (Spain, France, participated company in URBIOFIN project)
12	Urban biowaste to have insect protein/microbial protein for food/feed	Denmark, Spain (validation case from the project)	-
13	Food waste for feed production	-	-
14	Side-stream of the chemical pulp industry for fuel (aviation and shipping)		
15	Jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin	-	Finland, Netherlands, Norway, Germany, Switzerland, France
16	Agroforestry for the circular economy	Expected to be in many 32 EEA countries	Latvia
17	Use wood fiber from Agricultural and Forestry waste to produce textile	Finland, Sweden	-
18	Feathers from poultry sector to bioplastic	(Belgium, France, Spain, Poland: list the countries that involve both process and end products in the on-going project for this innovation. The project states the innovation will reach TRL 7 at the end of the project)	-
19	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food for human use	France, UK, Iceland	Spain
20	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce animal feed	Iceland, Denmark, Netherlands and Germany	France
21	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce leather	Iceland	-
22	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce fertilizer or biogas	-	-
23	Lignin as Bio-based packaging materials	-	-

3.3. Scalability potential: the status of assessment on scalability potential of the 23 selected innovations

This section focuses on the scalability potential of the 23 selected innovations. This report does not assess the scalability potential of the innovation directly. Rather, the report reviews (1) what kinds of scalability potentials have been assessed in the literature and the assessment results for each innovation, and (2) if the scalability potential has not been assessed, what kinds of analysis are still needed to assess the scalability potential. To this end, we first define the definition and criteria of the scalability potential to be used, present the procedures for this assessment review, and briefly summarize the methods for assessing scalability potential in the methodology section (Section 3.3.1). In the results section (Section 3.3.2), the report first presents the summary of assessment status of the innovation in a table, then summarizes the assessment results for the innovations that have not reached TRL 7 and finally summarizes the assessment results for those that have reached TRL 7.

3.3.1. Methodology

Scalability can refer to different meaning when talking about different scale-related terms, such as upscale, scaling up, or scaling out, and the definitions for these scale-related terms also vary in different disciplines and different sectors (Wigboldus and Leeuwis, 2013). To align with the Review Framework in section 2.2 (Figure 5) and utilize the reviewed information, we adopted two upscaling types described in Riondet et al. (2022):

(1) Upscaling – Upsizing from laboratory to industrial scale:

This upscaling refers to the process of an innovation that improves the technology/process maturity from the laboratory to industrial scale. Such upsizing process corresponds to TRL enhances from level 4 to level 7, making the technical feasibility of the innovation to reach industrial scale. This process aims to increase the production effectiveness, i.e., increasing the production per machine unit or time unit while minimizing cost (Riondet et al., 2022).

(2) Upscaling – Industrialization and massification:

This upscaling refers to methods for massive production and correspond to reaching TRL 9 (Riondet et al., 2022). Upscaling potential can be assessed through techno-economic assessment, which include assessing the technical feasibility to reaching TRL 9 as well as the relevant economic assessment (Riondet et al., 2022, Caldeira et al., 2020).

For both upscaling types, the potential (positive or negative) environmental contributions are included in the Review Framework of bio-based innovations proposed in this report (see Annex 10). Although the life cycle assessment (LCA) is the common approach for environmental assessment for scalability process and is usually implemented hand in hand with the techno-economic assessment for upscaling assessment (Riondet et al., 2022, Caldeira et al., 2020, Scown et al., 2021), many other monitoring tools exist to evaluate different environmental pressures and impacts. To assess the environmental contributions of selected bio-based innovations, 5 key impact categories that may provide a complete picture of the situation are identified and included in the Review Framework (see section 3.3.1.2) for the analysis of prioritized innovations.

In addition to techno-economic assessment and environmental assessment, feedstock availability is a critical limitation for upscaling bio-based innovations (Caldeira et al., 2020). Also, social domain is an important aspect to analyse scalability potential (Riondet et al., 2022). Based on these analysis methods and aspects for upscaling, we develop working flows to analyse the assessment status of scalability potential for the selected innovation, shown in Figure 10.

For each selected innovation, we first check the environmental contributions and feedstock availability for all selected innovations. Next, we will identify if it has reached TRL 7, based on the information collected in section 2.2. For those who have not reached TRL 7, the compulsory checking is whether there are assessments on technical feasibility to reach TRL 7. However, if other assessments were found from the innovation description and in the analysis of Review Framework (dash-arrow in Figure 10), the assessment results were also included in the results summary (section 3.2.2.1). For those that have reached TRL 7, we further checked the eventual implementation of a techno-economic assessment (including technical feasibility to reach TRL 9 as well as an economic assessment), LCA, and assessment on social acceptance and employment at full potential. The last two aspects were selected for social domain (see explanation in section 3.3.1.3).

Figure 10. Flowchart of scalability potential assessment

The following sub-sections provide a brief methodological description on technology-economic assessment, LCA, environmental contributions, employment evaluation, and social acceptance. In the results section (section 3.3.2), we will then use a table to show which innovations still lack which assessment for their scalability potential and summarize the assessment results from the literature for the innovation that have been assessed for their scalability potential.

3.3.1.1. Techno-economic assessment and Life cycle assessment (LCA)

Techno-economic assessment refers to the economic feasibility assessment under certain technology feasibility or scenarios, which is commonly used for assessing upscaling potential. It needs to define the assessment scope of the technology to be applied, so it usually includes information on current technology feasibility or technology challenges/limitation for further upscaling and can be assessed for a pilot plant or for industrial systems. In the assessment on economic feasibility, it compares the potential revenue and production costs at certain technology scenarios and implementation scales (pilot plant or for industrial systems). LCA is commonly conducted along with the techno-economic assessment for upscaling assessment. It is one of the approaches to evaluate the environmental performance (e.g., CO2 emission) by comparing to an alternative path or product (Caldeira et al., 2020, Riondet et al., 2022), and it can thus provide some assessment results for climate change aspect under the environmental contribution described in section 3.3.1.2. LCA also has some extended application to include social components and provide some assessment in social aspects, such as employment mentioned in section 3.3.1.3 and other social impacts (United Nations Environment Programme, 2009)

3.3.1.2. Environmental contributions: positive or negative

To evaluate the bio-based innovations and their potential to be “game changer” for a greener Europe, it is critical to understand the contributions they bring on the environmental dimension of sustainability, in addition to the economic and social dimensions. Environmental contributions can either be positive, thus bringing desirable consequences that enhance the health of ecosystems and boost biodiversity, or negative as they can jeopardise the status and well-functioning of ecosystems and biodiversity. To be able to manage the environment, we need tools that allow us to measure the pressures and impacts we pose on it and such tools are monitoring indicators. In the review framework proposed for the assessment of bio-based innovations (see Section 2.2.2 of this report and Annex 10), the pillar on environmental contributions identifies a set of five impact categories related to the environmental dimension of sustainability (see Table 23 in section 2.2.2 for their description): 1) land use and land use change 2) Ecosystem services – provisioning; 3) ecosystem services – regulating; 4) Climate Change; 5) Biodiversity. Such categories are critical to have a comprehensive overview of the environmental consequences of bio-based innovations, regardless of the specific monitoring tool chosen to do the assessment.

In the analysis of selected 23 bio-based innovations, we have screened the sources found in literature and on the web to understand if any of the 5 key impact categories has been analysed and eventually what tools have been used. Results of such qualitative assessment are provided in the following sections.

3.3.1.3. Employment evaluation and social acceptance

The social domain is an important aspect to analyse the scalability potential (Riondet et al., 2022): accordingly, the evaluation of the employment at full scale and the social acceptance of the innovation were selected as social domain for scalability potential in the Review Framework. The evaluation of the social acceptance plays an important role in the early stages of innovations’ development as social acceptance influences the market potential of a new innovation at a later stage (Kim, 2015). Meanwhile, the employment evaluation at the full scale helps to show the employment benefit and possible side effects from the upscaling of innovation. The information of these two assessments was directly taken from the contributions in the innovation review framework (see Section 2.2.2, Table 24 and Table 25). If there is literature assessing the employment effects of the innovation at the full sector scale or assessing the social acceptance of the innovation, it is included in the results summary.

3.3.2. Analysis status of the 23 innovations (Results)

Table 29 and Table 30 summarize the assessment results based on assessment procedure in Figure 10. More detailed results are summarised in the following two sections, divided into the innovations with TRL above or below 7 (see Table 30).

Table 29 shows that “climate change” and “Land use / land use change” are the two environmental contributions that have more assessments done for evaluating the innovations. Climate change category has been assessed for 15 out of 23 innovations, most of them (10 innovations) have quantitative assessments available. Land use / land use change has been assessed for 11 innovations, but only 2 of them have a quantitative assessment. 8 innovations have been evaluated for their contribution to Biodiversity, but only in qualitative terms. Finally, ecosystem services impact categories (provisioning and regulating) have fewer assessments and only one instance in quantitative terms. Innovations #6 (Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal), #7 (Macroalgae biorefinery for bio-energy, food & feed and bio-chemicals) and #16 (Agroforestry practices) are the three innovations that have assessments on all the environmental contributions.

For the feedstock availability (Table 29), the assessment has been conducted for most of the feedstock types. Some feedstock assessments were conducted for specific innovations. For some innovations, the description on feedstock is clear and precise enough to link to the quantitative feedstock assessment from other literature. However, around one-third of the innovations need more precise information on the feedstock they use to have quantitative assessment on feedstock availability, which can only have qualitative understanding of the feedstock availability based on other existing literature. The feedstock availability is not applicable for 4 innovations (see detailed descriptions in Section 3.2.2.1 and Section 3.3.2.2).

Table 30 shows that around half of 23 selected innovations reached TRL 7. While their feasibility to reach TRL 9 was seldom directly assessed, they can deem to have the necessary technological readiness for further upscaling based on other indirect information or literature. For the innovations that have not reached TRL 7, seven of them can judge their feasibility to TRL 7 based on indirect information or literature, while three of them do not have any assessment available.

For the assessment on industrialization and massification potential (Table 30), there is no innovation with a comprehensive analysis on all criteria, with the exception of innovation #6 (Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal) and innovation #9 (Algae-based biorefinery), which present all criteria marked under industrialization and massification potential criteria, although assessments on technology feasibility to reach TRL 9 and on employment effects were based on indirect literature for both innovations. Although techno-economic assessment and LCA have been conducted for a couple of innovations, some of them were conducted at pilot plan level (TRL 7). Also, although not all innovations have been subject to techno-economic assessment, other kinds of economic assessments are available for some innovations (see more details of each innovation in Section 3.2.2.1 and Section 3.3.2.2). Employment effects at the full potential scale has the largest knowledge gap when considering the scalability potential as the majority of innovations do not have relevant assessments found. By contrast, the evaluation of social acceptance is more common to access, or the acceptance or rejection can be inferred from indirect information.

Table 29: Analysis status of the scalability potential of innovations: Environmental contribution and Feedstock availability

#	Bio-based innovations	Environmental contributions					Feedstock availability
		Land use / land use change	ES - provisioning	ES – regulating	Climate Change	Biodiversity	
1	Lignin-based asphalt						
2	Agro-waste as building material						
3	Wood as sustainable material in construction						
4	Natural biopolymers extracted from plant leftovers for a novel generation of bio-circular and plastic-free materials.						
5	Bio-based and biodegradable polymers (PLA and PHA) used for bio-plastics						
6	Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal						
7	Macroalgae biorefinery for bio-energy, food & feed and bio-chemicals						
8	Macro algae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent						NA
9	Algae-based biorefinery						NA
10	Chlorella algae ingredients for food, feed and dietary supplement applications						NA
11	Food waste used to produce PHAs and biogas						
12	Urban biowaste to have insect protein/microbial protein for food/feed						
13	Food waste for feed production						
14	Side-stream of the chemical pulp industry for fuel (aviation and shipping)						
15	Jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin						
16	Agroforestry for the circular economy...						NA
17	Use wood fibre from Agricultural and Forestry waste to produce textile						
18	Feathers from poultry sector to bioplastic						
19	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food for human use						
20	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce animal feed						
21	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce leather						
22	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce fertilizer or biogas						
23	Lignin as Bio-based packaging materials						
		Qualitative assessment existing, no specific tools or results					
		Quantitative assessment existing, using specific monitoring tools (e.g. LCA, Footprint assessment)					
		NA: Not applicable					

Table 30: Analysis status of the scalability potential of innovations: Upsize, Industrialization and massification

		Upsize		Industrialization and massification					
		TRL \geq 7*	TRL \leq 6, but have assessment on technical feasibility to reach TRL 7**	TRL \leq 6, and no assessment on technical feasibility to reach TRL 7	Technology feasibility to reach or after TRL9**	Techno-economic assessment***	LCA***	Employment effects at the full potential scale**	Social acceptances**
1	Lignin-based asphalt								
2	Agro-waste as building material								
3	Wood as sustainable material in construction								
4	Natural biopolymers extracted from plant leftovers for a novel generation of bio-circular and plastic-free materials.								
5	Bio-based and biodegradable polymers (PLA and PHA) used for bioplastics								
6	Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal								
7	Macroalgae biorefinery for bio-energy, food & feed and bio-chemicals								
8	Macro algae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent								
9	Algae-based biorefinery								
10	Chlorella algae ingredients for food, feed and dietary supplement applications								
11	Food waste used to produce PHAs and biogas								
12	Urban biowaste to have insect protein/microbial protein for food/feed								
13	Food waste for feed production								
14	Side-stream of the chemical pulp industry for fuel (aviation and shipping)								
15	Jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin								
16	Agroforestry for the circular economy...								
17	Use wood fiber from Agricultural and Forestry waste to produce textile								
18	Feathers from poultry sector to bioplastic								
19	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food for human use								
20	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce animal feed								
21	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce leather								
22	Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce fertilizer or biogas								
23	Lignin as Bio-based packaging materials								

*Light green: TRL across from TRL <7 to TRL \geq 7 (e.g., TRL 4-7). The ranges mainly result from TRL differences between specific application/products, or different feedstock types under the same innovation; dark green: TRL \geq 7; white: TRL \leq 6, These three categories have been defined according to the initial literature review that was used to identify the innovation. Further collected literature showing higher implementation levels in different countries is considered as indirect information (see explanation for**) for assessing technological feasibility for further upscaling. ** Light green: indirect assessment based on other information or literature; dark green: direct assessment on the innovations. *** Light green: Assessment at the TRL 7 (scope of a pilot plan); dark green: assessment at TRL 9 (scope of industrialization).

3.3.2.1. Case by case analysis of upscaling – upsizing innovations below TRL 7

Innovation #5 - Bio-based and biodegradable polymers (PLA and PHA) used for producing bio-plastics (3rd generation, feedstock extracted from wide ranges of sources, including industrial and municipal waste or algae etc): The TRL for this innovation in general is low (TRL 3-4) (Wellenreuther and Wolf, 2020), although the TRL can vary depending on the feedstock type. For instance, using wastewater to produce PHA might have a higher TRL (at pilot level, thus level 5-6 or higher) as in the case of a Dutch company, which produces PHA through this feedstock (Gutschmann et al., 2022). Due to the wide range of the feedstock types, it is hard to find a direct assessment for upscaling of the entire innovation that covered all the feedstock types. However, the potential to produce PHA from algae and municipal waste can be found in Gutschmann et al. (2022), although they distinguish municipal waste as feedstock of 2nd generation from algae as feedstock of 3rd generation. There are some LCA and economic assessments of producing PHA from municipal wastewater treatment plant at municipal level or at level of wastewater treatment plant (Abedi, 2023, Crutchik et al., 2020). According to the Review Framework (see Annex 10), the impact category of “climate change” of the environmental contributions has been assessed by Wellenreuther and Wolf (2020), stating that - regardless of the specific type of feedstock - carbon emissions associated with the extraction of feedstock from food plant as well as the emissions due to the final disposal in landfill are reduced or avoided; however, biorefinery processes in the later stages of production may still be characterized by a high energy intensity, due to the low degree of technological maturity. Further search for specific studies that assess the environmental contributions of 3rd (or more) generation feedstock for producing bio-plastics is required.

Innovation #6 - Macroalgae cultivation for nutrient removal from the sea: Farming and harvesting cultivated macroalgae is a newly proposed approach to remove nutrients and control eutrophication in the brackish Baltic Sea (Kotta et al., 2022; Kulikowski et al., 2021). These cultivated macroalgae can have a variety of uses, and this innovation can thus be regarded as the input for Innovation #7. The four species, *Ceramium tenuicorne*, *Furcellaria lumbricalis*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, that are most suitable to be cultivated in the Baltic Sea are all still at the experimental to pilot stages. However, *Ulva intestinalis* is already commercially cultivated in Japan. In addition, Sweden and Denmark have commercial farms for other macroalgae species (Kulikowski et al., 2021). Therefore, technology feasibility for further upscaling can be expected. The main challenges for further upscaling of macroalgae cultivation and harvest in Europe include the cost of labour, shortage of skilled labour, and the automatization of the production process (Sharmila et al., 2021). Seasonality issues and the regulation and social acceptance of seaweed cultivation farm are also barriers (Sharmila et al., 2021, Lähteenmäki-Uutel et al., 2021). Concerning feedstock, assessments of cultivation potential and current production level for some specific species can be found in Kotta et al., (2022), Kulikowski et al., (2021), Gutschmann, (2022), and Seghetta et al., (2016). According to these studies, the most suitable areas and production potential within the Baltic Sea vary depending on the species, but production potential is generally good and especially higher in the south and outer Baltic Sea areas. Despite the low TRL level, several studies were found in literature reporting qualitative as well as quantitative assessments of the environmental contributions of this innovation (see Annex 10). Qualitative assessments have been found related to the “land use/land use change”, “ES provisioning” and “biodiversity” categories: macroalgae can be cultivated offshore in small-scale aquatic farms, thus avoiding the competition of land use with agriculture (Seghetta et al., 2017); algae can constitute biomass production for animal and agricultural use (feed and fertilizers) (Seghetta et al., 2017), while also functioning as habitat and refuge from microorganisms to macrofauna (Kotta et al., 2022). Quantitative assessments are mostly based on LCA approaches (Seghetta et al., 2016) as well as chemical-physical analysis of algae and their environmental conditions for growth modelling (Kotta et al., 2022) to assess the climate change mitigation potential via carbon sequestration and their capacity to regulate the environmental conditions of water bodies by

removing excess of nutrients and pollutants. All in all, it is important to highlight that such findings are based on modelled configurations of standard farms. Practical applications in the real environmental may differ in the ecological consequences that a large-scale expansion could bring.

Innovation #7 - Macroalgae biorefinery for bioenergy, food & feed, and bio-chemicals: This innovation can be seen as the follow-up stage of Innovation #6, as it uses cultivated macroalgae. The review focuses on the stages after macroalgae are harvested to the production of relevant biorefinery products. As the macroalgae species, biorefinery process and products are various under this innovation, the review below only covered part of the process and products or for specific species. Couple of studies indicated its technical barriers to reach TRL 7 and TRL 9 (e.g., Zhang and Thomsen, 2021, Sharmila et al., 2021, Adams et al., 2021) and conducted techno-economic assessments at pilot and industrial level within and outside EU (e.g., Zhang and Thomsen, 2021, Llano et al., 2023, Chong et al., 2020) and LCA for the environmental sustainability of the innovation (e.g., Zhang and Thomsen, 2021, Seghetta et al., 2016b). Techno-economic assessments for brown macroalgae *Laminaria digitata*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, and *Saccharina latissima* extraction show that the innovation at pilot and industrial level can be economic feasible only if the technical barriers of extracting valuable compound from macroalgae can be overcome (Zhang and Thomsen, 2021). For bio-energy from *Ulva rigida*, the techno-economic assessment showed economic feasibility at plant level (Llano et al., 2023). The social acceptability of the relevant products is positive (Kulikowski et al., 2021). Environmental contributions and feedstock assessment are the same as innovation #6, and Seghetta et al., (2016) provide quantitative information on the production capacity for certain products (e.g., Danish water in 2014 has the potential to produce 150 Mg/km² of *Saccharina latissimi* usable for producing fertilizers).

Innovation #8 - Macroalgae and mussel for nutrients removal from WWTP effluent: As of 2023, this innovation is still at TRL 3 in the laboratory (van der Meer et al., 2023), and assessments are missing concerning the technical feasibility for upscaling, as well as the techno-economic and other social assessments. Likewise, only qualitative environmental contributions have been assessed for this innovation, especially as for the regulating ecosystems services indicating an efficiency in the capacity of nutrient removal and filtration, and thus also contributing to lower the adverse effects on aquatic ecosystems (i.e. positive effect on Biodiversity) (van der Meer et al., 2023). The feedstock assessment is not applicable for this innovation as the cultivation of macroalgae and mussel for this innovation should be in artificial system; nonetheless this innovation might be primarily limited by the capacity or possibility to install an infrastructure at the end of wastewater treatment plants (technological limitation) rather than by the feedstock available.

Innovation #9 - (Micro) algae-based biorefinery (biofuel): Different from innovation #6 and #7, instead of using macroalgae, this innovation uses microalgae as feedstock. There is no direct study assessing its technical feasibility to further reach TRL 7, but relevant techno-economic assessments and LCA have been done (e.g., Wiatrowski et al., 2022, Saral et al, 2022, Thomassen et al., 2017), which indicate some technology limitation but also economic potential for upscaling through optimal strategy and suitable co-products. Most environmental assessments of microalgae biorefineries aim at analysing the environmental impacts using an LCA approach, although the low TRL of such technology does not allow to cover the whole range of input and output across the entire life cycle, thus providing unclear results on the most relevant impact categories (Thomassen et al., 2017). Nevertheless, climate change and resource depletion are the most frequently cited impact categories, with fossil fuels and water on top of the resources most affected. Then, the following impact categories may be also relevant: eutrophication, acidification, eco-toxicity, human toxicity, photochemical smog, ozone depletion, ionizing radiation and air emissions (Thomassen et al., 2017), although further evaluation is needed. Some social-economic assessments and reviews also have been done for microalgae biofuel. The studies reveal that sustainability target from societies and economic opportunity

are in general positive for such innovation, but the direction of policy is determinant for the development of the relevant industries (Moshood et al., 2021, Sharmila et al., 2021).

Innovation #11 - Food waste used to produce PHAs and biogas: There is no direct technology feasibility assessment found for this innovation, but a techno-economic assessment at pilot plant level was conducted and showed its positive economic feasibility (Rajendran & Han, 2022). According to the sources found in literature (Moretto et al., 2020, Battista et al., 2019), no quantitative studies of environmental contributions of such technology have been issued. However, a qualitative statement is made (Moretto et al., 2020) on the biorefinery capacity to minimizing energy consumption and waste generation while using available renewable resources like organic fraction of municipal solid waste and biological sludge. Avitabile et al. (2023) assessed food waste generation from EU, which indicated that 84 million tonnes of wet weight were generated in 2018.

Innovation #13 – Food waste for feed production: This is an innovation from a project, NOSHAN (2016). According to the main reference found on the website (NOSHAN, 2016), a LCA study was undertaken to assess the environmental impacts of the feed alternative supply chain, showing clear positive impacts compared to conventional feed production. Specifically, lower agricultural land occupation and natural land transformation are consequences observed in the category impact of “land use/land use change” and reduced energy needs and CO₂ emissions observed in the “climate change” category (see Annex 10). The project website (NOSHAN, 2016) also summarised the condition of the technology developed in this project; it showed that some technologies have been considered in the food and feed sectors, but some technologies need further development to seek the profitability. One of the developed technologies has reached TRL 9 in the USA but not yet in Europe. The assessment on feedstock availability is the same as innovation #11 – i.e., 84 million tonnes of food waste generated in the EU in 2018 – although further research would be needed to quantify how many feeds would be produced from this feedstock and how to regulate and manage competition among innovations for the same feedstock.

Innovation #14 - Side-stream of the chemical pulp industry for fuel (for aviation and shipping): This innovation can be seen together with Innovation #15. They aim for the same product based on similar processes but from different feedstock. This innovation will use the side-stream of the chemical pulping industry, i.e., bark and saw dust, as feedstock (Jaiyeola et al., 2023, Baudouin et al., 2020). The innovation is from an on-going project, BL2F (2020). According to information on the project website (BL2F, 2020), they are expected to conduct techno-economic assessment, environmental and social acceptance evaluation, and validate evaluation of the supply chain. Another LCA assessment of similar aviation fuel innovation based on residual soft wood (saw dust) has been conducted at EU level (Puschnigg et al., 2023), indicating the possibility to save up to about 80% of the GHG emissions with a best-case set-up. As for environmental contributions, the Project’s ultimate goal is to contribute to the decarbonization of transport sector in the EU by widely implementing its drop-in biofuel, which will contribute to decrease the use of fossil fuels and thus possibly reduce the emissions along the whole production line. However, no quantitative assessment of the reduction of the specific supply chain has been performed yet (according to the website), and contributions in other environmental impact categories have not been declared.

Innovation #15 - Jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin: The TRL for this innovation based on agricultural waste (e.g., corn stover, wheat straw, tomato steam) is still low. For the European countries that research on this innovation (Table 28), there are still mainly at the laboratory stage (TRL 3-4) (e.g., EHL CATHOL, 2020; Gosselink, 2022) and no assessment on higher technical feasibility at the higher TRL yet. However, the US has more research for scale up and technology-economic assessment at plant level (Shen et al., 2018, Gregg et al., 2023). No analysis as for the environmental contributions are found in the literature

collected in the review framework. More research is thus needed for these fields. The amount of agricultural waste generated from the EU can be found in Avitabile et al. (2023), but the amount of waste lignin produced from these agricultural wastes needs to be further investigated.

Innovation #16 - Agroforestry circular economy for producing animal feed, energy, biorefinery, fertilizer, wood pellets, board for packing etc. and maintain biodiversity: The TRL for this innovation is low (TRL 4) as the innovation was taken from an example that is in the experimental field in Latvia (RDI2CLUB, 2020). However, agroforestry is a rather mature approach that many EU countries have implemented (e.g., Mosquera-Losada et al., 2018), and the assessment on scalability potential of agroforestry systems and their connection to circular economy should be further checked case by case. Agroforestry practices are reported to be the best circular economy approaches as they also bring positive contributions to the environment: they provide numerous provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting ecosystem services, although little quantitative assessment – especially on the climate change – are being published (Pantera et al., 2021). The analysis conducted in the review framework (see Annex 10) reports qualitative assessments in all the impact categories of environmental contributions: “land use” is affected with multifunctional plantation in which forest and agricultural plants are combined on a large scale; the “provisioning services” are related to the use of trees’ chips as firewood, wood pellets, sauna boards and board for packaging; the “regulating services” come from residuals and by-products (i.e. wood ash, digestate and wastewater sludge) that can be used as fertilizers; as for “climate change” agroforestry is reported to be a carbon neutral system after 10 years; and finally, plantations provide feeds for wild birds and animals thus helping to maintain “biodiversity”. Further research is needed to find additional studies that may quantify the positive or negative contributions to the environment of agroforestry practices, especially regarding the actual productivity of land use. Investigations in this direction are expected to be carried out within the context of the ETC BE 2024 activities, task “*Agri-food systems contributing to biodiversity objectives*”.

3.3.2.2. Case by case analysis of Upscaling – industrialization and massification of innovations at TRL7 or above

Innovation #1 - Lignin-based asphalt: There is no assessment on employment effects of the innovation of lignin-based asphalt upscales to full potential scale. There is some news (e.g., Kennedy, 2021) that show its positive social acceptance, but no research really has investigated its social acceptance. Large amount of technical studies for the innovation focused on the laboratory and pilot levels (see review in Gaudenzi et al., 2023), but only one project (Haaksman et al., 2022) conducted techno-economic analysis and LCA for upscaling lignin-based asphalt innovation after reach TRL 9 in the case of fully applying the innovation in the Netherlands (Haaksman et al., 2022, Moretti et al., 2022, Corona, et al., 2022). Lignin-based asphalt entails environmental trade-offs regarding circularity and climate change, and thus various quantitative assessments have been investigated to evaluate the specific environmental contributions (e.g. LCA, material circularity index, biogenic carbon storage). Combining the various metrics can provide a good overall picture of its environmental sustainability, but it also poses methodological challenges due to the circularity nature and multifunctionality processes at play (Corona et al., 2022). Based on the literature review conducted for the Review Framework (Annex 10), existing studies assessed the impact categories of land use change (qualitative assessment), ES provisioning and the climate change (quantitative assessments). Specifically, lignin-based asphalt from pulp and paper industries does not have a direct link with land use and land use change; the Material circularity indicator (MCI) can be used to measure the provisioning services of ecosystems (Corona et al., 2022), and LCA is the usual approach to assess the climate change impact category (Corona et al., 2022). LCA results show that lignin-based asphalt can have 25-70% of reduction of climate impact in different layers of asphalt application compared to conventional asphalts (Haaksman et al., 2022,

Moretti et al., 2022, Corona, et al., 2022). The techno-economic analysis shows that the cost of the lignin-based asphalt with different level of mixtures with lignin is comparable with the conventional asphalts but not economically viable to substitute bitumen with large scale of lignin (Haaksman et al., 2022, Gaudenzi et al., 2023). Other economic analysis also shows that cost of lignin-based asphalt could range from lower to higher than conventional asphalts, depending on the percentage and composition of lignin-based asphalt (Xu et al., 2021, Zhang et al, 2016). The feedstock availability was assessed for all lignin production potential, so the feedstock competition among different lignin-based products was not considered. Globally, the biosphere has a stock of about 300 billion tons of accessible lignin and an annual growth of about 20 billion tones, making lignin (constituting about 15–25% of the total dry weight of woody plant material) the second most abundant bio-polymer after cellulose; meanwhile, the pulp and papermaking industries produce approximately 50 million tons of lignin per year (Chauhan et al., 2022), and Europe accumulates approximately 17 million tons of unwanted lignin every year (Circular Bio-based Europe, 2022). Further investigation would be needed to understand how much lignin-based asphalt could be produced out of this available feedstock, and how much bitumen-based asphalt it could substitute.

Innovation #2 - Agro-waste as building material in construction sector: There are no direct techno-economic assessments found for this innovation, but two reviews (Maraveas, 2020; Duque-Acevedo et al., 2022) showed that the technology for this innovation is quite mature and have many studies assessed its economic and social benefits. Some quantitative information on the feedstock is also available for certain types of agro-waste (e.g., EC, 2018c, Avitabile et al., 2023). According to Maraveas (2020), the environmental contributions of using agro-waste material in construction sector tackle two generic issues: the first is the use of alternative biological materials in place of cementitious materials, which contributes to the reduction of GHG during the production process; the other one deals with the challenge of waste disposal, which troubles the agricultural processing industry. The impact categories of land use and climate change are thus affected by this bio-based innovation, although further research would be needed to provide a quantitative estimate of these effects and of the (type and) amount of conventional materials that could be replaced by waste-based alternatives, also taking into account that other bio-based innovations could be produced out of the same agro-waste feedstock.

Innovation #3 - Wood as sustainable material in construction: Wood as construction material has a long history with mature technology, while some new technologies and products for modern wood buildings continue developing (Orfanidou et al., 2023, [New Wave, n.d.](#)). Some LCAs have been done for the scale of a building (e.g., Orfanidou et al., 2023). As for the environmental contributions, the use of sustainably sourced wood in construction contribute to capture and store CO₂ as well as to reduce the emissions associated with the production of conventional construction materials. As such, the innovation mostly impacts positively the climate change category. Quantitative assessments are carried out to measure the CO₂ emissions savings in several European projects related to the use of wood in construction by mostly applying a LCA approach ([Build-in-wood, 2022](#), [Interreg Europe, 2021](#), Primožič, L. (2023), [Bioregions, 2022](#)). In addition, the use of wood allows the production of lightweight and versatile modules which can be used for adding floors on top of existing buildings. Such practice is also instrumental in addressing the issue of consumption of healthy soil, thus positively impacting the “land use/land use change” category of environmental contributions ([Interreg Europe, 2021](#)). There are no direct techno-economic assessments found for this innovation. However, some studies indicated its higher cost and challenges in social acceptance (e.g., regulations, moisture and safety issues) (e.g. Hurmekoski et al, 2018, Pitkänen et al., 2016, Orfanidou et al., 2023), while other studies indicated that economic potential, interests among the stakeholders for such innovation, and the promotion of wood buildings from policies can be expected (e.g. Arkhangelskaya, et al., 2018, Hurmekoski et al, 2018). Asada et al. (2020) revealed a positive impacts of employment effects of EU region if the construction

material will be replaced by wood for certain percentage. The feedstock availability from EU-27 countries can be found in Avitabile et al. (2023): although the wood biomass is still increasing, the increase rate is slowing down due to increased demand for wood products. A further penetration of this innovation in the EU market thus needs to be carefully considered. In Finland, for instance, climate benefits from a further upscaling of this innovation can only be possible if forest harvest levels are kept unvaried by changing forest management practices towards producing more saw logs and less pulpwood (Seppälä et al., 2022). This can be encouraged by policy measures, including subsidies/taxes and legislative measures, although pulpwood demand is high with sizable investments in Finland to new pulp production plants. At wider EU level, an analysis is currently being conducted within the context of the H2020 Build-in-Wood project²⁰ to estimate how much unused wood biomass might be available to the European wood construction sector on a sustainable basis.

Innovation #4 - Natural biopolymers extracted from plant leftovers of the agricultural industry, turn into a novel generation of bio-circular and plastic-free material: This is an innovation from a company that has commercialized the products (Traceless Materials GmbH, 2023). Environmental contributions of such innovations are quantitatively accounted as for the “climate change” by conducting a LCA for providing the product in the market at large scale (Planet A GmbH, 2022) and assessing that their natural polymers save up to 76% of climate emissions from production in industrial plant to the end of life as high-nutrient compost. Also, the company declares that there is no additional land use for producing this bio-based innovation as residues from the agricultural land are used. However, such eventual benefit of land saving should be compared with the consequence of removing organic residues from it, thus affecting the soil quality and fertility. No specific information or assessment on the technology and economic on feasibility, employment effects and its social acceptances for such large-scale production are available from the information on the website. Avitabile et al. (2023) provided the assessment on amount of agricultural residues from EU-27 countries, but the feedstock type from the agricultural industry residues was not specified (Planet A GmbH, 2022). Thus, the accurate feedstock availability is unclear.

Innovation #10 - Developing, cultivating and producing vegan, plant-based and protein-rich Chlorella algae ingredients for food, feed and dietary supplement applications: The innovation is similar to #7 but based on microalgae cultivated in a closed fully controlled fermenters system ([Aliga ApS](#), n.d.). As the cultivation system is fully closed and controlled, the assessment on feedstock availability is not applicable to this innovation. The innovation has developed several algae products from a Danish company and expand to the Netherlands ([Aliga ApS](#), n.d.). Therefore, although there is no direct technical feasibility and techno-economic assessment, it is expected TRL 9 is reachable and has economic benefit. There is no employment assessment available for this innovation. As for the environmental contributions, the company website states that the cultivation of this algae, as it is occurring in manufacturing facilities, is not competing with agriculture for arable land and freshwater, rather providing a sustainable alternative to plant-based crops ([Aliga ApS](#), n.d.). Also, the company indicates that emissions from production processes are as low as <1kg of CO₂ per kg biomass cultivated ([Aliga ApS](#), n.d.). No direct assessment of the social acceptability of this innovation. However, based on their company development and survey for innovation #7, the social acceptability should be positive.

Innovation #12 - Urban biowaste valorised into insect protein/microbial protein for production of food/feed: This is an innovation from a project, VALUEWASTE (n.d.). The project stated the innovation reached TRL 7 within the project implementation and included the information of feedstock potential at the scale of one city (VALUEWASTE, n.d.). Fernández-Gutiérrez et al. (2022) also mentioned that Europe

²⁰ See <https://www.build-in-wood.eu/>

generates 1.18 kg of municipal solid waste per person per day, which includes a wide range of organic fractions usable for this innovation. Also, a social acceptance assessment was conducted, revealing an interest on the innovation from the citizens, and a higher acceptance of new products by those more educated (Eskelinen et al., 2022). As for the environmental contributions, the project deployed a LCA assessment for the environmental impacts, mostly highlighting no land competition for producing feed as well as emission reductions from land use change (see Annex 10). Overall, it proved from an environmental viewpoint that added-value bioproducts from biowaste (i.e., proteins and biofertilizers) are real alternatives to reach the market in the near future (Fernández-Gutiérrez et al., 2022).

Innovation #17 Use wood fibre from agricultural and forestry waste to produce textile fibre: There are at least 3 companies in Finland and 1 company in Sweden that have commercialized this innovation (Orfanidou et al., 2023). Orfanidou et al. (2023) conducted an LCA for this innovation to assess the environmental impacts beyond climate change and indicated the challenges in technology aspects as well as social and market acceptances for further upscaling. Environmental impact categories affected are “land use / land use change”, “ecosystem service provisioning” and “climate change”. Some wood-based fibres come from pulp logs from forest and contribute to lower environmental impacts compared to cotton, viscose and synthetic fibres, thanks to the use of renewable energy during the production process, the use of less chemicals and water, and the lower GHG emissions (Hasegawa et al., 2022, Orfanidou et al., 2023). The feedstock sources are various depending on fibre types and production chain, e.g., from forest residues or from industrial side streams (Orfanidou et al., 2023), thus the feedstock availability can only be checked if the textile fibre type can be specified. But total feedstock from wood and their waste can be found in the description of innovation #3.

Innovation #18 - Feathers (waste from poultry sector) to bioplastic (or other biodegradable products, like forest and seed trays, mulch films, hydroponic foams and nonwoven geotextiles): This is an innovation from an on-going project, the [UNLOCK Project](#), which is expected to end in 2025. The project states that their results will reach TRL 7, and they will assess the economic, social and environmental feasibility by conducting Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for environmental impacts, Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) for social impacts, and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) for economic impact, although the results are not available yet. Environmental contributions fall mostly in the category of ecosystem service provisioning because of using unexploited available biomass from waste stream of poultry sector, i.e. the feathers that can be the feedstock for biodegradable materials. The project description also states that the feedstock (waste feather) from the European poultry sector is 3.6 million tons per year ([UNLOCK Project](#)).

Innovation #19 - Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce processed food (e.g., fish pulp, fish mince, surimi) for human use: The innovation #19-22 are summarised from the same project, [DiscardLess \(n.d.\)](#), that has semi-quantification feasibility assessment on technology feasibility, economic feasibility, market potential that include the consideration of social acceptance and feedstock assessment (Iñarra et al., 2017). Compared to #20-22, this innovation #19 is the one that is most possible to upscale in a short term, in terms of technology maturity, economic feasibility and market potential. The fisheries and aquaculture production chain from EU-27 produces 925,000 tons of dry matter in waste (Avitabile et al., 2023). However, not all species and waste types are suitable for all innovation types. Based on Iñarra et al. (2017), the waste from almost all species is suitable for innovation #19. In addition to the DiscardLess (n.d.) projects, LCA for fish waste was only found for bioproducts production (e.g., omega 3 rich lipids and CaCO₃) but not for the application of innovation #19-22 (Caldeira et al., 2020). From the project description, environmental contributions are also not clearly stated, except for the “biodiversity” category, for which unwanted fish

species need to be properly managed, but their profitability must be subjected to the avoidance of incentivizing by-catches.

Innovation #20 - Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce animal feed (e.g., fish protein concentrates, fish protein hydrolysate, insect meal, fish meal and fish oil, silage): Following innovation #19, the results of feasibility assessment for each animal feed application from the project are different. For example, technology maturity is low for insect meals, while technology maturity is high for other animal feed applications. In terms of challenges for upscaling, the production value for fish meal, fish oil, silage, and insect meal are low. However, for the rest of feasibility assessment criteria for the remaining application, this innovation has advantage for upscaling (DiscardLess, n.d., Iñarra et al., 2017). Based on Iñarra et al. (2017), the suitable species waste for each animal feed application are also various a lot. Environmental contributions are also not clearly stated, except for the “biodiversity” category, for which unwanted fish species need to be properly managed, but their profitability must be subjected to the avoidance of incentivizing by-catches.

Innovation #21 - Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce leather: Following innovation #19, the technology maturity for this innovation is high. However, the feedstock availability is low as only a few discarded species are suitable for this innovation. In addition, the challenges of upscaling this innovation include the middle level of production value, low market potential, and middle level of production cost (DiscardLess, n.d., Iñarra et al., 2017). Environmental contributions are also not clearly stated, except for the “biodiversity” category, for which unwanted fish species need to be properly managed, but their profitability must be subjected to the avoidance of incentivizing by-catches.

Innovation #22 - Discards from fisheries or fish processing to produce fertilizer or biogas: Following innovation #19, the feasibility assessment for this innovation is low in general (DiscardLess, n.d., Iñarra et al., 2017). The only advantage of this innovation to upscale is low production cost for fertilizer production. The feedstock availability is high as almost all discarded species can be used to produce fertilizer or biogas. However, the content in the feedstock makes the process yield low to middle. Technical maturity, value of the products, and market potential are all at low to middle levels for both fertilizer and biogas production. These assessment results, together with the high production cost for biogas make the further upscale of this innovation challenges. Environmental contributions are also not clearly stated, except for the “biodiversity” category, for which unwanted fish species need to be properly managed, but their profitability must be subjected to the avoidance of incentivizing by-catches.

Innovation #23 - Lignin as bio-based packaging materials: Hararak et al. (2022) reviewed that lignin-based packaging materials have reached pilot level (TRL 7) but are not commercialised yet. The review also indicates that inexpensive lignin and the market potential make this innovation has chances to further scale up. Although there is no direct techno-economic assessment on lignin-based packaging materials, many studies did a techno-economic assessment or an LCA for lignin-based products/process/biopolymer that can further apply for producing packaging materials (e.g., Chauhan et al., 2022, Moreira et al., 2023 Daful and Görgens 2017, de Assis et al., 2018). Starting from the sources found in the review framework (Annex 10), the sustainability of lignin-based materials seems to be focused mostly on the material itself and its technical performances when substituting their fossil-based counterparts, rather than on the contributions (positive or negative effects) they bring to the environment (Hararak et al., 2022). However, the important role that lignin-based material can play in the circular economy is recognized by all studies (Hararak et al., 2022; Stark and Matuana, 2021), mostly when feedstock is coming from by-products of agriculture and forestry thus avoiding any additional land use. However, more research is needed to understand the environmental contributions from a quantitative measurement. The feedstock assessment is the same as innovation #1.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Despite ongoing multilateral environmental processes, developed countries have failed to reduce their emissions by 25%–40% below 1990 levels by 2020 as called for by the IPCC, and global greenhouse gas emissions in the decade 2010-2019 have surpassed those of any previous decade, with 2023 set to be the warmest year on record. Acknowledging this reality, the first Global Stock Take (GST) of the Paris Agreement, which was adopted on December 13th, 2023 at COP28 in UAE (UNFCCC, 2023b), has reaffirmed the Paris Agreement’s ambition to keep global temperature rise well below 2 °C, noting that limiting such increase to 1.5 °C would help limit the negative impacts of the climate crisis; the GST has thus called for – among others – a transition away from fossil fuels in energy systems, a tripling of renewable energy capacity, and an acceleration in the reduction of emissions from road transport as well as in zero- and low-emission technologies, noting that “*feasible, effective and low-cost mitigation options are already available in all sectors to keep 1.5 °C within reach [...]*” (UNFCCC, 2023b).

Within this context, this report has identified those key existing bio-based innovations in priority sectors of the EU economy that would stand a higher chance to support the transition called for by the GST (globally) and the EU Green Deal (regionally). First and foremost, our results show that about half of the EEA-32 region’s Ecological Footprint is driven by just 10 out of 65 sectors of the region’s economy, and **that bio-based innovations are most needed** – given the role these sectors have in driving the land use and carbon emissions of the EEA-32 region, **and potentially able to bring about economic benefits** – such as job opportunities, wage changes, and income expansion across interconnected sectors, **in the *Construction, Food and Agriculture, Transportation, Energy/electricity, and Textile* sectors**. Our results also point to the individual countries of the EEA-32 region in which bio-based innovations in the above sectors should be prioritized (e.g., France, Germany, Italy, Spain and Turkey), as activities in these countries drive the multiple footprints of the identified 6 key sectors.

Our analysis of the interdependencies that these 6 sectors of the EEA-32 region’s economy have with other sectors and economies (including outside of the region) indicates that **moving towards the decarbonization ambitions of the EU Green Deal could require prioritizing investments in bio-based innovations across key interconnected sectors, as well as abroad**. Further research, however, is needed to better understand these interconnections and identify all the involved stages of key supply chains (including intermediate steps), and to distinguish (and quantify) the impacts associated with the bio-based sectors of the economy from the impacts of the non-bio-based activities of the classical economy.

Next, our analysis points to 23 key innovations that use by-products, residuals or waste from agricultural, forest, marine, or industrial/municipal waste biomass as feedstock (i.e., bio-based innovations) to bring about innovations in the priority sectors identified above, and highlights the EU countries in which these 23 innovations are nowadays implemented (i.e., primarily Northern European and Scandinavian countries), showing a geographical mismatch between countries in which innovations are needed the most and countries in which innovations are currently being implemented, thus **calling for further investments in Southern European countries, and in north-south knowledge sharing within the EEA-32 region**.

Focusing on individual bio-based innovations, **those using algal biomass are found to be among the most promising innovations**, as algae can be grown in laboratories or taken from the marine environment (thus also contributing to nutrient removal), can have multiple end-uses across a wide range of sectors – including for food-related uses given their high nutritional value – while not competing for land for food production. On the negative side, despite knowledge on the scalability potential of algae-based innovations is higher than most of the other innovations, the trade-offs between the impacts of biorefineries and the potential benefits they bring are still unclear and would need to be further researched. **Innovations using agricultural biomass**

can also have multiple uses across the identified 6 key sectors; however, the potential impact on soil quality (e.g., carbon stock) – and indirectly on biodiversity – of taking out agro-biomass residuals of cultivations from croplands is yet to be fully understood. Among innovation using discarded marine fish biomass as feedstock, promising bio-based innovations could be those producing food for human consumption (e.g., fish pulp, fish mince and surimi) as they have high technological readiness and economic potential, although a clear picture of their environmental contributions is lacking.

Finally, although the feasibility (e.g., from an economic and feedstock availability viewpoint) and climate implications of a full-scale implementation of the identified bio-based innovations are (at least qualitatively) known, **we found that major gaps still exist in our understanding of the biodiversity and employment implications of upsizing and upscaling these 23 innovations,** and of the potential competition among bio-based innovations (e.g., for what concerns competing for the same feedstock), and between these latter and business-as-usual practices. Further research needs to be prioritized to shed light on such competition and ways in which competition for feedstock can be managed and regulated, the market penetration potential of “game-changing” bio-based innovations, and foresee all the environmental implications of upscaling these 23 key innovations, in order to avoid bringing about improvements in the decarbonization of the European economy (via a full-scale implementation of these innovations) at the expenses of unknown potential impacts on land-use and biodiversity.

As the COP28 Global Stock Take (GST) decision (UNFCCC, 2023b) has recognized for the first time the connection between the climate agenda and the Global Biodiversity Framework – emphasizing the importance of conserving, protecting and restoring nature and ecosystems to achieve the Paris Agreement’s targets – findings from this report and the work conducted within the ETC BE Task 1.2.7.1 (Leclère et al., 2023) indicates that **trade-offs likely exist between the short-term strategy to substitute fossil-based with bio-based products to decarbonize the EU economy** (via climate mitigation), **and the long-term negative consequences that biomass extraction could have on biodiversity** (e.g., biodiversity loss) **and climate resilience** (e.g., declining resilience). As a matter of fact, 14 of the 23 shortlisted innovations contribute to the ambition of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy of “*reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, whether sourced domestically or from abroad*”. Although such bio-based innovations use food waste, agriculture residues or forestry by-product as feedstocks to reduce the use of primary natural resources, their full-scale implementation could trigger further biomass extraction, placing increasing threats to biodiversity. Meanwhile, the alternative, longer-term strategy to store carbon in ecosystems (by leaving biomass on the ground or in the standing stock) to favour ecosystem resilience and climate adaptation could somehow limit the actual upscaling of bio-based innovations. Further research on these trade-offs is thus needed to understand the threshold within which substituting business-as-usual practices with bio-based innovations can bring about a net positive impact on decarbonization and biodiversity.

5. REFERENCES

- Abedi, F. (2023). Environmental Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) of Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) Production (A Techno-Environmental Assessment). Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT
- Adams, J. M. M., Morris, S. M., Steege, L., Robinson, J., & Bavington, C. (2021). Food-Grade Biorefinery Processing of Macroalgae at Scale: Considerations, Observations and Recommendations. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 9(10), 1082.
- Aguiar, A., Chepeliev, M., Corong, E., McDougall, R., & van der Mensbrugghe, D. (2019). The GTAP Data Base: Version 10. *Journal of Global Economic Analysis*, 4(1), 1-27. Retrieved from <https://www.jgea.org/ojs/index.php/jgea/article/view/77>
- Aguilar, A., Cole, J., Euston, S., Gardossi, L., O'Hara, I., Patermann, C., & Twardowski, T. (2021). The bioeconomy will contribute to addressing the challenges of climate change. *EFB Bioeconomy Journal*, 1, 100021-100022.
- Aliga ApS (n.d). Aliga microalgae. Retrieved from: <https://www.aliga.dk/production>
- Andrew, R. M. and Peters, G.P. (2013). A multi-region input–output table based on the global trade analysis project database (GTAP-MRIO). *Economic Systems Research*, 25, 99–121.
- Arkhangelskaya, Y. (2018). Economic assessment of a wood building: Life Cycle Cost and Stakeholders' Decision-Making. Aalto University.
- APRE and CDTI (2022). Guiding notes to use the TRL self-assessment tool. BRIDGE2HE H2020-101005071. Retrieved from: <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-12/trl-assessment-tool-guide-final.pdf>
- Asada, R., Cardellini, G., Mair-Bauernfeind, C., Wenger, J., Haas, V., Holzer, D., & Stern, T. (2020). Effective bioeconomy? a MRIO-based socioeconomic and environmental impact assessment of generic sectoral innovations. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 153, 119946.
- Avitabile V, Baldoni E, Baruth B, Bausano G, Boysen-Urban K, Caldeira C, Camia A, Cazzaniga N, Ceccherini G, De Laurentiis V, Doerner H, Giuntoli J, Gras M, Guillen Garcia J, Gurria P, Hassegawa M, Jasinevičius G, Jonsson R, Konrad C, Kupschus S, La Notte A, M'barek R, Mannini A, Migliavacca M, Mubareka S, Patani S, C Pilli R, Rebours C, Ronchetti G, Ronzon T, Rougieux P, Sala S, Sánchez López J, Sanye Mengual E, Sinkko T, Sturm V, Van Leeuwen M, Vasilakopoulos P, Verkerk PJ, Virtanen J, Winker H, Zulian G (2023). Biomass production, supply, uses and flows in the European Union. Integrated assessment. Mubareka S, Migliavacca M, Sánchez López J (Editors). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, doi:10.2760/811744, JRC132358
- Bandarian, R. (2007). Measuring commercial potential of a new technology at the early stage of development with fuzzy logic. *Journal of Technology Management & Innovation*, 2(4), 73-85.
- Barnosky, A. D., Hadly, E. A., Bascompte, J., Berlow, E. L., Brown, J. H., Fortelius, M., ... & Smith, A. B. (2012). Approaching a state shift in Earth's biosphere. *Nature*, 486(7401), 52-58.
- Battista, F., Frison, N., Pavan, P., Cavinato, C., Gottardo, M., Fatone, F., ... & Bolzonella, D. (2020). Food wastes and sewage sludge as feedstock for an urban biorefinery producing biofuels and added-value bioproducts. *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology*, 95(2), 328-338.
- Baudouin, D., Wörner, M., Yeadon, D., Hornung, U. & Joronen T. (2020). D1.1 - Report on the Feedstock Characterization. Black Liquor to Fuel by Efficient HydroThermal Application integrated to Pulp Mill (BL2F). Retrieved from: https://www.bl2f.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Attachment_0-2.pdf

- Beckham, Gregg T., Benavides, Thathiana, Heyne, Joshua, & Roman, Yuriy (2023). 2.3.4.104 - Lignin Conversion to Sustainable Aviation Fuel Blendstocks. United States. Retrieved from: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1971863>
- Ben Youssef, A., Zeqiri, A. (2022). Hospitality Industry 4.0 and Climate Change. *Circ.Econ.Sust.* 2, 1043–1063. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-021-00141-x>
- Bezama, A., Hildebrandt, J., & Thrän, D. (2022). Analyzing the Potential Environmental and Socio-Economic Impacts of Regional Energy Integration Scenarios of a Bio-Based Industrial Network. *Sustainability*, 14(23), 15886.
- Bioregions (2022) Key challenges and innovation opportunities for Wood Construction. Retrieved from: <https://bioregions.efi.int/key-challenges-and-innovation-opportunities-for-wood-construction/>
- Bjørn, A., Kalbar, P., Nygaard, S. E., Kabins, S., Jensen, C. L., Birkved, M., ... & Hauschild, M. Z. (2018). Pursuing necessary reductions in embedded GHG emissions of developed nations: will efficiency improvements and changes in consumption get us there?. *Global Environmental Change*, 52, 314-324.
- BL2F (2020). PROJECT PIPELINE. Retrieved from: <https://www.bl2f.eu/project-pipeline/>
- Borucke, M., Moore, D., Cranston, G., Gracey, K., Iha, K., Larson, J., ... & Galli, A. (2013). Accounting for demand and supply of the biosphere's regenerative capacity: The National Footprint Accounts' underlying methodology and framework. *Ecological indicators*, 24, 518-533.
- Bröring, S., Laibach, N., & Wustmans, M. (2020). Innovation types in the bioeconomy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 266, 121939.
- Build-in-wood (2022). Sustainable Wood Value Chains for Construction of Low-carbon Multi-storey Buildings from Renewable Resources. Retrieved from: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862820>
- Butchart, S. H., Walpole, M., Collen, B., Van Strien, A., Scharlemann, J. P., Almond, R. E., ... & Watson, R. (2010). Global biodiversity: indicators of recent declines. *Science*, 328(5982), 1164-1168.
- Caldeira, C., Vlysidis, A., Fiore, G., De Laurentiis, V., Vignali, G., & Sala, S. (2020). Sustainability of food waste biorefinery: A review on valorisation pathways, techno-economic constraints, and environmental assessment. *Bioresource Technology*, 312, 123575.
- Camelia, Surugiu & Remus, Hornoiu & Surugiu, Marius-Razvan. (2020). The analysis of CO2 emissions determinants in accommodation and food service activities using quantile regressions. *Romanian Statistical Review* 3/2020
- Cavelius, P., Engelhart-Straub, S., Mehlmer, N., Lercher, J., Awad, D., & Brück, T. (2023). The potential of biofuels from first to fourth generation. *PLoS biology*, 21(3), e3002063.
- Chauhan, Prakram & Agrawal, Ruchi & Satlewal, Alok & Kumar, Ravindra & Gupta, Ravi & Ramakumar, S.S.V. (2022). Next generation applications of lignin derived commodity products and their life cycle, techno-economical and societal analysis. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 197, 179-200. [10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2021.12.146](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2021.12.146).
- Chong, Ting & Cheah, Siang Aun & Tye, Ong & Wong, Lee & Goh, Chern & Tan, Inn shi & Foo, Henry & Lam, Man & Lim, Steven. (2020). Techno-economic evaluation of third-generation bioethanol production utilizing the macroalgae waste: A case study in Malaysia. *Energy*, 210, 118491. [10.1016/j.energy.2020.118491](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118491).
- Circular Bio-based Europe (2022). Industrial polymers now sustainably made from lignin. Retrieved from: <https://www.cbe.europa.eu/achievements/industrial-polymers-now-sustainably-made-lignin>

- Corona, Blanca & Hoefnagels, Ric & Vural Gürsel, Iris & Moretti, Christian & Veen, M. & Junginger, M.. (2022). Metrics for minimising environmental impacts while maximising circularity in biobased products: The case of lignin-based asphalt. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379, 134829. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134829.
- Council of the European Union (2023). Council conclusions on Climate and Energy Diplomacy “Bolstering EU climate and energy diplomacy in a critical decade”. 7248/23. Brussels, 9 March 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/62942/st07248-en23.pdf>
- Crutchik, D., Franchi, O., Caminos, L., Jeison, D., Belmonte, M., Pedrouso, A., Val del Rio, A., et al. (2020). Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) Production: A Feasible Economic Option for the Treatment of Sewage Sludge in Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plants? *Water*, 12(4), 1118. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/w12041118>
- Daful, A. G., & Görgens, J. F. (2017). Techno-economic analysis and environmental impact assessment of lignocellulosic lactic acid production. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 162, 53-65.
- Daly, H.E. (1990). Toward some operational principles of sustainable development. *Ecol. Econ.*, 1990(2), 1–6.
- Davis, K. F., Gephart, J. A., Emery, K. A., Leach, A. M., Galloway, J. N., & D’Odorico, P. (2016). Meeting future food demand with current agricultural resources. *Global Environmental Change*, 39, 125-132.
- de Assis, C. A., Greca, L. G., Ago, M., Balakshin, M. Y., Jameel, H., Gonzalez, R., & Rojas, O. J. (2018). Techno-economic assessment, scalability, and applications of aerosol lignin micro-and nanoparticles. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* 6, 2018, 11853–11868.
- DiscardLess (n.d.). Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries. Valorisation module. Available at: http://www.discardless.eu/www.discardless.eu/valorisation_module.html
- Díaz, S. M., Settele, J., Brondízio, E., Ngo, H., Guèze, M., Agard, J., ... & Zayas, C. (2019). The global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services: Summary for policy makers. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3553579>
- Duque-Acevedo, M., Lancellotti, I., Andreola, F. et al. (2022). Management of agricultural waste biomass as raw material for the construction sector: an analysis of sustainable and circular alternatives. *Environ Sci Eur*, 34, 70.
- EEA (European Environment Agency) (2018). The circular economy and the bioeconomy Partners in sustainability. EEA report n°8/2018. Retrieved from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/circular-economy-and-bioeconomy>
- EEA (European Environment Agency) (2020). SOER 2020. Retrieved from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2020/at-a-glance>
- EEA (European Environment Agency) (2023). Exiting the Anthropocene? Exploring fundamental change in our relationship with nature. Retrieved from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/exiting-the-anthropocene>
- EHL CATHOL (2020). EHL CATHOL: Committed to a carbon neutrality of the EU in 2050. Retrieved from: <http://ehl cathol.eu/project/#>
- Eskelinen, T., Sydd, O., Kajanus, M., Fernández Gutiérrez, D., Mitsou, M., Soriano Disla, J. M., Sevilla, M. V., et al. (2022). Fortifying Social Acceptance When Designing Circular Economy Business Models on Biowaste Related Products. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 14983.

European Commission (2018c) A sustainable Bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment. Publications Office of the European Union, Brussels, Belgium, Updated Bioeconomy Strategy

European Commission (EC) (2012). Innovating for sustainable growth: a bioeconomy for Europe (COM/2012/060 final). Communication. February 2012. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52012DC0060>.

European Commission (EC) (2018a). European Commission. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. A sustainable Bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment (COM(2018) 673 final). 2018. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018DC0673>.

European Commission (EC)(2018b). Bioeconomy: the European way to use our natural resources. Action plan.

European Commission (EC) (2019). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - the European Green Deal. COM/2019/640 final. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>

European Commission (2020). Energy efficiency in buildings. European Commission – Department: Energy – In focus. Retrieved from: https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-03/in_focus_energy_efficiency_in_buildings_en.pdf

European Commission (EC)(2021). EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System dashboards. Retrieved from: https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/visualisation/eu-bioeconomy-monitoring-system-dashboards_en

European Commission (EC)(2022a). EU Bioeconomy Progress strategy report. European Bioeconomic policy: stocktaking and future developments. DG for research and Innovation. May 2022. Retrieved from: https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/report-com2022283-eu-bioeconomy-strategy-progress-report-european-bioeconomy-policy_en

European Commission (EC)(2022b). Communication. EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics. DG ENV 30 November 2022. Retrieved from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/communication-eu-policy-framework-biobased-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en

European Commission (EC), Joint Research Centre (JRC), Giuntoli, J., Robert, N., Ronzon, T., Sanchez Lopez, J., Follador, M., Girardi, I., Barredo Cano, J., Borzacchiello, M.T., Sala, S., M'Barek, R., La Notte, A., Becker, W., Mubareka, S. (2020). *Building a monitoring system for the EU bioeconomy: progress report 2019. Description of framework*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/717782>

European Environment Agency (EEA), 2023. Exiting the Anthropocene? Exploring fundamental change in our relationship with nature. Available online at: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/exiting-the-anthropocene>

Eurostat (2023). Electric vehicles and power demand for transport up. Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20230324-1>.

- Fernández-Gutiérrez, D., Argüelles, A., Castejón Martínez, G., Soriano Disla, J. M., & Lara-Guillén, A. J. (2022). Unlocking New Value from Urban Biowaste: LCA of the VALUEWASTE Biobased Products. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 14962.
- Ferreira, V., Pié, L., & Terceño, A. (2021). Economic impact of the bioeconomy in Spain: Multiplier effects with a bio social accounting matrix. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 298, 126752.
- Footprint Data Foundation, York University Ecological Footprint Initiative, and Global Footprint Network (2023). National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts, 2023 edition.
- Fritsche, U., Brunori, G., Chiaramonti, D., Galanakis, C., Matthews, R., & Panoutsou, C. (2021). Future transitions for the Bioeconomy towards Sustainable Development and a Climate-Neutral Economy-Foresight Scenarios for the EU bioeconomy in 2050. In Borzacchiello, M.T., Stoermer, E. and Avraamides, M. editor(s), Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2021, ISBN 978-92-76-28414-7, doi:10.2760/469550, JRC123532.
- Galanakis, C. M., Brunori, G., Chiaramonti, D., Matthews, R., Panoutsou, C., & Fritsche, U. R. (2022). Bioeconomy and green recovery in a post-COVID-19 era. *Science of The Total Environment*, 808, 152180.
- Galli A., et al. (2023), EU-27 Ecological Footprint was primarily driven by food consumption and exceeded regional biocapacity from 2004 to 2014. *Nature Food* 4, 810–822 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-023-00843-5>
- Galli, A., (2015). On the rationale and policy usefulness of ecological footprint accounting: the case of Morocco. *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 48, 210–224.
- Galli, A., Iha, K., Halle, M., El Bilali, H., Grunewald, N., Eaton, D., ... & Bottalico, F. (2017). Mediterranean countries' food consumption and sourcing patterns: an ecological footprint viewpoint. *Science of the Total Environment*, 578, 383-391.
- Galli, A., Kitzes, J., Wermer, P., Wackernagel, M., Niccolucci, V., & Tiezzi, E. (2007). *An exploration of the mathematics behind the ecological footprint* (pp. 249-256). Wit Press: Billerica, MA, USA.
- Gaudenzi, Elena & Cardone, Fabrizio & Lu, Xiaohu & Canestrari, Francesco. (2023). The use of lignin for sustainable asphalt pavements: A literature review. *Construction and Building Materials*, 362, 129773. 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.129773.
- Gosselink (2022). Clean aviation fuel from waste wood and tomato stems. Retrieved from: <https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/research-institutes/food-biobased-research/show-fbr/clean-aviation-fuel-from-waste-wood-and-tomato-stems.htm>
- Guidehouse Inc (2019). Gas for Climate: Job creation by scaling up renewable gas in Europe. Reference No.: 203997
- Gutschmann, B., Huang, B., Santolin, L., Thiele, I., Neubauer, P., & Riedel, S. L. (2022). Native feedstock options for the polyhydroxyalkanoate industry in Europe: A review. *Microbiological research*, 264, 127177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2022.127177>
- Haaksman, I., Slaghek, T., Gürsel, I. V., Gosselink, R., ... & Verschuren M. (2022). Collaboration in asphalt Applications with Lignin in the Netherlands - (CHAPLIN TKI). Public report. Retrieved from: <https://www.wur.nl/en/project/tki-project-chaplin-collaboration-in-asphalt-applications-with-lignin-1.htm>

- Hararak, B., Winotapun, C., Wanmolee, W., Leelaphiwat, P., Boonruang, K., Chinsirikul, W., & Chonhenchob, V. (2022). Emerging challenges on viability and commercialization of lignin in biobased polymers for food packaging: A review. *Food Packaging and Shelf Life*, 34, 100969.
- Hasegawa, M., Karlberg, A., Hertzberg, M., & Verkerk, P. J. (2022). Innovative forest products in the circular bioeconomy. *Open Research Europe*, 2(19), 19.
- Hildebrandt, J., Hagemann, N., & Thrän, D. (2017). The contribution of wood-based construction materials for leveraging a low carbon building sector in Europe. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 34, 405-418.
- Hurmekoski, Elias & Pykäläinen, Jouni & Hetemäki, Lauri. (2017). Long-term targets for green building: Explorative Delphi backcasting study on wood-frame multi-story construction in Finland. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 3644-3654. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.08.031.
- Iñarra, B., Bald, C., Cebrian, M. (2017). DiscardLess WP6.2 Evaluation of the different valorisation alternatives prioritized from the technical, market, regulatory and socio-economic perspective. <http://www.discardless.eu/www.discardless.eu/index.html>
- Interreg Europe (2021), Wood as a sustainable construction material. Retrieved from: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/find-policy-solutions/stories/wood-as-a-sustainable-construction-material>
- IPCC (2006). Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Volume 4: Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA
- Iqbal, D. M., Wong, L. S., & Kong, S. Y. (2021). Bio-Cementation in Construction Materials: A Review. *Materials*, 14(9), 2175.
- Jaiyeola, A., Audi, I. & Legay, M. (2023). Replicability Study WP6 - Task 6.4. Black Liquor to Fuel by Efficient HydroThermal Application integrated to Pulp Mill (BL2F). Retrieved from: <https://www.bl2f.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/D6.4-BL2F-Replicability-Analysis-Draft.pdf>
- Karvonen, J., Halder, P., Kangas, J., & Leskinen, P. (2017). Indicators and tools for assessing sustainability impacts of the forest bioeconomy. *Forest ecosystems*, 4(1), 1-20.
- Kennedy, H.T. (2021). Lignin leads the way – World’s first lignin bio-asphalt road, lignin’s array of applications and more. Retrieved from: <https://www.biofuelsdigest.com/bdigest/2021/06/06/lignin-leads-the-way-worlds-first-lignin-bio-asphalt-road-lignins-array-of-applications-and-more/>
- Kim, Hee-Cheol. (2015). Acceptability Engineering: the Study of user Acceptance of Innovative Technologies. *Journal of Applied Research and Technology*, 13(2), 230-237.
- Kinzig, A. P., Ehrlich, P. R., Alston, L. J., Arrow, K., Barrett, S., Buchman, T. G., ... & Saari, D. (2013). Social norms and global environmental challenges: the complex interaction of behaviors, values, and policy. *BioScience*, 63(3), 164-175.
- Kitzes, J. (2013). An introduction to environmentally-extended input-output analysis. *Resources*, 2(4), 489-503.
- Kitzes, J., Peller, A., Goldfinger, S., & Wackernagel, M. (2007). Current methods for calculating national ecological footprint accounts. *Science for environment & sustainable society*, 4(1), 1-9.

- Kotta, J., Raudsepp, U., Szava-Kovats, R., Aps, R., Armoskaite, A., Barda, I., Bergström, P., Futter, M., Gröndahl, F., Hargrave, M., Jakubowska, M., Jänes, H., Kaasik, A., Kraufvelin, P., Kovaltchouk, N., Krost, P., Kulikowski, T., Kõivupuu, A., Kotta, I., Lees, L., ... Barboza, F. R. (2022). Assessing the potential for sea-based macroalgae cultivation and its application for nutrient removal in the Baltic Sea. *The Science of the total environment*, 839, 156230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156230>
- Kulikowski, T., Jakubowska, M., Krupska, J., Psuty, I., & Szulecka, O. (2021). Guide to macroalgae cultivation and use in the Baltic Sea Region. National Marine Fisheries Research Institute: Gdynia.
- Labaran, Y. H., Mathur, V., Muhammad, S. & Musa, A. (2022). Carbon footprint management: A review of construction industry. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, 9, 100531.
- Lasarte-Lopez, J., Ronzon, T., Van Leeuwen, M., Rossi Cervi, W. and M'barek, R. (2022). Estimating employment and value added in the bioeconomy of EU regions, EUR 31058 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76- 52269-0, doi:10.2760/850726, JRC128984.
- Lähtenmäki-Uutela, Anu & Rahikainen, Moona & Camarena Gomez, Teresa & Piiparinen, Jonna & Spilling, Kristian & Yang, Baoru. (2021). European Union legislation on macroalgae products. *Aquaculture International*, 29, 487-509. 10.1007/s10499-020-00633-x.
- Lakner, Z., Oláh, J., Popp, J., & Balázs, E. (2021). The structural change of the economy in the context of the bioeconomy. *EFB Bioeconomy Journal*, 1, 100018.
- Leclère, D., Araujo-Gutierrez, Z.M.F, Galli, A., Vormeier, P., Kupilas, B., Forsell, N., Di Fuvlvio, F., Visconti, P., Hofhansl, F., Mancini, M.S., Deppermann, A., Havlik, P., 2023. Nature-based solutions for Europe's sustainable future - The EU protection and restoration ambition in relation to other EU policy objectives: opportunities and tradeoffs. Final report of task 1.2.7.1 from the 2023 action plan of the European Topic Centre for Biodiversity and Ecosystems (internal report).
- Lehikoinen, M., Nieminen, E., Leinonen, E., Von Zwegbergk, A., Monni, S. (2023). Municipal Emissions From Tourism – Final Report for the Pilot Calculation. REPORT 05/2023. Sitowise OY.
- Leontief, W., 1970. Environmental Repercussions and the Economic Structure: An Input-Output Approach. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, Vol. 52, No. 3 (Aug., 1970), pp. 262-271
- Lin, D., Hanscom, L., Murthy, A., Galli, A., Evans, M., Neill, E., ... & Wackernagel, M. (2018). Ecological footprint accounting for countries: updates and results of the National Footprint Accounts, 2012–2018. *Resources*, 7(3), 58.
- Liu, P.R., and Raftery, A.E. (2021). Country-based rate of emissions reductions should increase by 80% beyond nationally determined contributions to meet the 2 °C target. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 2, 29.
- Llano, T., Arce, C., Gallart, L. E., Perales, A., & Coz, A. (2023). Techno-Economic Analysis of Macroalgae Biorefineries: A Comparison between Ethanol and Butanol Facilities. *Fermentation*, 9(4), 340.
- Loizou, E., Jurga, P., Rozakis, S., & Faber, A. (2019). Assessing the Potentials of Bioeconomy Sectors in Poland Employing Input-Output Modeling. *Sustainability*, 11(3), 594. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su11030594>
- Mancini, M. S., Galli, A., Coscieme, L., Niccolucci, V., Lin, D., Pulselli, F. M., ... & Marchettini, N. (2018). Exploring ecosystem services assessment through Ecological Footprint accounting. *Ecosystem Services*, 30, 228-235.

- Mancini, M. S., Galli, A., Niccolucci, V., Lin, D., Bastianoni, S., Wackernagel, M., & Marchettini, N. (2016). Ecological footprint: refining the carbon footprint calculation. *Ecological indicators*, *61*, 390-403.
- Maraveas, C. (2020). Production of Sustainable Construction Materials Using Agro-Wastes. *Materials*, *13*(2), 262.
- McNerney, J. & Savoie, C. & Caravelli, F. & Carvalho, W. M. & Farmer, J. D., (2021). How production networks amplify economic growth. *PANS*, *119*(1), e2106031118.
- Miller, R., & Blair, P. (2009). *Input-Output Analysis: Foundations and Extensions* (2nd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511626982
- Moreira, W. M., Moreira, P. V. V., Dos Santos, D. F., Gimenes, M. L., & Vieira, M. G. A. (2023). Nanogreen is the new future: the conversion of lignin and lignocellulosic wastes into nanomaterials. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, *30*(8), 19564-19591.
- Moretti, Christian & Hoefnagels, Ric & Veen, Marco & Corona, Blanca & Obydenkova, Svetlana & Russell, Scott & Jongerius, Anna & Vural Gürsel, Iris & Junginger, Martin. (2022). Using lignin from local biorefineries for asphalts: LCA case study for the Netherlands. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *343*, 131063. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131063.
- Moretto, G., Russo, I., Bolzonella, D., Pavan, P., Majone, M., & Valentino, F. (2020). An urban biorefinery for food waste and biological sludge conversion into polyhydroxyalkanoates and biogas. *Water Research*, *170*, 115371.
- Moshood, Taofeeq & Nawanir, Gusman & Mahmud, Fatimah. (2021). Microalgae biofuels production: A systematic review on socioeconomic prospects of microalgae biofuels and policy implications. *Environmental Challenges*, *5*, 100207. 10.1016/j.envc.2021.100207.
- Mosquera-Losada, María Rosa & Santiago-Freijanes, José & Rois, Mercedes & Moreno, Gerardo & Herder, Michael & Vazquez, Jose Antonio & Ferreiro-Domínguez, Nuria & Pantera, Anastasia & Pisanelli, Andrea & Rigueiro-Rodríguez, Antonio. (2018). Agroforestry in Europe: a land management policy tool to combat climate change. *Land Use Policy*, *78*, 603-613
- Muñoz, P., & Steininger, K. W. (2010). Austria's CO2 responsibility and the carbon content of its international trade. *Ecological Economics*, *69*(10), 2003-2019.
- New Wave (n.d). About the project. Retrieved from: <https://www.newwave-horizon.eu/about/>
- NOSHAN (2016). Sustainable Production of Functional and Safe Feed from Food Waste. Retrieved from: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/312140>
- O'Neill, D. W., Fanning, A. L., Lamb, W. F., & Steinberger, J. K. (2018). A good life for all within planetary boundaries. *Nature sustainability*, *1*(2), 88-95.
- Oberti, I., & Paciello, A. (2022). Bioplastic as a Substitute for Plastic in Construction Industry. *Encyclopedia*, *2*(3), 1408–1420.
- OECD/Eurostat (2018), Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation, 4th Edition, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris/Eurostat, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304604-en>

- Orfanidou, T., Hassegawa, M., Leskinen, P., Sixta, H., Oinas, P., Cardellini, G. (2023). Wood-based textiles & modern wood buildings. Knowledge to Action 6, European Forest Institute. <https://doi.org/10.36333/k2a06>
- Pantera, A., Mosquera-Losada, M. R., Herzog, F., & Den Herder, M. (2021). Agroforestry and the environment. *Agroforestry Systems*, 95(5), 767-774.
- Parisi, C., Baldoni, E., M'barek, R.(2020): Bio-based industry and biorefineries. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/ee438b10-7723-4435-9f5e-806ab63faf37>
- Philippidis, G., Sanjuán López, A. I., Ferrari, E., & M'barek, R. (2014). Employing social accounting matrix multipliers to profile the bioeconomy in the EU member states: is there a structural pattern? *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, 12(4), 913-926.
- Pitkänen, K., Antikainen, R., Droste, N., Loiseau, E., Saikku, L., Aissani, L., Hansjürgens, B., Kuikman, P. J., Leskinen, P., & Thomsen, M. (2016). What can be learned from practical cases of green economy? –studies from five European countries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 139, 666-676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.08.071>
- Planet A GmbH (2022). Life Cycle Assessment: Traceless. Retrieved from: <https://planet-a.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/traceless-lca-summary-published-1.pdf>
- Primožič, L. (2023). Dr. Dean Lipovac at the web conference on the launch of the handbook – Wood, the material of present and future. Retrieved from: <https://innorenew.eu/2023/11/dr-dean-lipovac-web-conference-launch-handbook-wood-material-present-future/>
- Puschnigg, Stefan & Fazeni-Fraisl, Karin & Lindorfer, Johannes & Kienberger, Thomas. (2022). Biorefinery development for the conversion of softwood residues into sustainable aviation fuel: Implications from life cycle assessment and energetic-exergetic analyses. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 386, 135815. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135815.
- Rajendran, N., & Han, J. (2022). Techno-economic analysis of food waste valorization for integrated production of polyhydroxyalkanoates and biofuels. *Bioresource technology*, 348, 126796. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.126796>
- RD12CLUB (2020). 25 cases for bioeconomy innovation around the Baltic Sea region. Retrieved from: <https://www.jamk.fi/sites/default/files/2022-01/25casesforbioeconomy-eng-26082020-web.pdf>
- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., ... & Rockström, J. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458.
- Riondet, L., Rio, M., Perrot-Bernardet, V., & Zwolinski, P. (2022). For an upscaling assessment integration in product design. *Procedia CIRP*, 109, 89-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2022.05.219>
- Robert, N., Giuntoli, J., Araujo, R., Avraamides, M., Balzi, E., Barredo, J. I., ... & Mubareka, S. (2020). Development of a bioeconomy monitoring framework for the European Union: An integrative and collaborative approach. *New Biotechnology*, 59, 10-19.
- Rogelj, J., Den Elzen, M., Höhne, N., Fransen, T., Fekete, H., Winkler, H., ... & Meinshausen, M. (2016). Paris Agreement climate proposals need a boost to keep warming well below 2 C. *Nature*, 534(7609), 631-639.
- Ronzon, T., Piotrowski, S., Tamosiunas, S., Dammer, L., Carus, M., & M'barek, R. (2020). Developments of economic growth and employment in bioeconomy sectors across the EU. *Sustainability*, 12(11), 4507.

- Saral, J.S., Satheesh, A.R., & Ranganathan, P. (2022). Economic and environmental analysis of algal biorefinery for the production of renewable fuels and co-product. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 14, 100189.
- Seghetta, M., Romeo, D., D'Este, M., Alvarado-Morales, M., Angelidaki, I., Bastianoni, S., & Thomsen, M. (2017). Seaweed as innovative feedstock for energy and feed—Evaluating the impacts through a Life Cycle Assessment. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 150, 1-15.
- Seghetta, M., Tørring, D., Bruhn, A., & Thomsen, M. (2016). Bioextraction potential of seaweed in Denmark - An instrument for circular nutrient management. *The Science of the total environment*, 563-564, 513–529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.04.010>
- Seghetta, Michele & Hou, Xiaoru & Bastianoni, Simone & Bjerre, Anne & Thomsen, Marianne. (2016b). Life cycle assessment of macroalgal biorefinery for the production of ethanol, proteins and fertilizers – A step towards a regenerative bioeconomy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 137, 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.07.195.
- Seppälä, J., Heinonen, T., Kilpeläinen, A., Peltola, H., Pukkala, T., Sihvonen, M., Soimakallio, S., Weaver, S., Vesala, T., Ollikainen, M. 2022. Metsät ja ilmasto: Hakkuut, hiilinielut ja puun käytön korvaushyödyt. Suomen ilmastopaneelin raportti 3/2022. [In Finnish, English abstract]. Available at <https://www.ilmastopaneeli.fi/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/ilmastopaneelin-raportti-3-2022-metsat-ja-ilmasto-hakkuut-hiilinielut-ja-puun-kayton-korvaushyodyt.pdf>
- Sharmila, V. G., M, D. K., Pugazhendi, A., Bajhaiya, A. K., Gugulothu, P., & J, R. B. (2021). Biofuel production from Macroalgae: present scenario and future scope. *Bioengineered*, 12(2), 9216–9238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21655979.2021.1996019>
- Shen, R., Tao, L. and Yang, B. (2019), Techno-economic analysis of jet-fuel production from biorefinery waste lignin. *Biofuels, Bioprod. Bioref.*, 13, 486-501. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1952>
- Sinkko, T., Sanyé-Mengual, E., Corrado, S., Giuntoli, J., & Sala, S. (2023). The EU Bioeconomy Footprint: Using life cycle assessment to monitor environmental impacts of the EU Bioeconomy. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 37, 169-179.
- Stark, N. M., & Matuana, L. M. (2021). Trends in sustainable biobased packaging materials: A mini review. *Materials Today Sustainability*, 15, 100084.
- Stark, S., Biber-Freudenberger, L., Dietz, T., et al., 2022. Sustainability implications of transformation pathways for the bioeconomy. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 29, 215-227 (DOI: 10.1016/j.spc.2021.10.011)
- Steffen, W., Richardson, K., Rockström, J., Cornell, S. E., Fetzer, I., Bennett, E. M., ... & Sörlin, S. (2015). Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*, 347(6223), 1259855.
- Steffen, W., Rockström, J., Richardson, K., Lenton, T. M., Folke, C., Liverman, D., ... & Schellnhuber, H. J. (2018). Trajectories of the Earth System in the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(33), 8252-8259.
- Swedish Environmental Research Institute (2021). Lack of alternatives to fossil-based plastics in the construction sector. Retrieved from: <https://www.ivl.se/english/ivl/press/news/2021-03-19-lack-of-alternatives-to-fossil-based-plastics-in-the-construction-sector.html> (30/06/2023)
- Tan, E. C., & Lamers, P. (2021). Circular bioeconomy concepts—a perspective. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 2, 701509.

Thomassen, G., Van Dael, M., Lemmens, B., & Van Passel, S. (2017). A review of the sustainability of algal-based biorefineries: Towards an integrated assessment framework. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 68, 876-887.

Tittensor, D. P., Walpole, M., Hill, S. L., Boyce, D. G., Britten, G. L., Burgess, N. D., ... & Ye, Y. (2014). A mid-term analysis of progress toward international biodiversity targets. *Science*, 346(6206), 241-244.

Traceless Materials GmbH (2023). Traceless. Retrieved from: <https://www.traceless.eu/about-us>

TWI2050 - The World in 2050 (2020). Innovations for Sustainability. Pathways to an efficient and post-pandemic future. Report prepared by The World in 2050 initiative. International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Laxenburg, Austria. Retrieved from: <http://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/16533>

UNECE and FAO, 2000. Temperate and Boreal Forest Resource Assessment. UNECE, FAO, Geneva.

United Nations Environment Programme, (2009). Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products. UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative at UNEP, CIRAI, FAQDD and the Belgium Federal Public Planning Service Sustainable Development. Retrieved from: <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2009%20-%20Guidelines%20for%20sLCA%20-%20EN.pdf>

United Nations Environment Programme (2022). 2022 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction: Towards a Zeroemission, Efficient and Resilient Buildings and Construction Sector. Nairobi.

UN Environment Programme (2021). A Manual to Measuring and Monitoring Resource Efficiency and Greenhouse Gas Emissions in the Hotel and Conference Sector. Paris.

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), 2023a. Technical dialogue of the first global stocktake. Synthesis report by the co-facilitators on the technical dialogue. Retrieved from: <https://unfccc.int/documents/631600>

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), 2023b. First global stocktake - Proposal by the President. Draft decision FCCC/PA/CMA/2023/L.17. Available at: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/cma2023_L17_adv.pdf

UNLOCL (n.d). About the project. Retrieved from: <https://unlock-project.eu/about-the-project/>

VALUEWASTE (n.d.). Project Description. Retrieved from: <https://valuewaste.eu/work-plan/>

van der Meer, T. V., Davey, C. J. E., Verdonshot, P. F. M., & Kraak, M. H. S. (2023). Removal of nutrients from WWTP effluent by an algae-mussel trophic cascade. *Ecological Engineering*, 190, Article 106930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2023.106930>

Wackernagel, M. & Rees, W.E. (1996). *Our Ecological Footprint: Reducing Human Impact on the Earth*, New Society Publishers: Gabriola Island, British Columbia, Canada.

Wackernagel, M., Onisto, L., Bello, P., Linares, A. C., Falfán, I. S. L., García, J. M., ... & Guerrero, M. G. S. (1999). National natural capital accounting with the ecological footprint concept. *Ecological economics*, 29(3), 375-390.

Weinzettel, J., Steen-Olsen, K., Hertwich, E. G., Borucke, M., & Galli, A. (2014). Ecological footprint of nations: Comparison of process analysis, and standard and hybrid multiregional input–output analysis. *Ecological Economics*, 101, 115-126.

- Wellenreuther, Claudia & Wolf, André (2020). Innovative feedstocks in biodegradable bio-based plastics: A literature review, HWWI Research Paper, No. 194, Hamburgisches WeltWirtschaftsInstitut (HWWI), Hamburg
- Wiatrowski, M., Klein, B.C., Davis, R.W. et al. (2022). Techno-economic assessment for the production of algal fuels and value-added products: opportunities for high-protein microalgae conversion. *Biotechnol Biofuels* 15, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-021-02098-3>
- Wiedmann, T., Minx, J., Barrett, J., & Wackernagel, M. (2006). Allocating ecological footprints to final consumption categories with input–output analysis. *Ecological economics*, 56(1), 28-48. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.05.012>.
- Wigboldus, S. and Leeuwis C. (2013). Towards responsible scaling up and out in agricultural development: An exploration of concepts and principles. Report number CDI-13-023. Centre for Development Innovation. <https://edepot.wur.nl/306491>
- Xu, C., Wang, D., Zhang, S., Guo, E., Luo, H., Zhang, Z., & Yu, H. (2021). Effect of Lignin Modifier on Engineering Performance of Bituminous Binder and Mixture. *Polymers*, 13(7), 1083. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13071083>
- Zhang, Haiwei & Hao, pw & Pang, Yuan & Mwanza, Aaron. (2016). Design Method and Cost-Benefit Analysis of Hybrid Fiber Used in Asphalt Concrete. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2016, 1-9. 10.1155/2016/8014704.
- Zhang, Xueqian & Thomsen, Marianne. (2021). Techno-economic and environmental assessment of novel biorefinery designs for sequential extraction of high-value biomolecules from brown macroalgae *Laminaria digitata*, *Fucus vesiculosus*, and *Saccharina latissima*. *Algal Research*, 60, 102499. 10.1016/j.algal.2021.102499.

6. GLOSSARY

Definitions of the most common terms and their related abbreviations (if any) used in this report presented in alphabetical order.

Bio-based innovation: a new product, process or service based on biological resources and/or biological processing methods.

Biocapacity (BC): the capacity of ecosystems to regenerate what people demand from those ecosystems. Life, including human life, competes for space. The biocapacity of a particular surface represents its ability to regenerate what people demand. Biocapacity is therefore the ecosystems' capacity to produce biological materials used by people and to absorb waste material generated by humans, under current management schemes and extraction technologies. Biocapacity can change from year to year due to climate, management, and also what portions are considered useful inputs to the human economy. The biocapacity of an area is calculated by multiplying the actual physical area by the yield factor and the appropriate equivalence factor. Biocapacity is usually expressed in global hectares.

Bioeconomy: according to the European Commission 2018 Bioeconomy strategy (EC, 2018), "The bioeconomy covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles. It includes and interlinks land and marine ecosystems and the services they provide; all primary production sectors that use and produce biological resources (agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture); and all economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources and processes to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy and services. To be successful, the European bioeconomy needs to have sustainability and circularity at its heart. This will drive the renewal of our industries, the modernization of our primary production systems, the protection of the environment and will enhance biodiversity".

Carbon Footprint: it refers to the environmental externality related to the amount of CO₂ emissions released into the atmosphere by each economic sector. The carbon Footprint considers 1) emissions from fossil fuel combustion by economic sector; 2) emissions from non-fossil fuel sources (gas flaring, anthropogenic forest fires, cement production and unsustainable biofuel production²¹; and 3) emissions from international marine and aviation transport, named "bunker fuel". It is measured in t CO₂ and thus it does not capture other GHG emissions (e.g., CH₄, etc), offering an underestimation of the climate impact of sectoral activities.

Cropland Footprint: it refers to the environmental externality related to the amount of arable land and permanent crops required to produce crop products, including livestock feed, fishmeal, oil crops, and rubber, used by each economic sector. It is measured in hectares (ha).

Direct Footprint intensity: it accounts for the direct environmental externalities (i.e. footprint demands) per unit of output in each economic sector.

Ecological Footprint Accounting Framework (EFA): the Ecological Footprint Accounting Framework is an environmental accounting tool introduced in the late 90's by Mathis Wackernagel and William Rees (Wackernagel and Rees, 1996). It starts from the recognition that the Earth is a thermodynamically closed and physically finite system and consequently it has a limited capacity to provide the natural resources that support all life on it. The tool thus measures the extent to which humanity is exceeding the planetary

²¹ According to IEA, unsustainable biofuel production is the part of the total production that is not balanced by biomass re-growth (approximately 10% of total according to IPCC Sink/Source Category 5).

boundaries and can be used to investigate issues such as the limits of resource consumption, the international distribution of the world's natural resources and how to address the sustainability of natural resources use across the planet. EFA integrates the **principles of sustainability** drawn from H. Daly (Daly, 1990)²² as well as the accounting **principles of additivity**²³ and **equivalence**²⁴ (Lin et al., 2018). Using these principles, EFA tracks the supply (biocapacity) and demand (Ecological Footprint) of renewable resources and ecosystem services of 6 main land types: cropland, grazing land, forest land, fishing ground, built-up land, and carbon Footprint (aka carbon uptake land).

Ecological Footprint (EF): it represents the demand side of the EFA methodology. It is a measure of the demand placed on the biosphere by the human population and its activities, given the prevailing technology and resource management.

EE-MRIO: the Environmental Extended Multi Regional Input Output analysis is a methodological framework that combines monetary and physical units of goods and services traded among countries and regions with multiple environmental externalities. It adopts a consumption perspective, and it is able to investigate multiple environmental pressures.

Equivalence Factors (EQF): according to the Ecological Footprint accounting framework (Wackernagel et al., 1999, Galli et al., 2007, Borucke et al., 2013, Lin et al., 2018), Equivalence Factors express the ratio between a given land type's average global productivity and the average global productivity of the entire planet's productive surfaces. EQF makes it possible to compare the land used for a given product category with the average global bio-productive surface area, which may be of higher or lower average productivity. EQFs are land specific and vary by year showing the productivity difference among land-use categories at the global level. Visit <https://www.footprintnetwork.org/> for more information

Forest Footprint: it refers to the environmental externality related to the area of forests needed by each sector to supply fuelwood and timber for forest products. It is measured in hectares (ha).

GTAP: The Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) is a global network of researchers and policy makers conducting quantitative analysis of international policy issues. GTAP's goal is to improve the quality of quantitative analysis of global economic issues within an economy-wide framework. See <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/about/project.asp>

Global hectares (gha): global hectares are the unit of measure of the EFA, where one gha represents one hectare with the world average biological productivity. The YFs and EQFs allow to express the consumption of natural resources and ecosystem services in global hectares of different land use types as standardized and cross-country comparable unit of measure that can be added into a single number.

Innovation: a new or improved product, process, or service that creates an added value for customers or society.

Total Footprint intensity: it accounts for both direct and indirect environmental externalities throughout the entire global supply chain linked to the final demand.

²² **Principles of sustainability** by H. Daly are: (1) renewable resources must not be consumed faster than they are regenerated; and (2) waste must not be created faster than it is assimilated by natural systems;

²³ **Principle of additivity:** given that human life competes for biologically productive surfaces, these surface areas can be summed;

²⁴ **Principle of equivalence:** biologically productive areas vary in their ability to produce biological flows. Therefore, areas are scaled proportionally to their biological productivity.

Yield Factors (Yfs): according to the Ecological Footprint accounting framework (Wackernagel et al.,1999, Galli et al., 2007, Borucke et al., 2013, Lin et al, 2018), Yield Factors express the ratio between national average yield and world average yield per each land type of the methodology (i.e. cropland, grazing land, forest land, fishing ground, built-up land, and carbon uptake land). Yfs are thus country specific and vary by land use type and year.

7. ANNEXES

Annex 1 – Available upon request

Annex 1 is an excel file showing the GTAP concordance table. GTAP sectors are associated to more commonly used sector classifications such as the Central Product Classification (CPC) and the International Standard Industry Classification (ISIC). Also, in the first column GTAP sectors are consolidated into broader categories identified by more general and colloquial names for the purposes of the task.

Annex 2. Top 10 countries' contributing to the Ecological Footprint of the top 3 sectors (Construction, Accommodation, food and service, and food product nec).

Construction Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Ecological Footprint		Total EF Intensity [gha/m\$]	Final Demand		Population	
		[gha]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]		[%]
1	France	30,278,108	14.8%	99	300,245	19.4%	65,923,756	12.3%
2	Germany	29,355,509	14.4%	114	241,444	15.6%	81,489,703	15.3%
3	Turkey	18,725,180	9.2%	232	80,662	5.2%	77,030,602	14.4%
4	Italy	16,164,272	7.9%	89	179,042	11.6%	59,619,102	11.2%
5	Poland	11,483,782	5.6%	185	61,835	4.0%	38,293,102	7.2%
6	Sweden	10,677,875	5.2%	228	46,888	3.0%	9,689,380	1.8%
7	Spain	10,537,307	5.2%	66	158,123	10.2%	46,521,801	8.7%
8	Finland	9,944,033	4.9%	365	27,423	1.8%	5,459,720	1.0%
9	Netherlands	8,502,810	4.2%	126	66,910	4.3%	16,889,400	3.2%
10	Belgium	8,320,628	4.1%	161	51,724	3.3%	11,219,200	2.1%
		204,158,018	75.4%	132	1,548,128	78.4%	412,135,765	77.2%

Accommodation, Food, service activities Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Ecological Footprint		Total EF Intensity [gha/m\$]	Final Demand		Population	
		[gha]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]		[%]
1	Italy	20,475,758	13.4%	134	152,617	16.8%	59,619,102	11.2%
2	Germany	20,056,145	13.2%	119	168,210	18.5%	81,489,703	15.3%
3	France	19,101,520	12.5%	122	156,585	17.2%	65,923,756	12.3%
4	Spain	17,597,603	11.5%	169	104,411	11.5%	46,521,801	8.7%
5	Turkey	14,989,058	9.8%	304	49,378	5.4%	77,030,602	14.4%
6	Poland	6,892,177	4.5%	290	23,777	2.6%	38,293,102	7.2%
7	Netherlands	6,645,967	4.4%	158	41,980	4.6%	16,889,400	3.2%
8	Belgium	6,277,704	4.1%	340	18,452	2.0%	11,219,200	2.1%
9	Ireland	3,876,236	2.5%	232	11,925	1.3%	4,686,350	0.9%
10	Austria	3,852,872	2.5%	145	26,599	2.9%	8,633,220	1.6%
		152,460,086	78.6%	168	908,493	83.0%	410,306,235	76.8%

Food products nec Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Ecological Footprint		Total EF Intensity [gha/m\$]	Final Demand		Population	
		[gha]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]		[%]
1	Germany	36,976,151	24.7%	455	75,332	24.7%	81,489,703	15.3%
2	France	18,612,450	12.4%	293	51,855	17.0%	65,923,756	12.3%
3	Spain	16,542,349	11.0%	469	30,879	10.1%	46,521,801	8.7%
4	Turkey	13,465,610	9.0%	884	15,297	5.0%	77,030,602	14.4%
5	Italy	10,230,561	6.8%	371	26,227	8.6%	59,619,102	11.2%
6	Belgium	7,266,344	4.9%	473	14,062	4.6%	11,219,200	2.1%
7	Poland	6,285,714	4.2%	576	10,878	3.6%	38,293,102	7.2%
8	Netherlands	5,373,012	3.6%	471	10,383	3.4%	16,889,400	3.2%
9	Norway	4,075,231	2.7%	842	5,572	1.8%	5,140,310	1.0%
10	Greece	4,073,719	2.7%	415	9,257	3.0%	11,264,700	2.1%
		149,732,729	82.1%	491	305,054	81.9%	413,391,675	77.4%

Annex 3. Carbon Footprint of the EEA-32 region by GTAP economic sectors.

Sector #	Sector Name	Carbon Footprint			2004-2014 var.	Total Footprint Intensity		Final Demand	
		[tCO ₂]	[%]			[tCO ₂]	[m\$]	[%]	
49	Construction	378,332,454	10.0%	-17%	244	1,548,128	9.8%		
52	Transport nec	306,156,548	8.1%	-2%	833	367,633	2.3%		
46	Electricity	256,939,091	6.8%	-31%	1809	142,034	0.9%		
50	Trade	227,008,208	6.0%	-15%	152	1,498,034	9.4%		
51	Accommodation, Food and service activities	174,995,594	4.6%	-19%	193	908,493	5.7%		
40	Computer, electronic and optical products	169,178,353	4.5%	18%	618	273,825	1.7%		
64	Human health and social work activities	167,235,708	4.4%	-9%	102	1,634,373	10.3%		
54	Air transport	157,994,277	4.2%	-10%	1459	108,298	0.7%		
42	Machinery and equipment nec	148,411,928	3.9%	-24%	398	372,543	2.3%		
43	Motor vehicles and parts	145,788,330	3.9%	-13%	387	376,951	2.4%		
62	Public Administration and defense	137,604,009	3.6%	-11%	100	1,377,434	8.7%		
28	Wearing apparel	114,851,482	3.0%	43%	623	184,398	1.2%		
56	Communication	98,427,259	2.6%	-24%	125	789,381	5.0%		
25	Food products nec	98,182,891	2.6%	-12%	322	305,054	1.9%		
45	Manufactures nec	97,391,316	2.6%	17%	382	254,626	1.6%		
33	Chemical products	88,793,548	2.4%	-5%	620	143,201	0.9%		
61	Recreational and other services	76,443,943	2.0%	-19%	134	571,197	3.6%		
32	Petroleum, coal products	75,491,852	2.0%	-9%	676	111,597	0.7%		
63	Education	72,897,689	1.9%	-16%	99	734,415	4.6%		
41	Electrical equipment	66,549,040	1.8%	107%	503	132,248	0.8%		
60	Business services nec	56,111,596	1.5%	-22%	123	454,709	2.9%		
44	Transport equipment nec	51,942,204	1.4%	8%	377	137,806	0.9%		
26	Beverages and tobacco products	50,196,331	1.3%	-16%	314	159,864	1.0%		
39	Metal products	41,729,056	1.1%	-17%	455	91,692	0.6%		
59	Real estate activities	41,365,852	1.1%	-19%	81	512,147	3.2%		
53	Water transport	36,046,015	1.0%	-10%	1275	28,280	0.2%		
22	Dairy products	35,926,586	1.0%	-12%	285	126,128	0.8%		
29	Leather products	33,953,452	0.9%	8%	507	66,904	0.4%		
65	Dwellings	32,502,624	0.9%	-8%	29	1,128,331	7.1%		
20	Meat products nec	31,054,804	0.8%	-14%	264	117,697	0.7%		
35	Rubber and plastic products	28,595,831	0.8%	6%	436	65,528	0.4%		
27	Textiles	28,147,326	0.7%	-38%	518	54,325	0.3%		
36	Mineral products nec	23,566,425	0.6%	-18%	909	25,926	0.2%		
34	Basic pharmaceutical products	19,781,648	0.5%	-2%	237	83,590	0.5%		
19	Bovine meat products	19,739,502	0.5%	-15%	267	73,855	0.5%		
4	Vegetables, fruit, nuts	18,284,261	0.5%	-28%	243	75,156	0.5%		
31	Paper products, publishing	17,618,284	0.5%	-31%	335	52,618	0.3%		
57	Financial services nec	16,985,695	0.5%	-22%	72	236,922	1.5%		
58	Insurance (formerly isr)	16,465,078	0.4%	-25%	74	222,058	1.4%		
55	Warehousing and support activities	15,856,006	0.4%	-5%	225	70,359	0.4%		
48	Water	15,389,884	0.4%	-11%	228	67,466	0.4%		
47	Gas manufacture, distribution	13,031,546	0.3%	6%	1000	13,030	0.1%		
21	Vegetable oils and fats	10,117,598	0.3%	2%	446	22,676	0.1%		
30	Wood products	6,579,312	0.2%	-40%	376	17,495	0.1%		
14	Fishing	6,008,227	0.2%	-49%	433	13,883	0.1%		
2	Wheat	5,831,584	0.2%	-8%	482	12,095	0.1%		
8	Crops nec	5,279,600	0.1%	-50%	343	15,391	0.1%		
24	Sugar	4,446,295	0.1%	-15%	337	13,205	0.1%		
3	Cereal grains nec	3,510,553	0.1%	-8%	811	4,328	0.0%		
10	Animal products nec	3,456,476	0.1%	-32%	287	12,056	0.1%		
11	Raw milk	3,054,947	0.1%	-28%	214	14,261	0.1%		
17	Gas	2,857,410	0.1%	-5%	169	16,883	0.1%		
13	Forestry	2,523,702	0.1%	-20%	231	10,929	0.1%		
5	Oil seeds	2,273,464	0.1%	42%	926	2,455	0.0%		
7	Plant-based fibers	2,127,952	0.1%	-42%	873	2,438	0.0%		
37	Ferrous metals	1,978,044	0.1%	-40%	751	2,634	0.0%		
38	Metals nec	1,957,212	0.1%	-76%	660	2,965	0.0%		
18	Other Extraction (formerly omn Minerals nec)	1,844,078	0.0%	-18%	374	4,930	0.0%		
15	Coal	921,121	0.0%	-4%	538	1,712	0.0%		
12	Wool, silk-worm cocoons	847,905	0.0%	144%	542	1,564	0.0%		
23	Processed rice	752,180	0.0%	-26%	324	2,321	0.0%		
9	Bovine cattle, sheep and goats, horses	624,579	0.0%	-17%	285	2,188	0.0%		
6	Sugar cane, sugar beet	428,372	0.0%	-59%	484	885	0.0%		
16	Oil	14,863	0.0%	20%	526	28	0.0%		
1	Paddy rice	5,137	0.0%	-58%	269	19	0.0%		
Total		3,770,404,136	100%	-12%	237	15,875,590	100%		

Annex 4. Top 10 countries' contributions to the carbon Footprint of the top 3 sectors (Construction, Transport nec, and Electricity).

Construction Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Carbon Footprint		Total Carbon Intensity [tCO ₂ /m\$]	Final Demand	
		[tCO ₂]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Germany	60,355,643	16.0%	232	241,444	15.6%
2	France	51,237,105	13.5%	167	300,245	19.4%
3	Turkey	45,968,611	12.2%	570	80,662	5.2%
4	Italy	37,736,720	10.0%	208	179,042	11.6%
5	Spain	22,910,841	6.1%	143	158,123	10.2%
6	Poland	22,668,519	6.0%	365	61,835	4.0%
7	Netherlands	18,356,682	4.9%	272	66,910	4.3%
8	Belgium	16,048,120	4.2%	310	51,724	3.3%
9	Switzerland	12,843,534	3.4%	203	63,223	4.1%
10	Romania	11,208,987	3.0%	381	29,344	1.9%
		378,332,454	79.1%	244	1,548,128	79.6%

Transport nec Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Carbon Footprint		Total Carbon Intensity [tCO ₂ /m\$]	Final Demand	
		[tCO ₂]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Italy	54,306,602	17.7%	944	57,116	15.5%
2	Germany	41,125,671	13.4%	944	43,323	11.8%
3	Turkey	32,576,765	10.6%	779	41,808	11.4%
4	France	29,840,465	9.7%	626	45,383	12.3%
5	Poland	24,809,313	8.1%	1,475	16,915	4.6%
6	Spain	16,698,253	5.5%	581	28,681	7.8%
7	Netherlands	14,611,114	4.8%	915	15,657	4.3%
8	Switzerland	9,079,918	3.0%	717	11,113	3.0%
9	Belgium	8,921,850	2.9%	550	16,182	4.4%
10	Austria	8,602,755	2.8%	668	12,485	3.4%
		306,156,548	78.6%	833	367,633	78.5%

Electricity Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Carbon Footprint		Total Carbon Intensity [tCO ₂ /m\$]	Final Demand	
		[tCO ₂]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Germany	52,273,338	20.3%	2,265	23,204	16.3%
2	Poland	30,507,399	11.9%	3,471	8,811	6.2%
3	Turkey	29,560,876	11.5%	4,559	6,484	4.6%
4	France	24,408,212	9.5%	1,168	20,898	14.7%
5	Czech Republic	16,130,425	6.3%	4,332	3,904	2.7%
6	Italy	15,541,121	6.0%	1,183	13,124	9.2%
7	Netherlands	9,385,712	3.7%	2,857	3,389	2.4%
8	Norway	8,099,742	3.2%	3,248	2,553	1.8%
9	Greece	7,857,510	3.1%	2,903	2,745	1.9%
10	Romania	7,662,208	3.0%	1,869	4,098	2.9%
		256,939,091	78.4%	1,809	142,034	62.8%

Annex 5. Top 10 countries' contributions to the cropland Footprint of the top 3 sectors (Food products, Accommodation, Food, service activities, Wheat).

Food products Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Cropland Footprint		Total Cropland Intensity [hectare/m\$]	Final Demand	
		[hectare]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Germany	8,734,569	24.4%	109	75,332	24.7%
2	France	4,394,198	12.3%	71	51,855	17.0%
3	Turkey	4,310,866	12.0%	284	15,297	5.0%
4	Spain	3,975,176	11.1%	124	30,879	10.1%
5	Italy	2,385,018	6.7%	87	26,227	8.6%
6	Belgium	1,827,315	5.1%	122	14,062	4.6%
7	Poland	1,508,307	4.2%	142	10,878	3.6%
8	Netherlands	1,320,162	3.7%	122	10,383	3.4%
9	Greece	1,009,029	2.8%	104	9,257	3.0%
10	Romania	745,236	2.1%	104	6,937	2.3%
		35,855,132	84.3%	118	305,054	82.3%

Accommodation, Food, service activities Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Cropland Footprint		Total Cropland Intensity [hectare/m\$]	Final Demand	
		[hectare]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Spain	3,439,509	15.3%	33	104,411	11.5%
2	Italy	3,068,823	13.7%	20	152,617	16.8%
3	Turkey	2,640,030	11.8%	53	49,378	5.4%
4	France	2,412,340	10.7%	15	156,585	17.2%
5	Germany	2,124,549	9.5%	13	168,210	18.5%
6	Belgium	1,343,497	6.0%	73	18,452	2.0%
7	Netherlands	1,028,579	4.6%	24	41,980	4.6%
8	Poland	870,830	3.9%	37	23,777	2.6%
9	Austria	637,102	2.8%	24	26,599	2.9%
10	Portugal	634,684	2.8%	36	17,119	1.9%
		22,448,757	81.1%	25	908,493	83.6%

Wheat Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Cropland Footprint		Total Cropland Intensity [hectare/m\$]	Final Demand	
		[hectare]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Italy	3,868,388	18.2%	1,051	2,912	24.1%
2	Turkey	3,812,004	18.0%	1,565	2,435	20.1%
3	Germany	3,325,618	15.7%	2,062	1,607	13.3%
4	Spain	2,050,426	9.7%	1,527	1,074	8.9%
5	France	1,684,035	7.9%	1,942	869	7.2%
6	Poland	1,666,892	7.9%	2,202	755	6.2%
7	Greece	735,899	3.5%	1,091	497	4.1%
8	Belgium	532,901	2.5%	2,115	272	2.2%
9	Czech Republic	530,325	2.5%	2,259	235	1.9%
10	Hungary	453,684	2.1%	2,414	189	1.6%
		21,226,316	87.9%	1,755	12,095	89.7%

Annex 6. Top 10 countries' contributions to the forest Footprint of the top 3 sectors (Forestry, Construction, Manufactures).

Forestry Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Forest Footprint		Total Forest Intensity [hectare/m\$]	Final Demand	
		[hectare]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Germany	9,950,646	18.1%	4,752	2,044	18.7%
2	France	6,555,724	12.0%	4,266	1,487	13.6%
3	Turkey	6,089,563	11.1%	5,190	1,173	10.7%
4	Finland	4,993,058	9.1%	6,869	726	6.6%
5	Poland	4,782,436	8.7%	8,083	594	5.4%
6	Romania	4,613,408	8.4%	6,183	746	6.8%
7	Sweden	3,195,074	5.8%	6,381	502	4.6%
8	Italy	2,734,899	5.0%	2,044	1,222	11.2%
9	Austria	1,984,880	3.6%	3,984	480	4.4%
10	Spain	1,325,709	2.4%	4,481	295	2.7%
		54,826,993	84.3%	5,017	10,929	84.8%

Construction Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Forest Footprint		Total Forest Intensity [hectare/m\$]	Final Demand	
		[hectare]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	France	7,575,070	16.2%	25	300,245	19.4%
2	Sweden	6,068,770	13.0%	132	46,888	3.0%
3	Finland	5,873,760	12.6%	217	27,423	1.8%
4	Germany	5,171,236	11.1%	20	241,444	15.6%
5	Norway	2,831,722	6.1%	60	47,606	3.1%
6	Poland	2,352,339	5.0%	38	61,835	4.0%
7	Austria	1,786,147	3.8%	49	36,642	2.4%
8	Turkey	1,675,508	3.6%	21	80,662	5.2%
9	Belgium	1,609,655	3.4%	31	51,724	3.3%
10	Italy	1,584,784	3.4%	9	179,042	11.6%
		46,791,933	78.1%	30	1,548,128	69.3%

Manufactures Sector: Top 10 Countries' Contributions in EEA 32

	Country	Total Forest Footprint		Total Forest Intensity [hectare/m\$]	Final Demand	
		[hectare]	[%]		[m\$]	[%]
1	Germany	3,519,644	24.4%	30	71,653	28.1%
2	France	1,328,902	9.2%	34	28,717	11.3%
3	Turkey	1,186,354	8.2%	65	17,612	6.9%
4	Poland	1,140,541	7.9%	152	8,734	3.4%
5	Italy	1,128,916	7.8%	35	25,045	9.8%
6	Belgium	1,064,741	7.4%	32	16,718	6.6%
7	Switzerland	920,644	6.4%	26	24,226	9.5%
8	Spain	708,628	4.9%	32	14,759	5.8%
9	Sweden	433,565	3.0%	64	5,298	2.1%
10	Austria	399,252	2.8%	46	7,151	2.8%
		14,406,489	82.1%	57	254,626	86.4%

Annex 7 – Available upon request

Annex 7 is an excel file showing the full list of bio-based innovations resulting from the literature research conducted during the work.

Annex 8 – Available upon request

Annex 8 is an excel file showing a reduced list of 67 bio-based innovations resulting from the first selection criteria applied during the work.

Annex 9 – Available upon request

Annex 9 is an excel file showing the priority list of 38 bio-based innovations resulting from the second selection criteria.

Annex 10 – Available upon request

Annex 10 is an excel file showing the final list of 23 selected bio-based innovations with the full analysis of their implementation and scalability potential to be game changing for a greener Europe.

European Topic Centre on
Biodiversity and ecosystems
<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-be>

The European Topic Centre on Biodiversity and ecosystems (ETC-BE) is a consortium of European institutes under contract of the European Environment Agency.

